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PROMETEO

A **PRO**babilistic fra**ME**work for coas**T**al and harbor
d**E**fense in the c**O**ntext of climate change

D1.1

Report on existing regulations and guidelines for the design of coastal and harbor defense solutions, main existing formulations for the description of failure mechanisms and options for adaptation to climate change

WP1 -Critical review - Design approaches for coastal and harbor defense solutions

M1.1 - Critical review of existing design regulations, formulations and adaptation solutions

O1

Task 1.1 – Task 1.2 – Task 1.3

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List of symbols and acronyms

Symbols

<i>Symbol</i>	<i>UM</i>	<i>Description</i>
A	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the formula of Burcharth et al. (1998)
A_{EBP}	[m ^{1/3}]	Scale parameter mainly dependent on sediment characteristics
A_c	[m]	Armor crest freeboard without crown wall
A_e	[m ²]	Eroded area of a cross-section of the rubble mound breakwater
A_N	[m ^{1/3}]	Scale parameter for the native sediments
A_F	[m ^{1/3}]	Scale parameter for the fill material
A_R	[m ^{1/3}]	Shape parameter depending on wave and sediment characteristics
a	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the formula of Powell and Allsop (1985)
a_G	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the formula of Goda (2009)
a_M	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the formula of Mase et al. (2013)
a_S	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the formula of Melby and Kobayashi (1998)
a_{WB}	[-]	Weibull's distribution scale parameter
a_0	[-]	Parameter to calculate K_L
B	[m]	Toe berm width
B_b	[m]	Width of the berm of the foundation cliff
B_c	[m]	Width of the structure
B_{eq}	[m]	Equivalent width of the cliff berm
B_h	[m]	Berm of fill height
B_m	[m]	Width of the berm of the foundation reef
B'_m	[m]	$\max \{l - (d - d'), 0\}$
B_R	[m ^{-3/2}]	Shape parameter depending on wave and sediment characteristics
B_{rel}	[-]	Part of the berm that has an influence on the breaking depth
B_{RMB}	[m]	Width of a section of the rubble mound breakwater
b	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the formula of Powell and Allsop (1985)
b_G	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the formula of Goda (2009)
b_M	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the formula of Mase et al. (2013)
b_{MK}	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the formula of Melby and Kobayashi (1998)
a_{WB}	[-]	Weibull's distribution shape parameter
C_b	[m/s]	Wave celerity in shallow water
C_R	[m ^{1/3}]	Shape parameter depending on wave and sediment characteristics
C_p	[-]	Coefficient of permeability (Etemad-Shahidi et al., 2020)
C_V	[-]	Stability coefficient for seebees
CV	[%]	Coefficient of variation
c	[-]	Empirical parameter to calculate t_d
c_{Pl}	[-]	Empirical coefficient for armor layer stability formulas in plunging wave conditions
c_M	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the formula of Mase et al. (2013)
c_S	[-]	Empirical coefficient for armor layer stability formulas in surging wave conditions
c_{sub}	[-]	Empirical coefficient of the formula of van der Meer (1991)
D	[m]	Depth measured at a distance of one wavelength from the wall
D_n	[m]	Diameter of the artificial armor units
D_{n50}	[m]	Median nominal diameter of the armor units
$D_{n50core}$	[m]	Median nominal diameter of core material

D_R	[m ^{-3/2}]	Shape parameter depending on wave and sediment characteristics
d	[m]	Depth measured directly in front of the vertical breakwater
d'	[m]	Depth of the dissipation chamber
d_B	[m]	Breaking depth
d_b	[m]	Toe berm height with the MWL
d_c	[m]	Depth of closure
d_{c*}	[m]	Depth of closure in the formula of Yoshida et al. (2014)
d_{eff}	[m]	Effective calculation depth
d_{50}	[m]	Median grain size
ERI	[-]	Economic Repercussion Index
F_h	[kN/m]	Horizontal wave force acting
F_h^*	[-]	Non-dimensional horizontal wave force
$F_{h,imp,1/250}$	[kN/m]	Total horizontal force impacting the structure (referring to an overtopping level of 1/250)
$F_{h,q,1/250}$	[kN/m]	Total horizontal force impacting the structure (referring to an overtopping level of 1/250) in the case of quasi-static wave motion
$F_{h,max}$	[kN/m]	Maximum horizontal wave force
$F_{h,max}^*$	[-]	Non-dimensional maximum horizontal wave force
$F_{h,q}$	[kN/m]	Quasi-static horizontal wave force
$F_{u,max}$	[kN/m]	Maximum value of the lifting force
f	[-]	Generic function
f_i	[-]	Reduction factor of D_{n50} for low-crested structures
$f_{\underline{X}}$	[-]	n-dimensional probability density functions of the variables \underline{X}
G_c	[m]	Rubble-mound breakwater crest width
g	[m/s ²]	Gravity acceleration
H	[m]	Wave height
H_b	[m]	Wave height at breaking
H_{bs}	[m]	Maximum wave height separating impulsive waves by already broken waves
H_{Des}	[m]	Design wave height
H_i or H_{inc}	[m]	Incident wave height
H_{local}	[m]	Local wave height
H_{max}	[m]	Maximum height reached among 250 incident waves of a sea state
H_s or $H_{1/3}$	[m]	Significant wave height
H_{si}	[m]	Significant wave height at depth h_s
$H_{s,TOE}$	[m]	Significant wave height at the toe of the structure
H_{s0}	[m]	Deep-water significant wave height
$H_{s,12}$	[m]	Mean annual significant wave height which occurs 12 hours per year on average
$H_{1/10}$	[m]	Average wave height of the $N/10$ highest waves in a sea state
$H_{1/20}$	[m]	Average wave height of the $N/20$ highest waves in a sea state
$H_{2\%}$	[m]	Wave height exceeded by 2% of the incident waves at the toe
h	[m]	Water depth
h_b	[m]	Wave breaking depth
h_c	[m]	Height measured between SWL and the top of the caisson wall
h_r	[m]	Water depth at the intercepting profile point
h_s	[m]	Depth measured at the base of the structure
h_t	[m]	Toe berm submergence
h_{TOE}	[m]	Water depth at the toe of the structure
h'	[m]	height of the vertical wall breakwater

h'_c	[m]	Height of the structure from seabed level
h^*	[-]	Impulsiveness parameter (EurOtop Manual, 2018)
h_o	[m]	Height of the center of the clapotis orbit above SWL
h_s	[m]	Depth measured at the base of the structure
h_{toe}	[m]	Water depth measured at the foot of the vertical wall
h_{5H_s}	[m]	Depth measured off the structure, at a distance of $5H_s$ from the wall
K	[-]	Generic empirical coefficient for the calculation of N_s
K_a	[-]	Coefficient related to the size of the air cushion
K_D	[-]	Stability coefficient
K_L	[-]	Coefficient that takes into account the percentage of air trapped in the breaking wave
K_m	[-]	Correction factor related to the mass
k	[-]	Wave number
k'	[-]	Coefficient to calculate t_r
k_b	[-]	Empirical correction factor to calculate H_b
k_r	[-]	Reflection coefficient of the structure
$k_{r,Fh}$	[-]	Parameter referring to the time development of the impact forces on the vertical wall
k_t	[1/m]	Transmission coefficient
k_w	[-]	Ratio between M_{imp} and M_{wave}
k_{wm}	[-]	Parameter of water mass involved in the impact
L	[m]	Wavelength
L'	[m]	Wavelength at depth d'
L_b	[m]	Wavelength of the breaking wave
L_D	[m]	Wavelength at depth D
L_{Des}	[m]	Design wavelength
L_{berm}	[m]	Characteristic width of the toe berm
L_{hs}	[m]	wavelength at depth h_s
$L_{m-1,0,TOE}$	[m]	Deep-water wavelength related to $T_{m-1,0,TOE}$
$L_{p,DEEP}$	[m]	Deep-water wavelength related to T_p
L_{pi}	[m]	Wavelength at depth h_s (at the base of the cliff) and relative to the peak period T_p
l	[m]	Width of the dissipation chamber
I_{dFh}	[kN s/m]	Momentum of the water mass involved in the impact
l_{Fh}	[m]	Arm of the horizontal forc
I_{rFh}	[kN s/m]	Momentum of the total mass involved in the wave breaking
l_{Fu}	[m]	Lifting force arm
M_{fmax}	[N/m]	Nonlinear maximum wave momentum flux
M_{imp}	[kg]	Mass of water which hits the wall
M_{wave}	[kg]	Total mass of the breaking wave
m	[-]	Foreshore slope
m_{rel}	[-]	Portion of the escarpment that has an influence on the breaking depth
N	[-]	Number of waves of a sea state
N_d	[-]	Percentage of displaced units (Hudson, 1959)
N_i	[-]	number of waves in the stress range i
N_m	[-]	Admissible average number of operational stoppages
N_{moved}	[-]	Number of displaced armor units inside the considered area
N_{od}	[-]	Number of displaced armor units within a strip of breakwater slope
N_{OW}	[-]	Number of overtopping waves

N_s	[-]	Stability number
N_{tot}	[-]	Total number of armor units inside the considered area
n	[-]	Number of elements
n_i	[-]	Number of waves occurring during the design life of the structure, in the stress range i
n_T	[-]	Total number of stress ranges considered
n_v	[-]	Armor layer porosity
OIER	[-]	Operational Index of Economic Repercussion
OISER	[-]	Operational Index of Social and Environmental Repercussion
P	[-]	Notional permeability (van der Meer, 1988a)
P_b	[%]	Probability of exceedance of the breaking wave height
P_D	[kN/m ²]	Wave dynamic pressure
P_f	[-]	Failure probability of a generic system
P_{fi}	[-]	Failure probability of the i -th element of the series system
$P_{f,l}$	[-]	Lower bound of the total failure probability of a system
$P_{f,u}$	[-]	Upper bound of the total failure probability of a system
P_i	[%]	Percentage of waves breaking directly on the structure
P_o	[kN/m ²]	Atmospheric pressure
P_{OW}	[-]	Probability of wave overtopping
P_{SW}	[-]	Petameter depending on the degree of stability of the waves (Tuozzo et al., 2024)
P_u	[kN/m ²]	Underpressure acting on the foundation base of the vertical structure
P_1	[kN/m ²]	Wave pressure at the undisturbed sea level
P_2	[kN/m ²]	Wave pressure at seabed level
P_3	[kN/m ²]	Wave pressure at the base of the vertical wall
P_4	[kN/m ²]	Wave pressure at the highest point of the loaded breakwater
P'_1	[kN/m ²]	Pressure at the undisturbed sea level (wave trough phase)
P'_2	[kN/m ²]	Pressure at seabed level (wave trough phase)
p	[kN/m ²]	Wave pressure
p_i	various	Generic parameter influencing the structure stability
p_{max}	[kN/m ²]	Maximum pressure at the wall
p_{ru}	[kN/m ²]	Pressure on the outer land-side edge of the foundation
p_u	[kN/m ²]	Pressure on the outer sea-side edge of the foundation
p_o	[kN/m ²]	Dynamic wave pressure at the base of the structure
p_1	[kN/m ²]	Peak pressure at the depth to the SWL equal to $0.5H_b$
q	[m ³ /s m]	Mean wave overtopping discharge
R	[-]	Resistance of the structure
R_A	[-]	Fill factor
R_f	[-]	Renourishment factor
R_c	[m]	Structure freeboard
R_D	[kN/m]	Total force resulting from the dynamic pressure distribution
R_d	[-]	Design value of the resistance of the structure
R_{MAX}	[m]	Run-up height not exceeded in $p\%$ of cases in runs of 100 waves
R_n	[-]	Nominal value of the resistance of the structure
R_S	[kN/m]	Total force resulting from the hydrostatic pressure distribution
$R_{2\%}$	[m]	Mean of the 2% of the maximum values of wave run-up
$R_{99\%}$	[m]	Mean of the 99% of the maximum values of wave run-up
r	[-]	Dolos weight ratio
r_b	[-]	Ration between B and L_{berm}
$r_{f,OLS}$	[-]	Required minimum operationality

S	[-]	External solicitations
\bar{S}	[-]	Time-varying damage in the formula of Melby and Kobayashi (1998)
S_{BA}	[-]	Eroded armor layer per unit length (Broderick and Ahrens, 1982)
S_N	[m]	Height of beach nourishment
S_n	[-]	Nominal value of the external solicitations
S_d	[-]	Design value of the external solicitations
SERI	[-]	Social and environmental repercussion index
SLR	[m]	Sea level rise
s	[-]	Wave steepness
s_m	[-]	Wave steepness calculated using T_m
s_{mc}	[-]	Critical wave steepness referred to s_m
$s_{m-1,0}$	[-]	Wave steepness calculated using $T_{m-1,0}$
s_p	[-]	Wave steepness calculated using T_p
T	[s]	Wave period
T_m	[s]	Mean wave period
$T_{m-1,0}$	[s]	Spectral wave period
$T_{m-1,0,TOE}$	[s]	Spectral wave period at the toe of the structure
T_p	[s]	Peak wave period
$T_{1/3}$ or T_S	[s]	Period of the significant wave
t	[s]	Generic time
t_d	[s]	Total duration of the impulsive horizontal action
$t_{d,Fh}$	[s]	Total duration of the impulse diagram
t_r	[s]	Rise time of the horizontal force
$t_{r,Fh}$	[s]	Rise time of the impulse diagram
t_R	[s]	Time taken to reach the maximum peak value of the horizontal force, assuming linear load growth
V	[m ³]	Replenishment volume
V_{max}	[m ³ /m]	Maximum individual wave overtopping volume
V_p	[m ³ /m]	Profile change volume
W^*	[m]	Cross-shore distance to closure the depth
W_{50}	[kg]	Medium mass of the armor unit
w	[m/s]	Fall velocity
\underline{X}	various	Set of stochastic variables
x	[m]	Distance from the shore
x_r	[m]	Intercepting profile point
x_0	[m]	Origin of the shoaling profile
Y	[m]	Desired distance of beach nourishment seaward translation
Y^*	[m]	Beach width to be protected
Y_0	[m]	Dry beach width
Z	[-]	Reliability function of a failure mode
z	[m]	Generic coordinate along the z-direction
α	[°]	Structure slope angle
α_{cliff}	[°]	Slope angle of the sea-side foundation cliff
α_{GEV}	[-]	Statistical parameter of the GEV
α_I	[-]	Impulsive wave force coefficient
α_{I0}	[-]	Coefficient of the effect of the height assumed by the wave above the cliff
α_{I1}	[-]	Coefficient of the geometric shape of the wave above the cliff

α_1	[-]	Pressure coefficient dependent on the length (and period) of the design wave
α_2	[-]	Pressure coefficient dependent on the steepness of the design wave
α_3	[-]	Pressure coefficient dependent on pressure decrease with depth
α^*	[-]	Pressure coefficient relative to wave impact
β	[-]	Reliability index
β_{GEV}	[-]	Statistical parameter of the GEV
β_{OLS}	[-]	Reliability index corresponding to $r_{f,OLS}$
β_{VB}	[°]	Angle between the most dangerous direction within an interval of $\pm 15^\circ$ from the main wave direction and the line perpendicular to the frontal line of the vertical wall
γ	[-]	Generic safety factor
γ_b	[-]	Toe berm factor
γ_{br}	[-]	Petameter depending on the degree of stability of the waves (Tuozzo et al., 2024)
γ_f	[-]	Armor layer roughness factor
$\gamma_{f,surging}$	[-]	Armor layer roughness factor for surging wave conditions
γ_{GEV}	[-]	Statistical parameter of the GEV
γ_{heat}		Specific heat ratio
γ_R	[-]	Partial factor of the resistance term
γ_S	[-]	Partial factor of the solicitation term
γ_β	[-]	Direction of wave attack factor
Δ	[-]	Relative buoyant density of the armor units
Δy	[m]	Shoreline advancement
δ	[°]	Characteristic curvature assumed by the wave at breaking
δ_1	[-]	Coefficient to calculate α_{I1}
δ_{11}	[-]	Coefficient to calculate α_{I1}
δ_2	[-]	Coefficient to calculate α_{I1}
δ_{22}	[-]	Coefficient to calculate α_{I1}
η^*	[m]	Height above the SWL where the wave pressure intensity is 0
η_{ov}	[m]	$\min\{\eta^*; h_c\}$
θ	[°]	Slope angle of the berm of the foundation cliff
λ	[1/s]	Aeration factor
$\lambda_{1,2,3}$	[-]	Pressure correction factors (dependent on geometry, type of structure)
$\lambda_{S,L,R,M,U}$	[-]	Pressure correction factors (slit wall, impermeable front wall, wave chamber rear wall, wave chamber bottom slab, uplift force)
ξ	[-]	Iribarren number
ξ_{cr}	[-]	Critical Iribarren number
ξ_m	[-]	Iribarren number calculated using T_m
$\xi_{m-1,0}$	[-]	Iribarren number calculated using $T_{m-1,0}$
ξ_p	[-]	Iribarren number calculated using T_p
ρ_a	[kg/m ³]	Density of the armor units
ρ or ρ_w	[kg/m ³]	Water density
τ		Duration of the pressure pulse
φ	[%]	Packing density
Ω	[-]	Dimensionless fall velocity
ω	[s ⁻¹]	Angular frequency of waves
ω_o	[kN/m ³]	Specific gravity of seawater

$\zeta_{\frac{1}{4}}$	[m]	The highest one-fourth of water elevation distribution at the structure's location (Buccino et al., 2023)
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Acronyms

BPS	Beach profile surveys
DoC	Depth of closure
EBP	Equilibrium beach profile
LCB	Low-crested/submerged breakwaters
MWL	Mean water level
OLS	Operational limit state
RF	Reliability factor
SLR	Sea level rise
SLS	Serviceability limit state
SWL	Still water level
ULS	Ultimate limit state

1. Introduction

1.1 Statement of the problem

Coastal zones host many natural ecosystems and economic and social activities, which require protection from the action of the sea. The design of coastal and harbor defense solutions is a complex task, due to the difficulty to describe their response to wave loads as well as to include the stochastic nature of climate forcing. Nowadays, the existence of a huge number of aging defense structures and climate change-induced forcing variability highlight the need for sustainable maintenance and adaptation plans.

Uncertainties related to the non-conventional nature of historical or adapted structures and to the effects of climate change on marine climate must be properly considered during the design process. Traditional deterministic design methodologies do not take into account such uncertainties, whereas probabilistic design methods employ probability distribution functions of the involved variables to estimate the failure probability of a certain system. In the world, only a few national design guidelines started to use probabilistic approaches, which however refer just to newly built structures, while the effects of climate change are considered only in a simplified manner. In Italy, technical recommendations for maritime dikes and coastal defense solutions date back to the '90s and are still based on a deterministic approach. Moreover, though climate-aware engineering design is required, for example by EU guidelines for public work funding, no solid know-how is available to designers and decision-makers.

In this context, PROMETEO aims to foster a more resilient approach for the management of coastal areas, by developing a probabilistic design framework able to consider the uncertainties related to the response of new, existing or adapted coastal and harbor defense solutions and met-ocean forcing in a changing climate. To this scope, the critical review of existing design regulations, the collection of state-of-art design formulas, and the study of possible adaptation solutions of aging structures are carried out, with reference to four types of coastal and harbor defense solutions, namely rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls, and artificial beach nourishments.

On the basis of the information derived from the critical review of existing design regulations, a probabilistic calculation procedure will be defined for the assessment of the performances of defense interventions.

1.2 Phases of the work

The present document is organized in the following three parts:

1. Chapter 2 contains the critical review and comparative analysis of weakness and strength of existing guidelines and recommendations for the design of coastal and harbor defense solutions. The knowledge of existing design methodologies will establish the foundations for the development of a new probabilistic framework, able to deal with uncertainties related to the complexity of morphodynamic processes and of the interaction between waves and structures as well as the stochastic nature of external forcing, also in the presence of climate change;

2. Chapter 3 provides a collection of existing design formulas for the description of failure mechanisms of rubble-mound breakwaters, vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments, in order to provide an overview of the available tools for the prediction of the defense performances and of their reliability, thus allowing the identification of weaknesses and gaps to be addressed within the project;
3. Chapter 4 presents the critical review of state of art on the adaptation of existing coastal and harbor defense solutions to the effects of climate change, in order to produce a comprehensive summary of already explored interventions as well as to inspire the proposal of new strategies for the adaptation to climate change, considering possible local construction constraints and limitations.

The above-mentioned chapters are made up by a specific section for each type of coastal and harbor defense considered here, namely rubble-mound breakwaters, vertical breakwaters, seawalls, and artificial beach nourishments.

Finally, Chapter 5 provides a summary of the critical review and draws the conclusion of the presented work.

2. Critical review of design regulations for coastal and harbor defense structures

2.1 Overview

The present chapter provides the critical review of existing national and international regulations for the design of coastal and harbor defense solutions. After a general description of existing design approaches, for each considered type of coastal and harbor defense solution, namely rubble-mound breakwaters, vertical breakwaters, seawalls, and artificial beach nourishments, the main design guidelines are cited and critically discussed. The outcomes of the presented critical review will provide indications for the development of the novel probabilistic framework for the design of coastal and harbor defense solutions, which is the main objective of the project PROMETEO.

2.2 General approaches for the design of coastal and harbor defense solutions

The definition of the design requirements of a coastal or harbor defense solution is performed by setting the acceptable probability of reaching a certain limit state. Following the definition of the British Standards Institution (BSI, 1991), two limit states can be considered:

- the ultimate limit state (ULS), which represents the failure of the structure, i.e. a condition in which the breakwater no longer substantially fulfills its function of providing protection to a harbor or land area or if the cost of damage repair, including interference with commercial operations, is unacceptable;
- the serviceability limit state (SLS), which exists when damage to the breakwater of considerable magnitude has occurred, but it is still possible to carry on most normal operations inside the harbor.

In addition, the operational limit state (OLS) can be taken into account, which occurs when the exploitation of the port area is temporarily reduced or suspended because of causes external to the structure without any structural damage (Puertos del Estado, 2002, 2010, 2018).

The acceptable failure probability or the acceptable degree of damage during lifetime should be decided at the beginning of the design process, on the basis of the functions for which the solution is designed, according to the indications of standards and codes, the experience of existing structures and economic evaluations. In the following, the expression failure probability is used to generally indicate the reaching of the considered limit state (i.e. ULS, SLS or OLS).

The correct identification of the events which can potentially lead to the ULS, SLS or OLS can be performed only by carrying out a risk analysis, i.e. the analysis of all the possible failure mechanisms and their interaction, specific for each type of coastal or harbor defense solution, and often for the single case study. According to the procedure proposed by CIAD project group (1985) with reference to a generic breakwater, the following steps should be considered to perform the risk analysis:

1. editing a detailed description of the structural system, which can give the necessary information to identify all the breakwater components;

2. individual analysis of the failure of each component of the structure, in order to analyze all the possible consequences;
3. identification of the initiating events potentially responsible of the failure of the components;
4. construction of a fault tree to represent all the possible accident sequences, from initiating event via single components failure to total failure of the structure;
5. quantitative evaluation of the reliability of the structure by combining the probabilities of component failures and initiating events, according to the logical sequences defined in the fault tree.

In order to implement steps 1, 2, 3 and 4, the coastal or harbor defense solution should be considered as a system composed of single components, which can either function or fail. Depending on the interactions between these components, failure of one component can cause failure of another element and even of the total system (US Army Corps of Engineers, 2002). The so-called fault tree is the usually employed tool to simply represent the complex interactions between the components and external events that can potentially trigger a failure mode. Failure mechanisms summarized by the fault tree can be related in series or parallel (US Army Corps of Engineers, 2002; Jonkman et al., 2015), as schematically shown in Figure 2.1. Therefore, the evaluation of the upper and lower bounds of the failure probability of a complex system should be carried out by decomposing the overall system into elementary series and parallel systems.

Figure 2.1 Schemes of a series system and a parallel system. Adapted from US Army Corps of Engineers (2002).

Failure of a generic series system occurs if any of the elements of the system fails. Therefore, the upper ($P_{f,u}$) and lower ($P_{f,l}$) bounds of the total failure probability of a system composed of n elements can be evaluated as follows:

$$P_{f,u} = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - P_{fi}) \quad (2.1)$$

$$P_{f,l} = \max(P_{fi}) \quad (2.2)$$

where P_{fi} is the failure probability related to the i -th element of the series system. The upper and lower bounds respectively correspond to no correlation and full correlation between the failure modes.

Instead, a parallel system fails only if all its components fail. Therefore, the upper (u) and lower (l) bounds of the total failure probability of a system composed of n elements can be calculated as follows:

$$P_{f,u} = \min(P_{fi}) \quad (2.3)$$

$$P_{f,l} = \prod_{i=1}^n P_{fi} \quad (2.4)$$

where P_{fi} is the failure probability related to the $i - th$ element of the series system. The upper and lower bounds respectively correspond to full correlation and no correlation between the failure modes.

The failure modes contained in a generic fault tree can be correlated through common parameters contained in the correspondent limit state equations (e.g. significant wave height, mean wave period, mean sea level), but also by physical interactions (US Army Corps of Engineers, 2002).

The evaluation of the failure probability of a single failure mode can be performed by means of the definition of the correspondent limit state equation, usually referred to as reliability function, expressed in the following format (US Army Corps of Engineers, 2002; Jonkman et al., 2015):

$$Z = R - S \quad (2.5)$$

where R represents the resistance of the structure to external solicitations S . It should be noted that Equation (2.5) can be also written in the safety factor format, i.e. as the ratio between R and S . The reliability function can be derived from state of art or case-specific equations describing the studied failure mode (e.g. stability of the armor layer, mean overtopping discharge, toe berm stability, etc). In general, if $Z < 0$ (i.e. $R < S$), the selected limit state is overcome by the structure, and hence the failure probability (P_f) corresponds to the probability that the reliability function assumes negative values (i. e. $P(Z < 0)$). Once the failure probability has been calculated, the reliability of the structure referred to the selected failure mode can be evaluated as the complement to unity of P_f .

The components R and S contained in Equation (2.5) depend on several stochastic variables, following relationships not always well known, and, as consequence, Z is a complicated function of all these variables. Therefore, the probability of failure of a certain system for a selected failure mode can be calculated by solving the following equation:

$$P_f = \int_{Z < 0} f_{\underline{X}} d\underline{X} \quad (2.6)$$

where $f_{\underline{X}}$ are the n -dimensional probability density functions of the stochastic variables \underline{X} .

The evaluation of failure probability can be carried out using five different categories of methods (CIAD project group, 1985; Jonkman et al., 2015):

- level 0 methods, which are based on the deterministic calculation of the probability of failure, usually considering deterministic or nominal values of the involved variables and

one global safety factor γ . The comparison between resistance and forcing of the system is performed according to an equation with the following format:

$$R_n > \gamma S_n \quad (2.7)$$

where the subscript n indicates that nominal values are considered.

- level I methods (semi-probabilistic approach), which consider the stochastic nature of the parameters involved in the design processes by using one characteristic value for load and one for resistance, the so-called design values. In particular, the characteristic value of R corresponds to a low percentile, whereas the characteristic value of S corresponds to a high percentile. The calculation of these percentiles is carried out by means of partial factors resulting from probabilistic calculation of level II. The comparison between resistance and forcing is performed according to the following equation:

$$R_d > S_d \quad (2.8)$$

where the subscript d indicates that design values are considered, i.e. $R_d = \gamma_R R$ and $S_d = \gamma_S S$.

- level II methods (probabilistic with approximations), in which normal probability distribution are assumed for both strengths and loads and the reliability function is linearized at a specific point to determine the actual probability of failure. On the basis of the applied linearization process, three different approach can be considered: i) the first order mean value approach, which consists on the linearization of the reliability function about the expected mean value of the involved parameters using Taylor-series expansion; ii) the first order design-point approach, which consists on the linearization of the reliability function about the point of failure envelope ($Z = 0$) having the highest joint probability density, using an iterative procedure in the case of nonlinear failure envelopes; iii) the approximate full-distribution approach, which is similar to (ii), but the exact probability distributions are approximated by equivalent normal distribution in the vicinity of the design point.
- level III methods (fully probabilistic), in which the probability of failure is evaluated by using the exact joint probability distribution functions of the variables, thus modeling the correlation between them. In very few cases the problem of the evaluation of the probability of failure can be solved by means of analytical formulations. Instead, it is usually necessary to apply numerical integration or to perform Monte Carlo simulations.
- level IV methods (risk-based), which also takes into account the consequences of failure in terms of cost and the risk, defined as the consequence multiplied the probability of failure, which is used as a measure of the reliability.

Since the project PROMETEO does not focuses on the quantification of the failure consequences, level IV methods will not be further discussed. Figure 2.2 summarizes the design approaches considered in the present work.

Figure 2.2 Summary of the design approaches.

It is worth to point out that before using the above-mentioned methods, they have to be calibrated so that consistent reliability levels are obtained. In particular, level I methods can be calibrated using level II methods and level II methods can be calibrated using level III methods (Jonkman et al., 2015).

The deterministic approach does not allow to evaluate the probability of failure of the system, but only to predict if the failure may occur or not with the assigned values of the variables involved in the reliability function (i.e. state equation) and the global safety factor. As regards the application of level I methods, the aim is to ensure a certain reliability of the structure, depending on the partial coefficients used. However, the stochastic nature of the parameters involved in the design processes is considered in a very simplified way, which enables to create standards to be applied for the principal categories of breakwater projects. Therefore, it is clear that if level 0 or level I method are employed, design optimization is not possible (US Army Corps of Engineers, 2002).

Level II and III methods can be used to overcome the shortcomings of deterministic and semi-probabilistic approaches. Nevertheless, the implementation of such methods is affected by difficulties related to the lack of insight in the correlation between different failure modes of structure. Indeed, if the probability of failure of a single mechanism can be calculated in a relatively simple way, the exact probability of failure of the whole system is still a challenge. As already stated, failure modes can be correlated through common parameters contained in the limit state equations, but also by physical interaction (US Army Corps of Engineers, 2002). However, information about the interactions between failure modes are usually insufficient and further research is needed (Castillo et al., 2004; Plate, 1995; Burcharth, 1992; Burcharth and Liu, 1995).

2.3 Regulations for the design of rubble-mound breakwaters

Rubble-mound breakwaters are commonly used in coastal engineering to protect shorelines, harbors, and other coastal infrastructures against wave impact and erosion. The overarching aim of the regulations for design is to provide simple and practical criteria and general guidelines for engineers and designers. This minimizes the need to deal with numerous parameters, focusing instead on a few major and influential variables, thereby facilitating the design process, with an acceptable level of accuracy and safety. However, addressing the unconventional behavior of rubble-mound breakwaters requires many field and laboratory tests and different environmental measurements to determine hydrodynamic loads and structure responses. For

this reason, the number of reliable guidelines for the design of coastal structures worldwide is limited compared to other civil engineering fields.

Many countries have their own national standards and regulations for the design of rubble-mound breakwaters. These standards may be developed by governmental agencies, engineering organizations, industry associations, or universities and research institutions. It is imperative for engineers and designers to consider a combination of these regulations, guidelines, and project-specific requirements based on the site of the structure and the existing regulations of the country to ensure safety, reliability, and environmental sustainability, as well as to protect themselves from a legal standpoint.

Designing breakwaters involves a deep understanding of wave climates, coastal processes, and sediment transport patterns specific to the project site. Typically, this information is acquired through comprehensive wave and coastal studies conducted either by project developers or as part of government-funded research initiatives. In the last decades, there has been a shift towards probabilistic methods in the design of rubble-mound breakwaters. These probabilistic models consider uncertainties in various parameters such as wave climate, storm surge, sediment transport, and structural behavior. Such methods assist in assessing the risks associated with design decisions and in optimizing breakwater designs for reliability and cost-effectiveness.

While the theoretical basis of the probabilistic design (i.e. level II and III) dates to the 1980s-1990s (CIAD project group, 1985; van der Meer 1988a; Burcharth 1992; Oumeraci et al., 1999), it has only recently started to be included in some recommendations and guidelines (e.g., USACE, 2002; TECH-JAPAN 2009, 2020; Puertos del Estado 2010), thanks to the widespread availability of relatively inexpensive and high-performing computers that enable complex probabilistic calculations. Moreover, on a global scale, various international organizations directly and indirectly provide guidelines and recommendations for breakwater design, including the International Maritime Organization (IMO), the International Association of Ports and Harbors (IAPH), the International Society for Coastal and Ocean Engineers (ISCOE), and the World Association for Waterborne Transport Infrastructure (PIANC), among others.

The probabilistic design of rubble-mound breakwaters involves considering different sources of uncertainties, such as wave climate, material properties, and environmental conditions, to ensure their reliability over their intended design life. Regulations governing the design of rubble-mound breakwaters vary worldwide and are often influenced by local conditions, engineering practices, and standards organizations.

The indications given by the most significant standards and manuals for the design of breakwaters regarding the methodologies for the assessment of the reliability of these structures are presented in the following and summarized in Table 2.1. It is worth to point out that the design standards and manuals reported in Table 2.1 refers to both rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, with the only exception of The Rock Manual (2007), which is specific for the former type of structure.

Table 2.1 Summary of the main regulations for the design of rubble-mound breakwaters. The star indicates that the design level is suggested without explain a methodology.

Regulation	Country	Year	Design level
The British Standards BS 6349-7	UK	1991	Level 0, I*, II*, III*
PIANC partial safety factors method	Global	1992, 2016	Level I
Italian guidelines for the design of maritime dikes	Italy	1996	Level 0, I*
Coastal Engineering Manual	USA	2002	Level I, II, III
Australian Standards AS-4997-2005	Australia	2005	Level 0, I*, II*, III*
The Rock Manual	Europe	2007	Level 0, I*, II*, III*
Technical Standards and commentaries on Port and Harbour Facilities in Japan	Japan	2009, 2020	Level I, II, III
ROM 0.0, ROM1.0-09, ROM-1.1-18	Spain	2002, 2010, 2018	Level 0, I, II, III
EurOtop Manual	Europe	2018	Level 0, I, II*, III*

2.3.1 The British Standards BS 6349-7 (1991)

In the United Kingdom (UK), coastal engineering standards are established by government agencies such as the Environmental Agency and the Maritime and Coastguard Agency. However, the UK does not have a single unified document specifically dedicated to rubble-mound breakwater design but may be found in the relevant standards from the British Standards Institution (BSI), such as the BS 6349 series (1991). The British Standards BS 6349-7 (BSI, 1991) highlight the necessity to carry out a risk analysis in order to obtain the best assessment of failure probability of the breakwater. In particular, once the service lifetime of the breakwater is chosen on the basis of the requirements that the structure must fulfill, the risk is evaluated as the product between the failure probability during the structure lifetime and its consequences. Such kind of analysis requires the inventory of all possible failure modes and thus the construction of a fault tree which can represent the relationships between the failure of each component of the structure (e.g. armor layers, filter layers, core, berm, capping wall, subsoil basement).

However, the method proposed for the evaluation of the reliability of the breakwater is deterministic (level 0) and based on the evaluation of the return period of the design wave as a function of service lifetime and acceptable failure probability of the breakwater. Level II and III methods are only mentioned as under development.

2.3.2 PIANC partial safety factors method (1992, 2003, 2016)

Burcharth (1992) developed a partial safety factors method (i.e. level I method) for the design of rubble-mound breakwaters, whose detailed explanation is given by PIANC (1992). The description of such a method for vertical breakwaters is presented by Burcharth and Sørensen (1999) and PIANC (2003). Moreover, a more recent report published by PIANC (2016) provides indications for the choice of safety levels and of the corresponding partial safety factors.

Four kind of partial safety factors were calibrated through a reliability analysis of level II: i) a load partial safety factor to be applied to the mean value of the permanent load equal to 1; ii) a partial safety factor to be used to the combination of the mean values of the resistance variables; iii) a load partial safety factor to be applied to the design significant wave height, which is a function of the structure service lifetime and the acceptable failure probability; iv) a partial safety factor to be used with the mean value of undrained shear strength of clay materials in the

subsoil. The magnitude of these partial safety factors reflects both the uncertainty and the relative importance in the reliability function of the related variable.

For calibration of the PIANC safety factors, wave data from four quite different geographical locations (i.e. Bilbao, Sines, Tripoli and Fallonica) were selected and fitted to a Weibull distribution. The wave data from Bilbao, Sines and Tripoli correspond to deep water waves, whereas the wave data from Fallonica correspond to shallow water waves. The uncertainties related to quality of the measured wave data were modeled by a multiplicative stochastic variable FH_s normally distributed with mean value 1 and standard deviation between 0.05 and 0.02 depending on the reliability of the data-set (e.g. buoy measurements, hindcast numerical models). As regards the design lifetime, periods of 20, 50 or 100 years were considered, whereas the acceptable values of failure probability were 0.01, 0.05, 0.10, 0.20 and 0.40. The partial safety factors were evaluated for two typologies of structure: rubble-mound breakwaters and vertical-wall caisson structures. In the first case, failure modes related to armor stability, toe berm breakage, run-up and scour were considered for different kinds of armor blocks. In the latter case, failure modes related to foundation (sand or clay subsoil), sliding, overturning, scour and toe berm were studied.

Even though the PIANC partial coefficient system represents an advanced level I method for the design of breakwaters for a specific failure probability level, it is applicable only to the failure modes selected for the study, and hence it is scarcely flexible to situations which differ from the reference ones.

2.3.3 Italian guidelines for the design of maritime dikes (1996)

The Italian guidelines for the design of maritime dikes (Consiglio Superiore dei Lavori Pubblici, 1996) suggest a methodology very close to the one presented in the British Standards BS 6349-7 (BSI, 1991). Indeed, a deterministic approach for the evaluation of the reliability of the breakwater is described, considering the structure lifetime and the maximum acceptable failure probability as functions of the typology of breakwater and the requirements it must satisfy. Then, the return period of the design wave height is calculated, and the verification of the deterministic state equations is carried out.

However, the design of rubble-mound breakwaters requires special attention, because not negligible damages are often accepted for this kind of structures. Hence, a more complex risk analysis is needed to assess the failure probability of a rubble-mound breakwater, and to this aim the Italian guidelines suggests the partial safety factors method (PIANC, 1992). It should be noted that the partial safety factors method cited by the Italian guidelines has been outdated by another version of the PIANC (2016).

2.3.4 Coastal Engineering Manual (2002)

Among the countries involved in coastal engineering practice, the United States (US) stands out for its remarkable advances and large investments, particularly in field and laboratory experiments related to the design of coastal rubble-mound breakwaters. However, when viewed from the perspective of a code of practice or a coherent set of regulations, it becomes evident that there is no single regulation or instruction in the form of a comprehensive collection governing the design of rubble-mound breakwaters. The lack of a unified approach is not necessarily a scientific or technical disadvantage, as the technical affairs in this country are highly

specialized due to the presence of numerous scientific centers and different environmental conditions in practice (e.g., Atlantic Ocean, Pacific Ocean, Caribbean Sea). Each region typically issues its own specialized rules for designing coastal structures, which are produced and provided separately. Design teams in the US are accustomed to this situation and are adept at making the necessary adjustments, unlike in other countries where such fragmentation is less common. For example, another distinguishing factor between American and the rest of world guidelines lies in the economic realm. Generally, Americans tend to prioritize efficiency and are inclined to reach conclusions quickly, benefiting from their stronger economic position on a macro scale. In contrast, other countries often prioritize economic conditions, which can complicate matters concerning technical regulations.

Coastal engineering practices in the US are primarily regulated by various federal agencies, including the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) and the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA). While there is not a specific federal regulation governing the probabilistic design of rubble-mound breakwaters, engineers typically adhere to several design guidelines and standards which anyway incorporate probabilistic methods to assess the performance and reliability of breakwater structures. USACE provides guidance to coastal engineers through the well-known Coastal Engineering Manuals (US Army Corps of Engineers, 2002).

The Coastal Engineering Manual (USACE, 2002) is an important international reference for the solution of most coastal engineering problems, since it summarizes in a single source the state of the art of coastal engineering until 2002, replacing the Shore Protection Manual (CERC, 1984) and several other US Army Corps of Engineers manuals. In particular, part VI of the Coastal Engineering Manual (USACE, 2002) provides a comprehensive description of definitions and procedures needed in the planning and design processes for coastal projects, stressing the necessity to move from a deterministic to a risk-based approach for the following reasons:

1. forcing, represented by wave characteristics, winds, water levels and currents both over short and long term, has a stochastic behavior;
2. the deterministic analysis of the interaction between structures and external loads masks the existing uncertainties and can be misleading;
3. damage and thus functional performances of a coastal project evolve incrementally;
4. because of the above factors, benefits and risks cannot be fully represented in deterministic terms;
5. in addition to the uncertainties associated directly with the coastal project considered, significant possibilities for changing adjacent areas can be introduced.

Reliability-based design of coastal structures is also presented in part VI of the Coastal Engineering Manual (USACE, 2002). The construction of the reliability function for a single failure mode is explained and both level II and III methods for its solution are presented. Furthermore, a possible way to evaluate the failure probability of the whole structure is described, taking into account the series or parallel-type links between the different failure modes. In particular, the upper and lower bound of the failure probability are evaluated considering the extreme conditions of no and full correlation between the elements of the fault tree, by means of the decomposition of the latter in simpler series or parallel subsystems. The presented methodology should be improved by a better understanding of the relationships between the different failure modes of a structure. Furthermore, in order to carry out an optimization of a design, the failure

probability must be used together with economic considerations. As the risk of human injury is marginal it is common to disregard such risk when designing breakwaters. Therefore, design of new breakwaters and rehabilitation of existing breakwaters can be based on life-cycle analysis targeting the minimum lifetime costs i.e., the costs of construction, maintenance, repairs and demolition, depositing and reuse of materials (PIANC, 2016). Finally, the PIANC advanced partial safety factor method PIANC (1992) is described in detail and tables containing the value of the safety factors for the different failure modes of rubble-mound breakwaters and vertical-wall caisson structures.

The USACE employs a more advanced Level III method, which differs from traditional reliability approaches, exemplifying a heightened level of sophistication in comparison. Indeed, traditional reliability approaches aim to approximate the failure surface using sophisticated mathematical techniques primarily to avoid the computational cost of numerically modeling the response to every single storm. Although these approaches employ elegant and complex solution strategies, they have inherent limitations. Most of these methods are parametric, requiring fitting of univariate and multivariate mathematical distributions and subsequent integration of these models. The USACE approach leans towards a brute force method, aiming to model everything in high fidelity and employ nonparametric extremal analysis approaches where possible. They precompute multivariate hazards (e.g., among the others, storm surge, water level (combined astronomical tide and surge response), wave climate, tropical and extratropical cyclones, hurricanes, sea level change and these data are freely available nationally online, incorporating both aleatory and epistemic uncertainty. The Coastal Hazard System (CHS) web application¹ can be accessed through the CHS web from the USACE Engineer Research and Development Center Coastal and Hydraulics website. In addition, a CHS wiki provides the latest up-to-date information on the system. USACE and general Federal coastal projects, R&D studies, flood-risk mapping, and emergency response activities require storm data and extensive high-fidelity modeling in a statistical context in order to plan and design projects and assess risk. These data are usually generated for each study at great expense. A typical coastal engineering study requires expensive modeling and measurements that include time- and spatially varying waves, water level, wind, atmospheric pressure, and currents, among other data types. The CHS provides comprehensive coastal data and the associated uncertainties in easily ingestible standardized formats, producing great potential for monetary savings and improved understanding of the complex processes. Interested parties can download a suite of storms for any specific location. Subsequently, they utilize software called *StormSim*, which reads these data in its native format.

StormSim adds epistemic uncertainty to every time-step of every storm by sampling the epistemic distributions using Monte-Carlo (M-C) sampling of normal distributions, generating hundreds of thousands of events. Then, the structure responses are computed for every time-step of each storm, keeping the maximum response for each storm. They incorporate structure response uncertainty when computing the structure response, namely the physical reactions of the structure to the expected wave climate forcing. Next, those responses are integrated to obtain an Annual Exceedance Probability (AEP) distribution for each storm response (e.g., wave runup, overtopping, armor size, armor damage, Goda pressure, etc.). Typically, they select an

¹ <https://chs.erdc.dren.mil/>

AEP and confidence level for design and compare it to targets. Generally, for overtopping the 100-year AEP at the 90% confidence level is used. Such an approach incorporates most of the uncertainties while maintaining multivariate relationships between parameters. *StormSim* automates most of the tedious work, offering both design mode and life-cycle simulation mode, which includes computations for damage, repairs, sea level rise (SLR), and other time-dependent factors. Numerous reports have been published online in an open-source form by the US Army Engineer Research and Development Center (ERDC) about specific projects on both the Atlantic and Pacific coasts. Technical reports published by ERDC can be found at their online library².

The Coastal Engineering Manual (USACE, 2002) serves as the primary coastal design guide in the US, but there are numerous other planning manuals within USACE that provide additional requirements for probabilistic evaluation and design. For example, US Army Corps of Engineers (1996) delineates procedures for risk and uncertainties in USACE Flood Risk Management and Coastal Storm Risk Management (CSRМ) studies. Similarly, FEMA's Coastal Construction Manual offers guidelines (Herseih et al., 2012) for designing structures to withstand coastal hazards such as storm surge, wave action, and erosion.

2.3.5 Australian Standards (AS-4997-2005)

In Australia, coastal engineering standards and guidelines are established by agencies such as the Australian Coastal Councils Association (ACCA) and the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization (CSIRO). The Australian Coastal Engineering Manuals, such as the Coastal Engineering guideline (Engineers Australia, 2017) and the NSW Coastal Design guidelines (NSW, 2023), provide comprehensive guidance on the design and management of coastal structures and shoreline protection measures, including rubble-mound breakwaters. These guidelines aim to enhance decision-making, built outcomes and environmental performance in coastal areas through strategic planning and urban design. The manuals serve as a comprehensive resource and incorporate the Australian Standard (AS-4997-2005) as guidelines for the design of maritime structures.

The objective of this Standard is to provide designers and regulatory authorities with a comprehensive set of guidelines and recommendations for the design, preservation, and practical applications of structures situated in the marine environment. Although there is no specific Australian Standard exclusively dedicated to the design of rubble-mound breakwaters, various documents and standards offer design guidelines and principles for these structures. Specifically, the Australian Standard sets out guidelines for the design of structures in a marine environment in conjunction with relevant international Standards and offers recommendations in addition to their requirements. This Standard covers the design of near-shore coastal and estuarine structures including jetties, seawalls and breakwater structures, among the others. However, rock armored structures such as rubble mound breakwaters and groins are excluded from this list. For rubble mound breakwaters, AS-4997-2005 recommends referring to the BS 6349, adopting the same probabilistic design level.

2.3.6 The Rock Manual (2007)

The Rock Manual (CIRIA et al., 2007) is a reference guideline for the use of rock in hydraulic engineering, born from the collaboration between France, Netherlands and United Kingdom. It

² <https://erdclibrary.on.worldcat.org/discovery>

represents an extensive summary of good practices on the design, the construction and the maintenance of rock structures for rivers, coasts and seas, and it has incorporated all the significant advances in knowledge that have occurred over the 10÷15 years before 2007.

As regards the design approach for rock structures, the following reasons why deterministic methods have been traditionally applied are discussed: i) limited existing data regarding progressive failure mechanisms; ii) the structural response models (e.g. design equations) are largely deterministic because they have been developed from failure criteria; iii) the past tendency to prefer a robust design based on safety factors in contrast to an optimized one. Furthermore, such a kind of approach is based on the unrealistic hypothesis that the structure remains safely intact, providing the same level of protection until the end of its design lifetime. Indeed, as structures age, the failure probability and the uncertainties in its response to external load usually increase.

The risk-based design approach proposed to consider the above-mentioned uncertainties consists in assessing the sensitivity of failure relative to a single mode to the variation of different parameters involved in the reliability function, thus constructing fragility curves, which graphically express how the failure probability changes with the selected parameter. Therefore, the method proposed can be considered as an advanced level 0 method, which allows a simplified evaluation of the failure probability of a single mode.

Level I, II and III approaches for the evaluation of the reliability of breakwaters are considered as alternative to the proposed deterministic method with sensitivity analysis and the following brief indication are given: i) for level I approaches, it is recommended the PIANC safety partial factors method PIANC (1992); ii) for level II approaches, the first order design-point method is mentioned, although not recommended because of problems in the convergence of most computer routines; iii) for level III approaches, a fully integration method based on Monte Carlo simulations is suggested.

Deterministic methods (Level 0) still play a role in the design process, with some consideration of uncertainty, particularly in the characterization of design parameters and material properties, but more advanced probabilistic methods are suggested for high-risk areas. However, no further information is given regarding the evaluation of the failure probability of the whole structure based on the relationships between the elements which constitute its failure fault tree.

2.3.7 Technical Standards and commentaries on Port and Harbour Facilities in Japan (2009, 2020)

In Japan, coastal Engineering standards are developed by organizations such as the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism (MLIT) and the Japan Society of Civil Engineers (JSCE). Design guidelines for rubble-mound breakwaters are outlined in documents such as the Coastal Disaster Prevention Manual and the JSCE Coastal Engineering Manual, which provide guidance on the design of coastal structures, including rubble-mound breakwaters, to mitigate the impacts of natural hazards such as tsunamis and typhoons. An important aspect of Japanese regulations is the cohesive nature of standards, unlike the fragmented nature seen in US and UK regulations. This cohesiveness is exemplified in the Technical Standards and Commentaries on Port and Harbour Facilities in Japan (Ports and Harbours Bureau et al., 2009, 2020), which are applied to the construction, improvement and maintenance of port and harbor facilities in

Japan. Ports and Harbours Bureau et al. (2009) proposes the transition to a performance-based design system, whereas Harbours Bureau et al. (2020) provides some updates to improve the design of existing structures.

The proposed performance-based design system is characterized as follows: i) the objective is the reason why the structure considered is needed; ii) the performance requirements represent the performance that the structure must satisfy to achieve the objective; iii) the performance criteria are the technical explanation of a set of rules for the verification of the performance requirements; iv) the performance verification is the act to verify that the performance criteria are satisfied. Whereas objectives, performance requirements and performance criteria are ruled, no particular method for performance verification is mandatory. The technical standards suggest the use of reliability-based design methods, since they are able to take into account the actions on the structure, the requirements for services and the uncertainty of the performance. However, other reliable methods such as numerical analysis methods, model test methods, and in situ test methods should be considered in specific situations.

As regards the reliability-based methods, level I, II and III approaches are described, although the level I one is adopted considering agreement with the upper-level standards, and simplicity and convenience in practical design work. Nevertheless, this does not restrict the use of the level II and level III approaches, that rather are suggested if high control of the failure probability is desired. For level II approaches, the partial safety factor relative to a generic variable is calculated as a function of its probability distribution (i.e. normal or log-normal) and a target reliability index, whose evaluation is based on the average safety level of conventional design criteria. Furthermore, the calculation of the target reliability index using a method based on the investment effect necessary for avoiding the risk of human loss, and hence on the minimization of the life cycle cost, is not rejected.

The necessity to consider a set of failure modes and their mutual links for the evaluation of the whole structure failure probability is also underlined and formulas for the evaluation of the system failure probability are proposed.

In Japan, the probabilistic level used for rubble-mound breakwaters design typically ranges from Level II to Level III. Specifically, given Japan's susceptibility to natural hazards, advanced probabilistic methods are often employed for rubble-mound breakwater design, especially in high-risk areas. Level III probabilistic design, which involves the use of sophisticated probabilistic methods such as Monte Carlo simulation or Bayesian inference to comprehensively account for uncertainty, is commonly adopted for projects in these areas. Multiple scenarios are considered to thoroughly assess the influence of various sources of uncertainty and variability on design outcomes. The specific probabilistic level adopted may vary based on project requirements, site-specific conditions, and the expertise of engineers and regulatory authorities involved.

2.3.8 ROM Program

Spain is one of the European countries with the most advanced regulations in the probabilistic design of rubble-mound breakwaters. The most recent Spanish set of design recommendations for breakwater design is the ROM 1.1-18 - Recommendations for Breakwater Construction Projects (Puertos del Estado, 2018), which is part of the regulatory framework of Puertos del Estado for maritime infrastructures that protect land areas against marine dynamics. The ROM 1.1-18 (Puertos del Estado, 2018) is a revision and expansion of the ROM 0.0-01 (Puertos del

Estado, 2002) and ROM 1.0-09 (Puertos del Estado, 2010), and it also includes the methodology described in the MEIPOR - Method for the Evaluation of Port Investments (Puertos del Estado, 2016).

These guidelines provide a comprehensive manual for the design, verification, and construction of breakwaters, with particular emphasis on climate, atmospheric, and marine agents, whose actions can significantly impact maritime structures. Specifically, ROM 0.0 deals with verifying failure modes, whereas ROM 1.0-09 focuses on the detailed description of the methodology for characterizing the set of climate agents and other project factors, the calculation of the joint probability of failure, and the definition of the situations in which each of the four verification approaches should be used. ROM 1.1 represents an advancement over the previous two versions. When applying ROM 1.1, it is advisable for engineers to be familiar with the recommendations of the ROM program. ROM 1.1-18 should only be applied by expert engineers or under the supervision of senior engineers with many years of experience in the fields of harbor and maritime works. Accordingly, users of ROM 1.1-18 and MEIPOR-16 should possess a solid background in numerical and statistical methods, risk and reliability, macroeconomics, coastal ecology, as well as specific notions of coastal, port, and maritime engineering.

Here, the methodological framework for coastal defense structures described in the ROM 0.0 (Puertos del Estado, 2002) is discussed in more detail. In particular, verification procedures related to failure and operational stoppage modes of breakwaters with semi-probabilistic approaches (i.e. level I) are presented and procedures to simplify the practical use of probabilistic methods (i.e. level II and III) are developed.

The design of breakwaters is based on three fundamental general criteria: i) the structure is spatially divided into homogeneous subsets and the works are organized in distinct temporal phases; ii) the desired performances of each subset in the various phases are selected; iii) the overall requirements in terms of structure safety and serviceability are defined. Moreover, the stochastic nature of the variables involved in breakwater design is considered spatially uniform and stationary in time.

Each subset is characterized by specific geometry, material, soil structure, topography, external solicitations and required hydraulic and structural performances. Generally, five subsets of a breakwater can be identified: i) junction of the breakwater with the soil; ii) main alignment that controls and protects against the prevailing wave action; iii) secondary alignments that link the different subsets of the breakwater; iv) transition or subset between two alignments or types; v) head or upper part of the breakwater.

The project phases are fundamentally five: i) construction; ii) serviceability; iii) maintenance and repairs; iv) remodeling, transformation, and dismantling; v) other phases and subphases (e.g. when the entry into service of the structure is partial or when situations particularly relevant are expected to occur during the previous phases). In each project phase, all breakwater subsets should comply with three requirements:

1. minimum useful life;
2. maximum joint probability of the principal failure modes, specified for the structure's useful life;

3. minimum operability delimited by the occurrence of a maximum number of annual stoppage modes and certain maximum duration.

The minimum useful life refers to the serviceability phase, and it corresponds to a period less than 5 year for provisional structures and greater than 5 years for definitive ones, depending on the Economic Repercussion Index (ERI³) of the maritime structure, as described in Table 2.IX. If the breakwater lifetime is equal to or longer than 50 years, the project should integrate and verify the effects of climate change on the breakwater performances by assessing the spatial and temporal evolution of the joint, conditional, and marginal probability distributions of the climate forcing and its loads.

Table 2.II Minimum useful life in the serviceability project design phase for permanent structures as a function of ERI. Source: Puertos del Estado (2002, 2010, 2018).

ERI	Useful life in years
5	15
6÷20	25
> 20	50

The safety and serviceability requirements that every subset of the breakwater should fulfill during each design phase are defined by a maximum accepted joint failure probability or operational stoppage. In the case of ULS or SLS, these limit probabilities P_f (and the correspondent reliability index β) are fixed as function of the social and environmental repercussion index (SERI⁴) relative to the considered structure, following the indication in Table 2.III. In the case of ULS design, if two different damage levels are considered for initiation of damage and destruction, cumulative damage models can be employed in order to define repair strategies as an integral part of the breakwater design. In such cases, the joint failure probability among the principal modes is distributed at the destruction level, but it can be transposed to other damage levels. It should be noted that the cumulative damage is usually described with reference to the main armor layer and berms (in terms of geometric form and/or cumulative number of displaced units), the crown wall and superstructure (in terms of displacements and/or overturning), and the wave overtopping (in terms of number of events and cumulative value of overtopping volumes).

Table 2.III Maximum joint probability in the serviceability phase or the useful life of the breakwater for ULS and SLS. Source: Puertos del Estado (2002, 2010, 2018).

SERI	P_f		β	
	ULS	SLS	ULS	SLS
<5	0.20	0.20	0.84	0.84
5÷19	0.10	0.10	1.28	1.28
20÷29	0.01	0.07	2.32	1.50
≥ 30	0.0001	0.07	3.71	1.50

³ The ERI assess the economic repercussions of the reconstruction of the subset and of the cessation or its foreseeable impact on the economic activities directly related with it in the event of the destruction of the breakwater.

⁴ The SERI qualitatively assesses the expected social and environmental impact in the case of the total destruction of the subset, and it evaluates the possibility and repercussion of loss of human lives, damage to the environment as well as to the historical and artistic heritage, social alarm generated.

In the case of operability during the serviceability phase, the required minimum operability $r_{f,OLS}$ and the correspondent reliability index β_{OLS} are evaluated based on the Operational Index of Economic Repercussion (OIER⁵), following the indication of Table 2.IV. Moreover, within the specified time period (generally an average year of useful life) the sum of the admissible average number of operational stoppages N_m should be less than the maximum values defined as a function of the Operational Index of Social and Environmental Repercussion (OISER⁶), as shown in Table 2.V. Finally, the maximum acceptable duration of a stoppage within the specified time period is set as a function of the indexes OIER and OISER, according to Table 2.VI. It is worth to point out that the values ERI, SERI, OIER and OISER are determined as function of the type of protected area, according to the reference tables contained in the guidelines.

Table 2.IV Minimum operability during the serviceability phase of the breakwater. Source: Puertos del Estado (2002, 2010, 2018).

OIER	$r_{f,OLS}$	β_{OLS}
≤5	0.85	1.04
6÷20	0.95	1.65
>20	0.99	2.32

Table 2.V Maximum average number of operational stoppages in the time period. Source: Puertos del Estado (2002, 2010, 2018).

OISER	N_m
<5	10
5÷19	5
20÷29	2
≥30	0

Table 2.VI Most probable value of the maximum duration of an operational stoppage (hours). Source: Puertos del Estado (2002, 2010, 2018).

OIER \ OISER	OISER			
	<5	5÷19	20÷29	≥30
≤5	24	12	6	0
6÷20	12	6	3	0
>20	6	3	1	0

The performance of each subset is described and quantified by one or various forms and mechanisms that can affect its safety and operability. Therefore, the project objectives related to safety are verified if the probability of occurrence of the failure modes does not exceed the proposed limit values. Similarly, the project objectives related to operability are verified if the time period considered (any year of the structure's useful life) complies with the proposed thresholds. In particular, after the analysis of mutually exclusive occurrence of the modes and the discussion of their statistical dependence, a fault tree of the set of failure or stoppage modes can be draft, considering both parallel and series links. For verification purpose,

⁵ The OIER assesses the cost of the total loss of operability of the subset. It delimits the minimum operability of the subset in the time interval considered (usually one year).

⁶ The OISER evaluates the expected social and environmental repercussion in the case of the total loss of operability of the subset within the time interval considered.

the failure modes are classified as: i) modes that can be verified by level 0 methods imposed by other regulations, because they do not contribute to the joint failure probability of the structure; ii) non-principal modes, characterized by the possibility to significantly improve the reliability of the subset by slightly increasing the total cost of the structure; iii) principal modes, which are failure and stoppage mode for which the reliability can be hardly improved.

The activation of a principal failure mode and its consequences can be defined by means of different method, namely the resolution of a verification equation, the physical and/or numerical modelling, and standards of good practice. The application of the first method implies three steps: i) formulation and format of the equation, which is usually expressed as ration between resistance and solicitations (i.e. global safety factor format) or difference between resistance and solicitation (i.e. safety margin format); ii) criteria to assign and combine values with project factors and terms; iii) method of equation resolution. The recommendations propose the use of level I, II and III methods for the verification of breakwaters against a failure mode assigned to an ultimate or serviceability limit state, and a stoppage mode assigned to an operational stoppage limit state. The choice between the proposed method is based on economic, social and environmental requirements, expressed by the ERI and SERI indexes, as shown in Table 2.VII. When a multiple verification procedure (a level I method along with a level II or III method) is indicated, the state equation is verified if the two considered procedures show that the reliability, functionality or operability required are fulfilled. Since level I methods must be included in these cases, and also since they are easy to use, it is suggested to use them for the pre-dimensioning of the structure.

In conclusion, the main innovations introduced by the Spanish design recommendations compared to the previous breakwater design guidelines are: i) the detailed description of the methodology for the characterization of the set of climate agents and other project factors; ii) the detailed description of the methodology for the calculation of the joint failure probability of the whole structure; iii) the definition of the situations in which each of the four verification approaches (i.e. level 0, I, II and III) should be used.

Table 2.VII Indications for the choice of the appropriate method for the solution of the state equation of a failure or stoppage mode based on ERI and SERI indexes. Source: Puertos del Estado (2002, 2010, 2018).

ERI	SERI			
	<5	5÷19	20÷29	>30
5	Level 0	Level I	Level I and II or III	Level I and II or III
6÷20	Level I	Level I	Level I and II or III	Level I and II or III
>20	Level I and II or III			

2.3.9 EurOtop Manual (2018)

The EurOtop Manual (EurOtop, 2018) gives guidance on analysis of wave overtopping for flood defenses attacked by wave action, referring to three principal types structures: i) sloping sea dikes and embankment seawalls; ii) armored rubble slopes and mounds; iii) vertical, battered or steep walls. It replaces all the previous version of the manual and also the sections regarding the hydraulic performances of rock defense structures in The Rock Manual (CIRIA et al., 2007). In parallel with the manual, an Artificial Neural Network (i.e. the EurOtop ANN) based on the

extended CLASH⁷ database is provided to predict mean overtopping discharge for each kind of structure geometries, given by a number of hydraulic and geometrical parameters as input.

Regarding the models for overtopping prediction, four categories of sources of uncertainties can be identified: i) fundamental or statistical uncertainties conditioned by random processes of Nature and which cannot be diminished; ii) data uncertainty, related to measurement errors, non-homogeneity of data, errors during data handling, non-representative reproduction of measurement due to inadequate temporal and spatial resolution; iii) model uncertainty, which leads to an inadequate reproduction of physical processes in Nature; iv) human errors during production, abrasion, maintenance of the structure as well as other human mistakes which are not covered by the model. The problem of the uncertainties related to human errors is not further developed in the manual. The uncertainties of the input parameters can be described using the statistical distributions or relative variation of these parameters. Finally, the model uncertainty is taken into account using the same approach than for parameters uncertainties using a multiplicative approach. Indeed, the standard form of the empirical models for overtopping prediction proposed in the EurOtop Manual (EurOtop, 2018) is the following:

$$q = m \times f(x_i) \quad (2.9)$$

where q is the mean overtopping rate, $f(x_i)$ is the model function of the variables x_i and m is the model factor. The model factor m is assumed to be normally distributed with a mean value of 1.0 and a coefficient of variation specifically derived for the model. It is also possible that m is one of the coefficients in a formula, which is assumed to be a stochastic variable, and that the uncertainty is given by the standard deviation of this coefficient.

Therefore, three different approaches are presented to deal with the uncertainties related to the parameters of the wave overtopping models:

1. the mean value approach, which consist in using the formulas as given with the mean value of the stochastic model parameters (i.e. level 0). This method should be applied to predict or compare with test data, also considering a graphical representation of the 5%-exceedance lines or 95%-confidence band, thus including some probabilistic considerations;
2. design or assessment approach, which is an easy semi-probabilistic approach derived from the mean value approach (i.e. level I). The uncertainty of the prediction is included by giving to every involved stochastic parameter a value equal to its mean increased by its standard deviation;
3. probabilistic approach, which consider the stochastic parameters with their given standard deviation and assuming a normal or log-normal distribution (i.e. level II or III).

If no information on statistical distributions is available for water levels or sea state parameters, they can be considered as normally distributed and the following assumptions regarding their coefficients of variation (defined as the ratio between standard deviation and mean of the stochastic variables) could be taken (Schüttrumpf et al., 2007): i) the significant wave height has a coefficient of variation equal to 5.0%; ii) the peak wave period has a coefficient of variation equal to 5.0%; iii) the design water level at the toe has a coefficient of variation equal to 3.0%.

⁷ www.clash-eu.org

Other parameters are independent of their mean values so that standard deviations (prototype measures) can be used for the water depth, the crest height and the height of the berm and the friction factor. However, the only presented example of a probabilistic approach of level II application is the case of wave overtopping over smooth slopes. Monte Carlo simulations were performed to obtain the uncertainty in the resulting mean overtopping discharges, which is combined with the already proposed model uncertainties for the parameters of the formula. Therefore, EurOtop (2018) does not examine in depth the problem of the uncertainty related to the stochastic nature of the variable involved in the overtopping processes, focusing only on the model uncertainty. Furthermore, since the manual refers only to the hydraulic performances of defense structures, failure modes not linked to excessive overtopping discharges are not analyzed.

2.4 Regulations for the design of vertical breakwaters

The indications given by the most significant standards and manuals for the design of vertical breakwaters regarding the methodologies for the assessment of the reliability of these structures are presented in the following and summarized in Table 2.VIII.

Table 2.VIII Summary of regulations for the design of vertical breakwaters. The star indicates that the design level is suggested without explain a methodology.

Regulation	Country	Year	Design level
The British Standards BS 6349-7	UK	1991	Level 0, I*, II*, III*
PIANC partial safety factors method	Global	1992, 2016	Level I
Italian guidelines for the design of maritime dikes	Italy	1996	Level 0, I*
Coastal Engineering Manual	USA	2002	Level I, II, III
Australian Coastal Engineering Manual	Australia	2005	Level I/II/III
ROM - Recommendations for Breakwater Construction Projects	Spain	2019	Level 0, I*, II*, III*
Technical Standards and commentaries on Port and Harbour Facilities in Japan	Japan	2009, 2020	Level I, II, III

2.4.1 The British Standards BS 6349-7 (1991)

Concerning the design of vertical breakwater, as already discussed in Section 2.3.1 with reference to rubble-mound breakwaters, the UK does not have a single regulatory instrument specifically dedicated for providing technical instructions for the design of this type of structure. For this purpose, in the UK, we refer to the reports published by the BSI (British Standards Institution), in particular the document BS 6349 -7: 1991 entitled "Maritime structures - Part 7: Guide to the design and construction of breakwaters".

The afore cited document, as already highlighted in Section 2.3.1 above, the general principle is that the design of any type of breakwater, and therefore also of vertical wall breakwaters, must be conducted using probabilistic methods based on risk analysis. In particular, once the service life of the breakwater has been chosen, on the basis of the requirements to be met by the structure, the risk is assessed as the product between the probability of failure during the life of the structure and its consequences. The objective of the probabilistic models is to determine the probability of failure for each of the stress response mechanisms of the structure, to determine the reliability function corresponding to the limit state considered; in the case of cast-

in-place dams, the limit states considered are both incipient damage and collapse; in the case of vertical-wall breakwater, on the other hand, given that their repair is generally difficult and often very costly, the initial damage limit state is not considered, but only the ultimate collapse limit state is considered. Therefore, the document BS 6349 -7: 1991 lists the different techniques that can be used to determine the probability of failure for a specific reliability function, indicating the different levels I, II and III of risk analysis currently available, and their intrinsic characteristics.

However, the method proposed for the design and verification of vertical breakwaters, as extensively illustrated in BS 6349 -7: 1991, is deterministic. It is based on the identification of wave loads acting on the structure and the stresses induced by the design wave with an assigned return time, indicating a probability of occurrence of the event, predefined in relation to the useful lifespan of the structure.

For the determination of wave loads, BS 6349 -7: 1991 refers to the contents of BS 6349-1:1984, which was updated and replaced by the report BS 6349-1: 2000 'Maritime structures - Part 1: Code of practice for general criteria'. The latter describes the different formulations to be adopted for the identification of pressure distributions acting on the vertical wall, based on the different characteristics of the incident wave motion. The deterministic approach suggested by the BS provides for the verification of the design in relation to different failure mechanisms, through the comparison of resistant and stressing forces, the ratio of which must be greater than the value of specific global safety factors. In particular, the safety factor for the slip and overturning failure mechanism is 1.2, which may be increased to 1.5 – 2, if the mooring of boats on the inner side of the breakwater is foreseen.

For the ultimate load analysis of structures with quasi-static wave load response characteristics, the design wave parameters considered are the height and period of the average maximum incident wave with a return period of 50 years. When the dynamic response of the structure to the wave load is significant and therefore not negligible, the dimensioning of the structure must consider all the possible wave forcings, characterized by different wave periods, falling within the range of all the possible cases of interest, and relative maximum heights that would determine the maximum dynamic stress of the structure.

The design wave forces must be derived from the previously defined design wave parameters, either by calculation or by testing on a physical model. However, some caution is required in the case of vertically clad structures, due to the difficulties in accurately modelling or calculating the impact pressures that sometimes occur in the prototype.

Finally, it should be noted that BS 6349-1: 2000 devotes specific attention to the verification of fatigue failure mechanisms. In this regard, the British Standard suggests the use of a specific safety factor for fatigue analysis. Direct wave loading on maritime structures comes mainly from waves with periods of up to 20 seconds. When the maximum stresses due to wave loading constitute more than 40 % of the total maximum combined stresses, the fatigue life of the structure must be verified. For the fatigue analysis, the number of waves that can occur during the design life of the structure within a range of height and period intervals must be evaluated. The safety factor against fatigue failure during the design life can then be determined with the Palmgren-Miner equation:

$$1 \quad \text{Safety factor: } \sum_{i=1}^{n_T} (n_i/N_i) \quad (2.2)$$

where n_i is the number of waves occurring during the design life of the structure, in the stress range i , N_i is the number of waves in the stress range, i , required to cause the failure of the structure, n_T is the total number of stress ranges considered.

2.4.2 PIANC partial safety factors method (1992, 2003, 2016)

The partial safety factors method proposed by PIANC (1992, 2003, 2016), as described in Section 2.3.2 with reference to rubble-mound structures, is also applicable to the design of vertical breakwaters.

2.4.3 Italian guidelines for the design of maritime dikes (1996)

With regard to the design of vertical- breakwaters, as seen with regard to jetties in Section 2.3.3, the methodology suggested by the Technical Instructions for the Design of Seawalls (Consiglio Superiore dei Lavori Pubblici) is deterministic, quasi-probabilistic. The approach adopted for the evaluation of the reliability of the breakwater, is to fix the design life of the structure, on the basis of the functionality requested and of a fixed level of safety to be adopted for it. At the same time, for rigid structures such as vertical breakwaters, since it is extremely difficult to repair any kind of damage sustained, the maximum allowable probability of total destruction of the wall work is associated with the economic repercussion and the expected risk of loss of life. Based on the service life of the structure and the maximum accepted probability of destruction, the design return time is determined, which is the probabilistic benchmark in the given approach.

Through the return time, in fact, the design wave height is evaluated, which represents the maximum value expected during the service life of the structure with vertical part, with which to determine the maximum stresses to which the structure is subjected by wave action, to be used to carry out stability verifications.

According to the Technical Instructions, stability verifications of the structure should be conducted for 4 different failure mechanisms:

1. slip verification;
2. tipping verification;
3. crushing verification of the foundation cliff;
4. slip verification of the complex structure-soil.

The deterministic approach indicated by the Italian guidelines for stability verifications is made explicit through the adoption of specific factors of safety all-inclusive of all uncertainties related to the calculation models adopted for the acting loads and resistant forces.

For stress calculations, the Technical Instructions suggest the use of Saint-Flou's formulas in the case of quasi-stationary waves, while in the case of breaking waves the use of Goda's unmodified formulas is indicated (see Design Formulas section).

In such formulas, the Technical Instructions suggest the use of a wave height less than the maximum wave height expected over the service life of the structure. In particular, a wave height of $H = H_{1/20}$ is recommended for crest phase stability verifications, $h = H/100$ for

preliminary verification of non-slippage in crest phase and for verification of stability in cable phase.

Finally, for the design of the embankment reef, the Italian guidelines, suggest the use of Hudson's Formula for the sizing of the boulders to protect the outer sea-side escarpment; for the design of the dam crest wall, on the other hand, the use of Hiroi's formula is indicated, with which to determine the acting stress.

2.4.4 Technical Standards and commentaries on Port and Harbour Facilities in Japan (2009, 2020)

Japanese regulations referring to the design of vertical-wall dams can be found within the publication "Technical Standards and commentaries on Port and Harbour Facilities in Japan" (2020), which summarizes the ministerial ordinances and public notices as well as related comments and technical notes referring to the "Technical Standards for Port and Harbour Facilities" issued by the Japanese Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism (MLIT) based on the regulatory provisions of the Ports and Harbour Bureau.

The general guidance on the performance-based design system proposed by these guidelines, as discussed in Section 2.3.7 with reference to jetty dams, also applies to vertical-wall dams.

Performance requirements represent the performance that the structure must meet in order for it to be called reliable, achieving the goal set for its construction. Performance criteria are the rules that must be met in order for performance to be guaranteed. Japanese standards identify these rules in methods based on the reliability of the structure also defined as the probability that it will not reach a limit state during its operational life.

As mentioned above in "Technical Standards and Commentaries for Port and Harbour Facilities in Japan (2007)," methods to be adopted for the design of all breakwaters (including vertical-wall breakwaters) based on full-scale reliability are given. They are classified into three levels I, II and III:

- Level III reliability-based design method, to directly calculate the probability of failure using a probability calculation based on the probability distribution of each basic variable.
- Level II reliability-based design method, to evaluate the reliability index β using a probability calculation based on the mean, distribution, and covariance of each basic variable (not dependent on the probability distribution) and evaluating the performance so that β is equal to or greater than the limiting value.
- Design method based on level I reliability to deterministically verify performance by introducing some partial factors into the performance verification equation and replacing the equation with characteristic values for the basic variables to ensure a margin of safety. This method is also called the "partial factor method." The partial factor is determined by the level 3 or 2 reliability-based design method, called "code calibration."

For vertical-wall breakwaters, "Technical Standards and Commentaries for Port and Harbour Facilities in Japan (2007) propose the use of a Level I probabilistic design method, in which partial factors of safety to be applied to the stressing (buckling) actions and resisting forces are adopted for verification at limit states.

For composite vertical wall breakwaters, the table of performance verification steps given in the Japanese guidelines is shown in Figure 2.3.

Attached Table 10-3 Performance Verification Items and Standard Indexes to Determine the Limit Values of Gravity-type Breakwaters (Except Sloping Breakwaters)

Ministerial Ordinance			Public Notice			Performance requirements	Design state			Verification item	Standard index to determine the limit value
Article	Paragraph	Item	Article	Paragraph	Item		State	Dominating action	Non-dominating action		
14	1	2	35	-	1	Serviceability	Permanent	Self-weight	Water pressure	Circular slip failure of ground	Action-resistance ratio with respect to circular slip failure
					2		Variable waves (L1 earthquake ground motion)	Self-weight, water pressure	Sliding/overturning of breakwater body, bearing capacity of foundation ground		

* [] means the alternative dominant action to be studied as design situations.

Figure 2.3 Performance verification items modes of vertical breakwater.

Figure 2.4 shows the tables of partial safety coefficients given by the Japanese guidelines for overturning and sliding verification of vertical-wall breakwaters.

Verification object	Partial factor multiplied by resistance term γ_R	Partial factor multiplied by load term γ_S	Adjustment factor m
Overturning of breakwater body (Variable state of waves)	0.95	1.14	— (1.00)

Verification object	Partial factor multiplied by resistance term γ_R	Partial factor multiplied by load term γ_S	Adjustment factor m
Sliding of a breakwater body (Variable state of waves)	0.83	1.08	— (1.00)

Figure 2.4 Partial Factors used for the performance verification of the overturning (up) and sliding (down) of breakwater bodies.

The technical standards do not exclude but rather encourage the adoption of probabilistic level II and III for the design of vertical-wall dams especially for high-risk areas.

2.4.5 ROM Program

The ROM program developed by the Spanish state institutions (Puertos dos Estado) represents the technical-economic tool developed to support the decision-making process for defining port investment projects.

The specific objective is to provide maritime engineering with an efficient method for the design, construction, maintenance and repair of maritime structures, which, in addition to meeting the technical requirements necessary to guarantee the defined performance levels of the structure, must comply with a set of predetermined environmental, social and economic requirements.

Thus, the method developed and published in ROM 0.0-01 (2002) and ROM (2019) guidelines is a performance method that optimizes design, in which performance can also be defined in terms of the level of acceptable risk. Normally, risk is defined as the product of the probability of noncompliance with requirements by the resulting consequences. In ROMs, on the other hand, the method intends to verify the non-exceedance of a certain threshold value of the joint probability of the various failure mechanisms that may affect the structure, during its service life.

These thresholds, in addition to being based on technical requirements, are also defined by the ROM method, on the basis of the nature and importance of the structure, both economically and socio-environmentally, which is taken into account through the use of the ERI and SERI indicators, mentioned in Section 2.3.8 above referring to jetty dams.

Ultimately, the method proposed by ROM, in its general lines, is defined regardless of the type of breakwater. It provides for the possibility of using type I, II and III probabilistic procedures for the design of structures. In ROM report 0.0-01, examples are given about Level I can be applied to vertical breakwater, by referring to the application of global factors of safety or partial coefficients. The use of the higher probabilistic levels is exclusively prescribed if the greater effort required by these levels of design, in terms of human resources, processing time and therefore investment, is justified by the nature, objectives and importance of the work; for this purpose, the economic and environmental indicators ERI and SERI are used, and if they reach certain values, the designer must use the more stringent design methods of Level II and III.

2.4.6 Coastal Engineering Manual (2002)

The information in Section 2.3.4 also applies with respect to vertical breakwaters. In particular, it should be noted that the EMC, for this type of structure, refers to the partial safety coefficients of the Level I probabilistic method proposed by PIANC (2002), reporting their values in the tables contained within Chapter VI-6-6 of the same manual.

2.5 Regulations for the design of seawalls

While the structural response of seawalls benefits from general regulations for breakwater design, as pointed out in Section 2.3 and Section 2.4, major aspects of functional design remain almost unregulated. The old Italian guidelines for the design of maritime dikes (Consiglio Superiore dei Lavori Pubblici, 1996) characterize wave overtopping as an essentially deterministic process, where it is suggested to fit the coefficients of an empirical formula (Owen, 1980) via specific physical model experiments. Different from structural response, no “calculated risk frame” is suggested, so that the selection of the design storm (in terms of return period) is left to the engineering judgment.

The British Standards 2017 (BSI, 2017) mention wave overtopping at seawalls as a fundamental process to consider, but engineers are essentially referred to research manuals such as “Overtopping of Seawalls” (Besley, 1999) or the most recent version of the EurOtop Manual (2018). It is worth noticing that the inherent large uncertainties that affect wave overtopping are expressly highlighted in several sections of the British Standards, where it is stated that “*Repeating (physical model) tests with the same wave conditions can lead to differences in overtopping*”. Along with the recourse to physical modelling (p. 49), advanced numerical

modelling (e.g. CFD) is suggested in shallow water where the structures are subject to breaking waves and impulsive loadings. However, no clear probabilistic frame is given.

As a sole example of wave overtopping calculation in a probabilistic frame, the Spanish ROM (Puertos del Estado, 2002) provides a second level calculation example where the surface of failure is expressed as the exceeding of a deterministic threshold, namely the crest freeboard (tolerable individual overtopping equal to zero). However, the joint distribution of wave height and period refers to the findings of Longuet-Higgins (1975), which inherently holds in deep water. Hence, the method is hardly realistic under depth-limited conditions.

It should be finally mentioned that, although the currently available design equations generally describe accurately their uncertainties (e.g., as statistical distribution of related parameters), they are inherently unfit for a wave-by-wave analysis as described in the Spanish ROM, as they look at the mean rate of overtopping in a sea-state. Otherwise, the statistical distribution of the individual volume would be necessary, for which the body of existing literature is not equally wide. Moreover, tolerable overtopping volumes are not unanimously established as for the mean rates. As an example, in *Table 5.4* of The Rock Manual (CIRIA et al., 2007), individual volume thresholds for seawalls are not available, while the latest EurOtop Manual (2018, *Table 3.1*) provides general thresholds regardless of the structure involved (e.g. either vertical seawall or rubble mound breakwaters).

Table 2.IX summarizes the above-discussed national and international regulations for the design of seawalls, giving information about the proposed design approach.

Table 2.IX Summary of regulations for the design of seawalls. The star indicates that the design level is suggested without explain a methodology.

Regulation	Country	Year	Design level
Italian guidelines for the design of maritime dikes	Italy	1996	Level 0, I*
ROM 0.0, ROM1.0-09, ROM-1.1-18	Spain	2002, 2010, 2018	Level 0, I, II, III*
The British Standards BS 6349-1-2	UK	2017	Level 0, I, II*, III*
EurOtop Manual	Europe	2018	Level 0, I, II*, III*

2.6 Regulations for the design of artificial beach nourishment

Since the 1980s, there has been a notable shift towards employing "soft" remedial measures such as beach nourishment, mainly due to the limitations and impracticality of "hard" methods such as groins, breakwaters, and seawalls. Currently, beach nourishment, often combined with "supporting structures", has become increasingly significant (Cooper et al., 2009). Many coastal countries globally are now conducting regular beach nourishments as a viable means of erosion mitigation and coastal protection (e.g., Cooke et al., 2012; Hamm et al., 2002; Luo et al., 2016). Artificial beach fill entails adding sand or other sediment to a beach to counter erosion and enhance recreational and ecological benefits. Rather than viewing beach nourishment as beach reconstruction, it should be seen as part of ongoing beach maintenance efforts.

Ideally, beach nourishment initiatives should align with a coordinated national strategy, enhancing strategic beach areas from environmental, social, or economic perspectives. Key technical considerations for beach nourishment include the frequency of intervention and

lifecycle design, sediment volume, grain size compatibility, protective dunes, long-term sand resources, placement location, "hybrid" projects, and down-drift impacts (CUR, 1987). Regulations governing the design of artificial beach nourishment projects vary by jurisdiction, typically encompassing environmental impact assessments, careful selection of sediment sources and compatibility, coastal engineering analysis, permitting processes, stakeholder engagement, and ongoing monitoring and maintenance. Several authorities, non-profit bodies and industry associations have published guidelines dealing with coastal erosion and different types of coastal protection. These guidelines are usually based on experience and engineering recommendations for efficient coastal protection, but also incorporate environmental considerations.

Existing reviews of beach nourishment practice (e.g., Hanson et al., 2002; Bird and Lewis, 2015) have focused on the general design criteria (motivation, techniques and methods) and legal and financial aspects. However, new legal settings (e.g., the Marine Strategy Framework Directive in the EU, cf. European Commission, 2008) and recent research on the environmental impact of beach nourishment activities motivate a comprehensive up-to-date review of beach nourishment strategies with a focus on environmental impacts. Recently, Staudt et al. (2021) reviewed 205 openly accessible coastal management strategies, legal texts, guidelines, EIA documents, websites, project reports, press releases and research publications about beach nourishments in several developed countries around the world. Despite progress in adaptation research, a critical knowledge gap remains regarding the appropriateness and applicability of various adaptation options, including their transferability between different coastal settings. To enhance the protection of coastal resources in a sustainable way, beach and shoreface nourishment can be part of broader integrated coastal management zone management (ICZM) plans⁸, but coordination at different spatial levels of governance is required.

2.6.1 In the absence of explicit references to the probabilistic nature of input variables, it can be reasonably inferred that the design approach adopted in existing regulations for the design of artificial beach nourishment is of a traditional deterministic type. Consequently, due to the lack of detailed methodological indications or probabilistic frameworks, a comparative table has not been included. *Italy regulations*

Italy stands out as an exception to the trend observed in other European countries, as the number of beach fills has decreased in recent years. With a coastline stretching 7,500 km, nearly half of which comprises low-lying alluvial beds highly susceptible to coastal erosion, Italy places significant importance on coastline engineering, especially evident in tourist destinations like the northern Adriatic beaches, attracting over 90 million tourists annually. Since 1969, modern beach fills have been practiced in Italy, with approximately 50 fills completed in 36 sites, totaling about 15 million cubic meters of fill volume. These projects typically involve a combination of sand nourishment and hard structures (Benassai et al., 1997), with most projects based on a generic design incorporating both hard and soft structures.

While minor projects often rely on simple scoping methods for design, larger projects employ more refined methodologies, considering factors such as longshore sediment transport rates and volume budgets. However, monitoring of beach fills in Italy is limited or nonexistent, with

⁸<https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/adaptation-options/adaptation-of-integrated-coastal-management-plans>

no established methodology for maintenance schemes or performance evaluation. In addition, the Dutch CUR (1987) manual is consulted in determining long-term trends, renourishment intervals, etc. These projects were, however, undertaken in the framework of the Special Law for the Safeguard of Venice (Law of April 16th, 1973 no. 171). Coastal waters and beaches in Italy are State-owned, with initial costs typically borne by the state and maintenance responsibilities formally assigned to regional governments. However, exceptions exist for emergency measures, where funds may come from the state, while revenues generated from coastal activities accrue to municipalities. Legislation such as the Law no. 542 of 14 July 1907, titled "*Legge per la difesa degli abitati dall'erosione marina*", repealed by Law no. 9 of 18 February 2009 "*Conversione in legge, con modificazioni, del decreto-legge 22 dicembre 2008, n. 200, recante misure urgenti in materia di semplificazione normativa*" and the Decree Law no. 431 of 8 August 1985 noted as "*Legge Galasso*" regulate coastal defenses and development, with restrictions on development imposed to ensure sustainable exploitation of coastal areas. New legislative developments, including a coastal plan and potential transfer of competence from the state to regions, are expected to enhance coastal zone management. The regions were requested to issue territorial and landscape plans aimed at regulating the uses of these areas and ensuring their sustainable exploitation. Stabilization of dunes to protect the hinterland is now being considered. New legislative developments are expected by the application of the so-called "coastal plan", currently under preparation by the Ministry of the Environment. Other new legislative developments that could eventually move in the direction of "coastal zone management" are also expected following the possible adoption of the strategic environmental assessment for the coastal zone and the transfer of competence from the State to the regions (Presidential Decree (DPR) no. 616 of 24 July 1997, Article 69, paragraph 6).

The MATTM-REGIONI agreement, also known as the Intergovernmental Agreement between the Ministry of the Environment and the Regions, is a significant agreement in Italy regarding environmental management and policy coordination. This agreement aims to establish a framework for collaboration and coordination between the central government, represented by the Ministry of the Environment, Land and Sea (MATTM), and the regional governments (Regioni). Italy's regional governments have significant autonomy in various policy areas, including environmental protection and management. The MATTM-REGIONI agreement serves as a mechanism to ensure coherence and consistency in environmental policies and initiatives across the country while respecting the specific characteristics and priorities of each region. Key aspects of this document include policy coordination, resource allocation, data sharing and monitoring, and the legal framework. Overall, the MATTM-REGIONI agreement plays a crucial role in promoting collaboration and synergy between the central government and regional authorities to address environmental challenges effectively and achieve sustainable development goals across Italy.

In Italy the main regulations dealing with the beach nourishment regards the sourcing of filler material, which can occur either through land borrow pits, by extracting suitable sands from the sea, or by exploiting dredging operations in port areas. The use of dredged material from ports for replenishment, if of acceptable quality, occurs both during construction and operation phases. In the latter case, the problem of port siltation is simultaneously addressed by creating a sand bypass system, where sands are pumped through pipelines downstream of the port (submerged) by dredges and/or fixed onshore facilities, restoring natural littoral drift. However,

recent regulations (Legislative Decree 152/06, Legislative Decree 4/2008, Law 2/2009 and subsequent amendments) require prior environmental characterization of dredged sediments for consideration of their reuse or for correct waste disposal.

2.6.2 United States regulations

The United States is a global leader in beach renourishment projects, primarily due to widespread erosion affecting approximately 90% of its coastlines (Leatherman, 1988). Renourishment efforts have been ongoing since the early 20th century, with documented projects dating back to 1922 at Coney Island, New York (Campbell and Benedet, 2006). By 2006, over 200 areas had undergone renourishment, resulting in the deposition of around 9 million cubic meters of sediment annually (Campbell and Benedet, 2006). Consequently, the US has emerged as the foremost country globally in terms of experience, the number of projects, and the volume of sediment nourished (Basco, 1999). Elko et al. (2021) analyzed decadal and regional trends in beach nourishment in the US since its inception nearly 100 years ago. Over the last century, beaches in more than 475 US communities have been restored with over 1.5 billion cubic yards (1.2 billion cubic meters) of sand, with over 3200 individual nourishment events occurring.

However, regulations for artificial beach renourishment in the US are dispersed and lack uniformity. States experiencing severe beach erosion typically implement their own comprehensive beach nourishment policies and funding mechanisms. While most nourishment projects receive federal funding for erosion control and flood mitigation, some also aim at recreational enhancements and the beneficial use of dredged sediment. For federally funded projects, standardized designs outlined in the Coastal Engineering Manual are adhered to, while non-federal projects managed by local governments and private owners may vary in design and policy (USACE, 2002).

In the US, beach nourishment is primarily evaluated for its structural damage mitigation benefits, particularly widened beaches, through the calculation of benefit-cost (B/C) ratios. Each site-specific case is evaluated separately to determine if the benefits exceed the costs. However, there is a significant backlog in Corps of Engineers projects with B/C ratios greater than 1 but still unfunded due to political and budget reasons (Hillyer, 1996).

Debates have arisen in the United States regarding the appropriate federal role in beach nourishment activities and the allocation of funding. Some opponents argue that federal funding for nourishment projects is wasteful and has led to the accelerated development of vulnerable coastal areas, putting more people and properties at risk (Trembanis, Pilkey, and Valverde, 1999). Moreover, protection benefits are seen as temporary and poorly documented, with primary beneficiaries often being private property owners and recreational interests (Carter, 2012).

Like European shoreline management, beach nourishment is the preferred coastal management tool in the US to adapt to sea-level rise and reduce potential storm damage (Young and Coburn, 2017; Young, 2019). However, a nationwide, long-term strategy for beach nourishment is lacking in the US, with individual coastal states responsible for formulating their own strategies and policies (National Research Council, 1995).

The National Research Council (1994, 1995) has comprehensive experience with nourishment activities in the USA, covering engineering and environmental aspects. A widely referenced documents focusing on US coasts are the Coastal Engineering Manual (CEM) by the US Army Corps of Engineers (2002) and the *Engineering and Design of beach fills* (USACE, 1995, Manual No.1110-2-3301). The additional manual “Environmental Engineering for Coastal Shore Protection” contains recommendations for environmental monitoring programs, data collection, habitat assessment etc. (USACE, 1989).

The American Shore and Beach Preservation Association (ASBPA) has leveraged the expertise of their membership and key partners such as the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers’ (USACE) Regional Sediment Management (RSM) Program to compile the ASBPA National Beach Nourishment Database and host the database online (<https://asbpa.org/>). The database provides details of U.S. beach nourishment events (year, volume, length, cost, etc.).

Today, beach nourishment projects are regulated by state and federal agencies and typically administered by federal, state, or local government entities. The National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) of 1970 requires federal agencies to assess the environmental effects of their proposed actions prior to making permitting or construction decisions. Consultations with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and NOAA’s National Marine Fisheries Service at a minimum are required for beach projects. Congress enacted Public Law 71–520 authorized the USACE to conduct shore erosion studies in cooperation with states in 1930. The USACE helped states in this planning and technical advisory role for decades until the first federal Beach Erosion Control project was built in Carolina Beach, NC in 1964. Federal beach projects are currently authorized for a 50-year project life by Congress in the Water Resource Development Act (e.g., USACE, 2019). Funding for the initial nourishment and subsequent renourishments are appropriated as necessary. Over the years, the project classification has changed from beach erosion control to shore protection, to storm damage reduction. However, the beach nourishment projects continue to be funded through the USACE flood control authority. A second type of federal project that results in beach nourishment is funded through the navigation authority. Section 111 of the River and Harbor Act of 1968 allows for federal nourishment to mitigate damages caused by federal navigation projects. The individual coastal states are responsible for strategies and policies regarding beach nourishments, which is why no nation-wide, long-term strategy exists. The legislative framework for the state policies, the Coastal Zone Management Act (1972), which includes the (voluntary) national Coastal Zone Management (CZM) Program, enables the single states to pass individual laws enforcing beach nourishments (National Research Council, 1995). Those states which carry out many beach nourishments (e.g. North Carolina, California and Florida) have incorporated this concept into their legislation (Hedrick, 2000). In total, 21 states had developed dedicated beach nourishment policies by the year 2000. In addition, six states (California, Florida, North Carolina, Ohio, Rhode Island and South Carolina) have issued their own explicit guidelines on where to deposit sand during beach nourishment projects (Hedrick, 2000). While implementation of the CZM Program is conducted and financed at state level, the program is administered by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA).

2.6.3 Netherlands’s regulations

Notably, the Netherlands has pioneered the concept of mega-nourishment, exemplified by the Sand Engine project, which entailed the placement of 21.5 Mm³ of sediment along the coast of

the Hague in 2011 (Stive et al., 2013). Since the 1970s, modern beach fills have been commonplace in the Netherlands, driven by centuries-long efforts to safeguard against flooding. Recently, the "Building with nature" project, part of the Interreg North Sea Region Initiative, aims to produce new guidelines for the design of coastal structures, including artificial beach nourishment, in the North Sea countries.

Previously, Dutch policy leaned towards selective retreat, but following devastating floods in 1953, it shifted towards dynamic preservation, aiming to compensate for natural erosion through nourishment efforts to maintain the 1990 coastline position nationally. Coastal protection responsibility is shared between national (Rijkswaterstaat with local offices) and regional authorities (water boards), with strict design parameters dictating nourishment volumes and effectiveness factors (CUR, 1987). The Sea Defence Law of 1996 regulates coastal safety responsibility and task divisions between government and regional authorities, with the overall supervision by the Minister of Transport, Public Works, and Water Management. Collaboration between levels of government ensures coastal management aligns with regional planning policies.

The Netherlands has the most strategic long-term approach to beach renourishment, characterized by rigid design and legislation, primarily using the "Dutch Method" but also experimenting with localized large-scale beach renourishment (Royal Haskoning DHV, 2009; Stive et al., 2013).

The Netherlands has a national strategy to maintain the shoreline of 1990, implemented by the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management (Hillen and Roelse, 1995).

2.6.4 UK regulations

In the United Kingdom, since the 1950s, coastal defense efforts are primarily organized through management plans, with funding typically provided by central government, quasi-governmental agencies, and local councils. Increasingly, financial contributions are sought from other stakeholders as well. In the UK, beach renourishment is considered among a range of responses to coastal challenges, with evaluations conducted against technical, economic, environmental, and legislative criteria (Hanson et al., 2002).

To address past issues where coastal defense schemes relocated rather than solve flooding or erosion problems, a national strategy for planning and installing defenses has been introduced. Coastal management schemes in the UK now involve shoreline management plans for each coastal 'cell', integrating relevant information on coastal attributes and processes. Recommendations are made based on consultations and may involve shoreline maintenance, advancement, or retreat, depending on the circumstances. When intervention is deemed necessary, more detailed planning and site study are undertaken to determine the most effective form of works, often including beach nourishment. The Beach Management Manual and government policies provide guidance and frameworks for coastal defense strategies (Simmonds et al., 1996).

Coastal defense in England, Scotland, and Wales is regulated under the Coast Protection Act (1949), with local government authorities responsible for implementation. The Environment Agency plays a supervisory role in sea defense works to protect against flooding, while funding for coastal defense projects comes from various sources including central government,

environmental agencies, and local authorities. The department responsible for coastal defense in each region will give ultimate approval and may assist financially with a scheme. Sea defense in England and Wales may be undertaken by the environment agency who has the overall supervisory powers to protect against flooding, under the Water Resources Act (1991). Sea defense works may also be undertaken by councils or by internal drainage boards, under the Land Drainage Act (1991), and owners may undertake works on their own property. Efforts to monitor the efficiency of large-scale schemes are ongoing through regular beach profile collections. Coastal managers in the UK have also explored the potential effectiveness of mega-nourishment along the coastline and are designing large-scale projects such as 'beach scraping' in Norfolk. Publications like the CIRIA Beach Management Manual (Rogers et al., 2010) and the Shoreline Management Guidelines (Mangor et al., 2017) provide guidelines for beach nourishments, based on experience, modeling, and comprehensive information about environmental impacts during nourishment activities. While the former manual gives a detailed description of beach management practice (and legal framework) in the UK, the latter is intended as a practical handbook for international stakeholders, e.g. coastal managers, planners and engineers.

2.6.5 Spain regulations

In Spain, particularly along the Mediterranean coast where tourist demand is high, numerous beach fills have been implemented, with approximately 600 projects completed over 13 years (Hanson et al., 2002). These efforts, primarily aimed at enhancing recreational beach use, have been particularly prevalent due to the interruption of sand transport by harbor installations, causing erosion along the coast. Since 1983, modern beach fills have been practiced, typically without supporting structures, although detached breakwaters are occasionally used.

Financial processes for beach nourishment in Spain are regulated by the Shores Act of 1989, which designates all beaches as State-owned and imposes restrictions on building and development within a designated protection zone landward from the beach. While the act stipulates that coastal defense is the responsibility of the central government, funding for projects may involve contributions from regional governments, local authorities, international organizations, and private entities. In practice, almost all nourishments are financed by the central government because, according to the Shores Act, coastal defense is strictly its responsibility.

Despite the existence of a comprehensive database about the physical characteristics of Spanish beaches, and although several approaches have been made to implement the ICZM approach in Spain and to develop a national strategy for coastal management, no national master plan exists (Barragán Muñoz, 2010; Sanò et al., 2010). It has been hypothesized by Ariza (2011) that the absence of a responsible institution for coastal management might be the main reason. However, a 2016 strategy for climate change adaptation of the Spanish coast lists beach nourishments and artificial dunes as measures to counter coastal erosion (MAPAMA, 2016).

2.6.6 Germany regulations

Germany, along with other nations, is actively developing sophisticated regulations and engineering practices to address the challenges of coastal protection and management, particularly in the context of climate change. With a coastline spanning 1900 km, of which nearly one-third consists of sandy beaches prone to erosion, Germany has implemented various

measures to safeguard its coastal areas. The transition from hard to soft protection measures in Germany's sandy coastal zones began in 1951 with the first modern fill on the Island of Norderney.

Coastal protection in Germany is governed by well-developed, long-term strategies, regulated by constitutional law and federal legislation. The Conflicting Legislation Act allows the national government to intervene when state legislation conflicts or lacks effectiveness. The five coastal federal states have formulated special regulations for coastal protection in their federal legislation. Although these regulations differ in certain aspects, the national government has not yet made any use of the Conflicting Legislation Act. The national government, being aware of its overall responsibility, financially supports the coastal protection works of the coastal federal states. This support is subsidiary, i.e., national funds are only granted if matched by funds from the concerned federal states.

Since 1950, over 95% of nourishment sites in Germany have benefited from general protection guidelines or site-specific master plans, with the remainder financed by local authorities for recreational purposes. The "*Empfehlungen für Küstenschutzwerke*" (Recommendations for Coastal Protection Structures) issued in 1993 provide guidance on coastal protection practices in Germany, serving as a reference for engineering and design standards in coastal projects. These recommendations contribute to the ongoing efforts to ensure the safety and resilience of Germany's coastal infrastructure amid changing environmental conditions. A more recent version of the recommendations exists (Ausschuss für Küstenschutzwerke der DGEG und der HTG, 2007). However, the chapter about nourishments has not been updated since its original publication in the beginning of the 1990s. In a current research project (Interreg VB NSR: Building with Nature) an international group of coastal authorities from the North Sea region evaluates the technical design criteria for beach nourishments along their coastlines, aiming at the development of new design guidelines (Wilmink et al. 2017).

2.6.7 France regulations

In France, coastal defense works are significant, but beach nourishment is considered a marginal technique for erosion control. Traditionally, France's approach to beach nourishment involves coupling it with hard structures to minimize sand losses and maintenance efforts. Major nourishment projects often involve using sand dredged from nearby harbors to maintain navigable depths.

The design methods for coastal defense works in France are well-developed, with detailed design studies conducted for numerous projects, based on the well-known coastal engineering concepts (CERC, 1984), but also includes environmental considerations. Under the "*Loi relative au dessèchement des marais*", 16 septembre 1807, art. 33 (Fr.), retrieved via Legifrance, the Ministry of Public Works certifies the necessity of coastal defense works, and the costs are typically borne by the protected landowners in proportion to their interests. However, subsidies from public funds may be provided in certain cases. Despite this, subsidies have generally been limited due to the constrained financial resources allocated to coastal defense works. This law also sets out guidelines for the so-called 'compulsory' associations that are responsible for having these works carried out and maintained.

France lacks a national coastal management framework, and each project is managed according to local conditions. However, there is a gradual shift towards regional collaboration and

awareness of the need for regional planning in coastal management. The Littoral Law of 1986 extends the concept of coastal defense works to natural sites and imposes accreditation procedures for large-budget projects. It also prohibits new artificial beach developments and emphasizes the protection of the natural state of the coastline. Efforts to improve coherence between earlier laws and newer environmental legislation are underway.

2.6.8 Denmark regulations

In Denmark, the coastline stretches over 7400 km, with historical interventions like marram grass planting stabilizing dunes on the North Sea coast about a century ago. However, subsequent construction of harbors and groin groups led to significant down-drift erosion, causing the disappearance, or weakening of dunes along a 50 km stretch by 1982. To address this erosion, a coastal protection scheme was initiated in 1982. The primary strategy involved reinforcing dunes wherever possible. In areas where dune reinforcement wasn't feasible, revetments were constructed to protect the remaining dunes. Low detached breakwaters were also used in highly exposed stretches with nourishment efforts. Approximately 97% of the nourishment volume was focused on the North Sea coast, where dunes shield the low hinterland from flooding. The policy formulated in 1982 aimed to reestablish and maintain a safety level against flooding with a minimum 100-year return period, halt erosion near coastal towns, and reduce erosion in areas where it would jeopardize flood safety within the next century.

Unlike some other countries, Denmark doesn't prioritize the need for wider beaches for recreational purposes, as it boasts a high number and total length of quality beaches relative to potential users. The principal design parameters for coastal protection projects in Denmark include autonomous erosion rates, desired project lifetimes, and the effectiveness factor of nourishment sand. Autonomous erosion calculations are based on regression analyses of erosion in different profile segments. The policy dictates that beaches should be renourished annually to counteract erosion caused by storms with a 1-year return period. However, excessive nourishment volumes can negatively impact beach quality. Full-scale tests have shown that nourishment projects with a lifespan of around 3 years can effectively protect the shoreface portion of the profile (James, 1975). In Denmark, safety assessments and erosion control policies are established through agreements between local authorities and the national government, based on recommendations from Danish coastal authorities. These agreements are renegotiated every 5 years, with costs shared between the government and local authorities. Coastal protection regulations differ for the Baltic Sea and Kattegat coasts, governed by an act passed in 1988. Under this act, counties are responsible for administering coastal protection projects, with assistance provided by the coastal authority during planning stages and consulting firms during project execution. Unlike the North Sea coast, there is generally no public funding for coastal protection in this region, with costs borne by individual landowners. The coastal authority oversees permitting for coastal protection and other structures in the coastal zone.

The Danish Coastal Authority (Kystdirektoratet) has set up a separate policy for safety assessment and erosion control, which is used to manage the nourishment activities in critically eroding areas. This policy is re-negotiated every five years. From 1983 until 2015, Denmark has nourished its coastlines along the North and Baltic Seas with an average of 1.8 million m³ per year; in 2015 the annual nourishment volume had reached 2.5 million m³. The efficiency of the nourishment strategy is evaluated through annual beach profiles. In case the nourishments contribute to national flood safety (i.e. in highly erosive areas at the West coast), the activities

are planned, financed and maintained by the government and local authorities; in all other cases the individual landowners are responsible for coastal protection (Kystdirektoratet, 2015a,b).

3. Collection of design formulas for coastal and harbor defense structures

3.1 Overview

The present chapter provides a collection of formulas for the design of rubble-mound breakwaters, vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments, which are obtained from existing research papers and design guidelines. The selected formulas refer to the main failure modes of each considered structure type. Moreover, only formulas valid for newly built coastal and harbor defense solutions are available.

3.2 Design formulas for rubble-mound breakwaters

As shown in Figure 3.1, the generic rubble-mound breakwater is built of several layers, namely the outer armor layer, one or more filter layers, the core, the toe berm. In the case of harbor breakwaters, a conglomerate superstructure is usually present. The design of each part of such a kind of structure is a very complex task, because of the stochastic nature of external forcing and structure response to solicitations. The design phase is affected by even more uncertainty when referring to upgrading solutions of existing breakwaters, which are usually non-conventional structures whose characterization is often difficult because of the lack of historical documentation on the suffered damages as well as repair and modification interventions. For this reason, the existing design formulas refer only to newly built structures.

The traditional design of breakwaters is an iterative process. After the preliminary definition of the breakwater dimensions, based on the analysis of the wave run-up and overtopping phenomena under the wave design conditions, size and weight of the units of the armor layer are computed, and the number of layers is selected also based on the unit type. Then, the dimensions of the toe berm and of the quarry stones that compose it are calculated. The thickness of the filter and bedding layers is also computed, and the size of material for their construction is selected. Finally, the foundations of the structure as well as the stability of the superstructure are verified. The obtained design is corrected if the design requirements are not satisfied, and the above-mentioned steps are repeated if necessary. All the design computations are made by using state-of-the-art empirical formulations, which have been developed for different kinds of rubble-mound breakwaters (i.e. rock- or artificial block-armored, emerged, low-crested or submerged) and wave conditions (i.e. shallow or deep waters, breaking and non-breaking waves). The probabilistic design approach also employs the above-mentioned empirical formulations, which can be rewritten in the form of reliability functions including the acceptance limits set for the considered failure mechanisms.

As already stated, the modelling of the correlation between failure modes is still a challenge (see Section 2.2). In particular, for the case of multilayer rubble-mound breakwaters with superstructure, a great variety of failure modes can occur, whose reciprocal interactions are often complex and hardly comprehensible. Indeed, rubble-mound breakwaters show a more flexible behavior than other typology of breakwaters (e.g. vertical breakwaters), which make the comprehension of the response mechanisms of this kind of structures even more challenging. Figure 3.1, adapted from Burcharth and Liu (1995), summarizes the main failure modes typical

of rubble-mound breakwaters. Failure can occur because of the erosion of the armor layer, both on the sea and rear side. Besides the armor hydraulic instability, the breakage of the armor units can take place, due to wave induced stresses, cracking processes resulting from thermal stress and fatigue of concrete. In addition, toe berm erosion as well as scour at the toe could lead to the failure of the whole structure. Slip failure can affect various part of the breakwater, i.e. toe berm, core, filter and armor layer. Moreover, settlement of the core and of the subsoil can occur, as well as instability of the filter layer. The impact of the wave load can also induce the breakage or the sliding of the wave wall. Finally, huge overtopping discharges can cause the failure to satisfy the design requirements of protection.

In the present work, only the formulas referred to the following failure modes are reviewed:

- armor hydraulic instability;
- excessive mean wave overtopping discharge.

Figure 3.1 Failure modes of rubble-mound breakwaters. Adapted from Burcharth and Liu (1995).

3.2.1 Hydraulic instability of the armor layer

The estimation of hydraulic stability for rock armor units is a standard practice among coastal engineers. Design formulas in engineering manuals are semi-empirical and primarily derived from datasets obtained through small-scale physical model experiments. Rock armor stability differs from other structural designs due to its variability, which is complex and difficult to quantify given the wide range and numerous permutations of the variables involved. Its complexity arises from the stochastic nature of wave loading and structure response, influenced by the random armor shape, orientation, and contact/interlocking between armor units, as well as the wide variation in structure and armor characteristics.

Existing literature provides two kinds of empirical formulations, namely hydraulic stability formulas and damage progression models. The hydraulic stability formulas express the fact that the stability of the armor layer is reached when the stability number N_s is lower than a certain function f (Campos et al., 2020):

$$N_s = \frac{H}{\Delta D_{n50}} < f(K, p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n) \quad (3.1)$$

where H is the wave height, $\Delta = (\rho_a - \rho_w)/\rho_w$ is the relative buoyant density of the armor units, D_{n50} is the mean nominal diameter of the armor units, K is an empirical coefficient, and (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n) are n parameters influencing the structure stability.

Instead, the damage progression models correlate progressive damage levels to the characteristics of the structure and of the external forcing, in some cases including also the damage time evolution. Damage of the armor layer is usually measured using one of the following parameters:

- the percentage of displaced units, which is defined as follows (Hudson, 1959):

$$N_d = \frac{N_{moved}}{N_{tot}} \cdot 100 \quad (3.2)$$

where N_{moved} is the number of displaced units and N_{tot} is the total number of units inside the considered area. The unit displacement is usually defined as position shifted more than a distance equal to the median nominal diameter of the armor units (D_{n50});

- the number of displaced units out of the armor layer within a strip of breakwater slope of width D_{n50} , which is defined as follows (van der Meer, 1988a):

$$N_{od} = \frac{N_{moved}}{B_{RMB}/D_{n50}} \cdot 100 \quad (3.3)$$

where B is the width of the tested section;

- the eroded volume per unit length, which is defined as follows (Broderick and Ahrens, 1982):

$$S_{BA} = \frac{A_e}{D_{n50}^2} \quad (3.4)$$

where A_e is the eroded area of the considered cross-section with respect to the zero-damage condition.

The parameter S appears particularly suitable for rubble-mound breakwaters made up by quarry stones with a certain size grading, for which the evaluation of the eroded volume provides useful insight on the damage processes. Instead, the parameter N_{od} is largely employed for artificial units-armored structures. In this latter case, the armor units have all the same diameter, which is simply called D_n .

It should be noted that the parameter H corresponds to the wave height of a sinusoidal wave when the formula is calibrated on experimental data acquired during regular wave tests. In this case, the selection of the design wave from a natural wave train is not straightforward. The replacement of H with the significant wave height (H_s or $H_{1/3}$, i.e. the average wave height of the $N/3$ highest waves in a sea state composed of N waves), the $H_{1/10}$ or the $H_{1/20}$ (i.e. the average wave height of the $N/10$ and $N/20$ highest waves in a sea state composed of N waves, respectively) has been suggested by manuals and experimental investigations, as highlighted by Campos et al. (2020). When the formula is calibrated on experimental data acquired during irregular wave tests, the significant wave height is usually employed as descriptor of the acting wave load.

In Table 3.I the currently employed empirical formulations for the design of the armor layer of the structure trunk are summarized, together with the ones proposed by some recent research works. Only rocks and the most employed artificial concrete units are considered, namely cubes, Antifer (which are assimilated to cubes), Tetrapod, Accropode, Dolos, and Seebes. Figure 3.2 presents a classification of concrete armor units based on shape, number of layers, placement method, and stability factor. Moreover, the cases of berm breakwaters and composite breakwaters are not included.

Placement	Shape				Number of layers
	Massive	Bulky	Slender	Multi-hole	
Randomly Placed	Antifer Cube (1973)	Stabil (1961) Akmon (1962)	Tetrapod (1950) Dolos (1963)		Double
		Accropode (1980) Xbloc (2003) Accropode II (2004) Core-loc (1995)	A-Jack (1998)		Single
Pattern- or random placed	Cube Cubipod (2016)				Double / Single
Pattern-Placed	Non-interlocking			Cob (1969) Shed (1982) Seabee (1978)	Single
	Interlocking	XblocPlus (2018) C-Roc (2018)		WEIGHT INTERLOCKING FRICTION	

Figure 3.2 Classification of concrete armor units (Scaravaglione et al., 2022).

Figure 3.3 explains the geometrical characteristics of a rock-armored breakwater which are included in the design formulas. The sketch of an artificial block-armored breakwater closely resembles the rock-armored version illustrated in Figure 3.3, with the only difference being the use of concrete armor units instead of rocks. The other variables employed for the design (e.g. empirical coefficients, armor unit characteristics, wave forcing descriptors) are described in the caption of Table 3.I. For the sake of clarity, the definitions of wave steepness (s) and Iribarren number (ξ), which are frequently included in the formulas, are here provided:

$$s = \frac{2\pi H_s}{gT^2} \tag{3.5}$$

$$\xi = s^{-0.5} \tan \alpha \tag{3.6}$$

where H_s is the significant wave height, g is the gravity acceleration and α is the breakwater slope. Both s and ξ have the subscript “ m ”, “ p ” or “ $m - 1,0$ ” depending on the considered wave period, namely the mean wave period T_m , the peak wave period T_p or the spectral wave period $T_{m-1,0}$. The knowledge of the Iribarren number, which combines armor layer slope and wave steepness, allows the identification of type of breaking of the waves which reach the structure. In particular, the design formulations usually consider the following classification: i) plunging waves when the Iribarren number is lower than ξ_{cr} ; ii) surging waves when the Iribarren number is higher than ξ_{cr} . The critical Iribarren number is defined as follows:

$$\xi_{cr} = \left(\frac{c_{Pl}}{c_s} P^{0.31} (\tan \alpha)^{0.5} \right)^{1/(P+0.5)} \tag{3.7}$$

where c_{Pl} and c_S are two empirical coefficients employed in the plunging and surging wave formulas, respectively, and P is the notional permeability factor (see Figure 3.4).

The formulas presented in Table 3.1 were developed considering orthogonal wave attack, which is expected to produce a more intense load than oblique waves. Therefore, when the incident waves are oblique, the armor size calculated with the state-of-art design formulas can be reduced, using empirical reduction factors (Bali et al., 2022, 2023).

Figure 3.3 Sketch of a rock-armored breakwater. The geometrical characteristics of the structure considered by armor stability and mean wave overtopping discharge formulas are indicated.

Figure 3.4 Notional permeability factor (van der Meer, 1988a).

In the following, the most employed formulas among the ones presented in Table 3.1 are discussed, distinguishing between rock-armored and artificial block-armored breakwaters. For the latter case, design recommendations are provided also for those units for which a specific design formula does not exist yet.

Table 3.1 Summary of existing formulas for the design of the armor units of rubble-mound breakwaters. The symbols are defined in the section List of symbols and acronyms (continues).

Reference	Structure	Armor unit	Wave condition	Formula
Hudson (1974)	Two-layer armored, non-overtopped	Various	Regular waves, deep and shallow waters, breaking and non-breaking waves	$W_{50} = \frac{\rho_a g H^3}{K_D \Delta^3 \cot \alpha} \rightarrow \frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} = \frac{(K_D \cot \alpha)^{1/3}}{1.27} \quad (3.8)$ <p style="text-align: center;">with CV = 18%</p>
Powell and Allsop (1985)	Two-layer armored, overtopped but not submerged, low-crested	Rock	Irregular waves	$\frac{N_{od}}{N_a} = a \exp [b s_p^{-1/3} H_s / (\Delta D_{n50})] \rightarrow \frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} = \frac{s_p^{1/3}}{b} \ln \left(\frac{1 N_{od}}{a N_{tot}} \right) \quad (3.9)$
van der Meer (1988a)	Two-layer armored, non-overtopped	Rock	Irregular waves, deep waters, shallow waters	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} = \begin{cases} c_{Pl} \cdot S_{BA}^{0.2} P^{0.18} N^{-0.1} \xi_m^{-0.5} & (\text{plunging waves } \xi_m < \xi_{cr}) \\ c_S \cdot S_{BA}^{0.2} P^{-0.13} N^{-0.1} (\cot \alpha)^{0.5} \xi_m^P & (\text{surging waves } \xi_m > \xi_{cr}, \cot \alpha < 4) \end{cases}$ <p style="text-align: center;">for $0.005 < s_m < 0.06$</p> <p style="text-align: center;">where</p> $c_{Pl} = \begin{cases} 6.2 \text{ (CV = 6.5\%)} & \text{for deep waters} \\ 8.7 \text{ (CV = 6.5\%)} & \text{for shallow waters} \end{cases}$ $c_S = \begin{cases} 1.0 \text{ (CV = 8\%)} & \text{for deep waters} \\ 1.4 \text{ (CV = 8\%)} & \text{for shallow waters} \end{cases}$ <p style="text-align: right;">$N \leq 7500$ (for higher values, $N = 7500$) and $0.1 \leq P \leq 0.6$</p>

Table 3.1 Summary of existing formulas for the design of the armor units of rubble-mound breakwaters. The symbols are defined in the section List of symbols and acronyms (follows).

Reference	Structure	Armor unit	Wave condition	Formula
van der Meer (1991)	Two-layer armored, overtopped but not submerged, low-crested	Rock	Irregular waves, deep and shallow waters	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta f_i D_{n50}} = \begin{cases} c_{Pl} \cdot S_{BA}^{0.2} P^{0.18} N^{-0.1} \xi_m^{-0.5} & \text{(plunging waves } \xi_m < \xi_{cr} \text{)} \\ c_S \cdot S_{BA}^{0.2} P^{-0.13} N^{-0.1} (\cot \alpha)^{0.5} \xi_m^P & \text{(surging waves } \xi_m > \xi_{cr} \text{)} \end{cases}$ <p>for $0.005 < s_m < 0.06$</p> <p>where</p> $c_{Pl} = \begin{cases} 6.2 \text{ (CV = 6.5\%)} & \text{for deep waters} \\ 8.7 \text{ (CV = 6.5\%)} & \text{for shallow waters} \end{cases}$ $c_S = \begin{cases} 1.0 \text{ (CV = 8\%)} & \text{for deep waters} \\ 1.4 \text{ (CV = 8\%)} & \text{for shallow waters} \end{cases}$ <p>$N \leq 7500$ (for higher values, $N = 7500$) and $0.1 \leq P \leq 0.6$</p> $f_i = \left(1.25 - 4.8 \frac{R_c}{H_s} \sqrt{\frac{s_p}{2\pi}} \right)^{-1} \text{ for } 0 < \frac{R_c}{H_s} \sqrt{\frac{s_p}{2\pi}} < 0.052$
van der Meer (1991)	Two-layer armored, submerged	Rock	Irregular waves	$\frac{h'_c}{h} = (c_{sub} + 0.1S) \exp(-0.14N_s \cdot s_p^{-1/3})$ <p>where $c_{sub} = 2.1$ (CV = 17%)</p>
Melby and Kobayashi (1998)	Two-layer armored, 1:2 slope, marginally overtopped	Rock	Irregular waves, breaking condition	$[\bar{S}(t)]^{1/b_{MK}} = [\bar{S}(t_n)]^{1/b_{MK}} + (a_S N_S^5)^{1/b_{MK}} \frac{t - t_n}{T_m}; \quad t_n \leq t \leq t_{n+1}$

Table 3.1 Summary of existing formulas for the design of the armor units of rubble-mound breakwaters. The symbols are defined in the section List of symbols and acronyms (follows).

Reference	Structure	Armor unit	Wave condition	Formula
van Gent et al. (2003)	Two-layer armored, non-overtopped	Rock	Irregular waves, shallow waters	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} = \begin{cases} c_{PI} \cdot S_{BA}^{0.2} P^{0.18} N^{-0.1} \frac{H_s}{H_{2\%}} \xi_{m-1,0}^{-0.5} & (\text{plunging waves } \xi_{m-1,0} < \xi_{cr}) \\ c_S \cdot S_{BA}^{0.2} P^{-0.13} N^{-0.1} \frac{H_s}{H_{2\%}} (\cot \alpha)^{0.5} \xi_{m-1,0}^P & (\text{surging waves } \xi_{m-1,0} \geq \xi_{cr}) \end{cases}$ <p style="text-align: right;">(3.14)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">where</p> <p style="text-align: center;">$c_{PI} = 8.4$ (CV = 8%) and $c_S = 1.3$ (CV = 12%)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">$N \leq 7500$ (for higher values, $N = 7500$) and $0.1 \leq P \leq 0.6$</p>
van Gent et al. (2004)	Two-layer, slope 1:2 and 1:4, non-overtopped	Rock	Irregular waves, deep and shallow waters, breaking and non-breaking conditions	$\frac{S_{BA}}{\sqrt{N}} = \left(0.57 \frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} \sqrt{\tan \alpha} \frac{1}{1 + D_{n50core}/D_{n50}} \right)^5$ <p style="text-align: right;">(3.15)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">for $0.6 < \frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} < 4.3$, $1 < \xi_m < 5$, $0.18 < \frac{H_{s0}}{h} < 2.7$, $0 < \frac{D_{n50core}}{D_{n50}} < 2.7$</p> <p style="text-align: center;">with CV = 11%</p>

Table 3.1 Summary of existing formulas for the design of the armor units of rubble-mound breakwaters. The symbols are defined in the section List of symbols and acronyms (follows).

Reference	Structure	Armor unit	Wave condition	Formula
Melby and Hughes (2004); Melby and Kobayashi (2011)	Two-layer armored, 1:1.5 and 1:2 slope, marginally overtopped	Rock	Irregular waves, deep waters using vdm database	$N_m = \begin{cases} 5 P^{0.18} \sqrt{\cot \alpha} \left(\frac{S}{\sqrt{N}}\right)^{0.2} & S_m \geq S_{mc} \\ 5 P^{0.18} \cot \alpha^{0.5-P} \left(\frac{S}{\sqrt{N}}\right)^{0.2} S_m^{\frac{P}{3}} & S_m < S_{mc} \end{cases} \quad (3.16)$ <p>where</p> $N_m = \left(\frac{M_{fmax}}{\rho_w g h^2 \Delta}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} h D_{n50}^{-1}$ $S_{mc} = -0.0035 \cot \alpha + 0.028$
Eldrup and Andersen (2019)	Two-layer armored, 1:1.5 and 1:2 slope, non-overtopped	Rock	Irregular waves, shallow waters	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} = \begin{cases} 4.5 \left(\frac{S_{BA}}{\sqrt{N}}\right)^{0.2} & 1.6 \xi_{m-1,0}^{(0.4 P - 0.67)} \quad (\text{plunging waves } \xi_{m-1,0} < \xi_{cr}) \\ 3.1 \left(\frac{S_{BA}}{\sqrt{N}}\right)^{0.2} & p^{0.17} \min[\cot \alpha, 2]^{0.23} \quad (\text{surging waves } \xi_{m-1,0} \geq \xi_{cr}) \end{cases} \quad (3.17)$

Table 3.1 Summary of existing formulas for the design of the armor units of rubble-mound breakwaters. The symbols are defined in the section List of symbols and acronyms (follows).

Reference	Structure	Armor unit	Wave condition	Formula
Etemad-Shahidi et al. (2020)	Two-layer armored, non-overtopped	Rock	Irregular waves, deep and shallow waters, breaking and no-breaking conditions	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} = \begin{cases} 4.5 \cdot C_p N^{-1/10} S_{BA}^{1/6} \xi_{m-1,0}^{-7/12} (1 - 3m) & (\text{plunging waves } \xi_{m-1,0} < 1.8) \\ 3.9 \cdot C_p N^{-1/10} S_{BA}^{1/6} \xi_{m-1,0}^{-1/3} (1 - 3m) & (\text{surging waves } \xi_{m-1,0} \geq 1.8) \end{cases}$ <p style="text-align: center;">with CV = 11%</p> <p style="text-align: center;">where $C_p = [1 + (D_{n50core}/D_{n50})^{3/10}]^{3/5}$</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(3.18)</p>
van der Meer (1988b)	Two-layer armored, 1:1.5 slope, non-overtopped	Cube	Irregular waves, deep waters	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_n} = \left(6.7 \frac{N_{od}^{0.4}}{N^{0.3}} + 1 \right) s_m^{-0.1} \quad \text{for } 3 < \xi_m < 6 \text{ and } P = 0.4$ <p style="text-align: center;">with CV = 10%</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(3.19)</p>
van Gent et al. (1999, 2002)	One-layer, slope 1:1.5	Cube	Irregular waves, deep waters	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_n} = \begin{cases} 2.0 \div 3.0 & \text{start of damage } (N_{od} = 0) \\ 3.0 \div 3.5 & \text{failure } (N_{od} = 0.2) \end{cases}$ <p style="text-align: right;">(3.20)</p>
van der Meer (1988b)	Two-layer armored, 1:1.5 slope, non-overtopped	Tetrapod	Irregular waves, deep waters, surging waves	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_n} = \left(3.75 \frac{N_{od}^{0.5}}{N^{0.25}} + 0.85 \right) s_m^{-0.2} \quad \text{for } 3.5 < \xi_m < 6 \text{ and } P = 0.4$ <p style="text-align: center;">with CV = 10%</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(3.21)</p>
d'Angremond et al. (1994)	Two-layer armored, 1:1.5 slope, non-overtopped	Tetrapod	Irregular waves, shallow waters	$\frac{H_{2\%}}{\Delta D_n} = 1.4 \left(3.75 \frac{N_{od}^{0.5}}{N^{0.25}} + 0.85 \right) s_m^{-0.2} \quad \text{for } 3.5 < \xi_m < 6 \text{ and } P = 0.4$ <p style="text-align: center;">with CV = 10%</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(3.22)</p>

Table 3.1 Summary of existing formulas for the design of the armor units of rubble-mound breakwaters. The symbols are defined in the section List of symbols and acronyms (follows).

Reference	Structure	Armor unit	Wave condition	Formula
De Jong (1996)	Two-layer armored, 1:1.5 slope, non-overtopped	Tetrapod	Irregular waves, deep waters, plunging waves	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_n} = \left(8.6 \left(\frac{N_{od}}{N^{0.5}} \right)^{0.5} + 3.94 \right) s_m^{0.2}$ <p style="text-align: center;">with CV = 50%</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(3.23)</p>
De Jong (1996)	Two-layer armored, 1:1.5 slope, low-crested	Tetrapod	Irregular waves, deep waters, plunging waves	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_n} = \left(8.6 \left(\frac{N_{od}}{N^{0.5}} \right)^{0.5} + 2.64k_t + 1.25 \right) s_m^{0.2} \left[1 + 0.17 \exp \left(-0.61 \frac{R_c}{D_n} \right) \right]$ <p style="text-align: center;">with CV = 50%</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(3.24)</p>
van der Meer (1988b)	One-layer, slope 1:1.33	Accropode 7	Irregular waves, deep waters, non-breaking waves	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_n} = \begin{cases} 3.7 & (CV = 20\%) \text{ no damage } (N_{od} = 0) \\ 4.1 & (CV = 20\%) \text{ failure } (N_{od} > 0.5) \end{cases}$ <p style="text-align: center;">It is recommended to use a safety coefficient for design of about 1.5 on N_s values.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(3.25)</p>
Burcharth et al. (1998)	One-layer, non-overtopped or marginally overtopped	Accropode 7	Irregular waves, breaking and non-breaking conditions	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_n} = A(N_d^{0.2} + 7.70) \quad \text{for } 3.5 < \xi_m < 4.5$ <p style="text-align: center;">where</p> $A = 0.46 (CV = 0.02 + 0.05(1 - N_d)^6)$ <p style="text-align: right;">(3.26)</p>

Table 3.1 Summary of existing formulas for the design of the armor units of rubble-mound breakwaters. The symbols are defined in the section List of symbols and acronyms (follows).

Reference	Structure	Armor unit	Wave condition	Formula
Burcharth and Liu (1992)	Two-layer armored, 1:1.5 slope, non-overtopped	Dolos	Irregular waves, breaking and non-breaking conditions	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_n} = (47 - 72r)\varphi D^{1/3} N^{-0.1} = (17 - 26r)\varphi^{2/3} N_{od}^{1/3} N^{-0.1}$ <p style="text-align: center;">for</p> $0.32 < r < 0.42 \quad 0.61 < \varphi < 1 \quad 1\% < D < 15\% \quad 2.49 < \xi_0 < 11.7$ <p style="text-align: center;">with CV = 22%</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(3.27)</p>
Holtzhausen (1996)	Two-layer armored, 1:1.5 slope, non-overtopped	Dolos	Irregular waves, breaking and non-breaking conditions	$N_{od} = 6.95 \cdot 10^{-5} \left(\frac{H_s}{\Delta^{0.74} D_n} \right)^7 \varphi^{1.51}$ <p style="text-align: right;">(3.28)</p>
Brown (1983)	Uniformly placed armor units	Seebes	Irregular waves	$\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_n} = (1 - n_p) C_B \cot \alpha^{\frac{1}{3}}$ <p style="text-align: right;">(3.29)</p>

3.2.1.1 Rock-armored breakwaters

Typically, design stability formulas are derived by assuming the incipient instability of an armor unit subjected to certain wave forces. Early relations describing seaside armor rock incipient motion were formulated by Iribarren (1938), Hudson (1959), Losada and Gimenez-Curto (1979), and others. These relations exhibited similarities but primarily differed in the parametric description of the structure slope and internal friction angles.

In particular, the well-known Hudson formula has been the most widely used formula for many decades. The equation in stability number form is given in Equation (3.8). The stability coefficient K_D varies primarily with the structure type, location on the structure, wave breaking, shape of the armor units, roughness of the armor unit surface, sharpness of edges, and degree of interlocking obtained in placement (see CERC, 1984). The original Hudson equation was developed for monochromatic waves and was validated using the average of the highest three waves in a short monochromatic burst. In the SPM (CERC, 1984), $H_{1/10}$ was introduced for design purposes, but K_D was still quantified for the lower envelope of stability. The Hudson damage assessment was based on the eroded area on an average section and considered a “no damage” condition, allowing for the removal of as much as 1% of the total number of armor units in the cover layer or 0-5% of volume.

Substantial progress in breakwater hydraulic stability research was achieved by Thompson and Shuttler (1975). The authors introduced irregular waves and recognized the significance of factors such as the type of breaking, stone placement, and storm duration. Later, Broderick and Ahrens (1982) introduced the new damage parameter S , defined by Equation (3.4). The results obtained by Thompson and Shuttler (1975) were reanalyzed by van der Meer (1988) and, more recently by van der Meer (2021).

Van der Meer conducted a large laboratory experimental campaign, including both small- and large-scale tests, quantifying the influence of various parameters (e.g., wave period, damage level, permeability, number of waves (duration), wave steepness, type of armor layer) on the hydraulic stability of rock armor units. The author derived two different formulas, one for plunging waves and one for surging waves, which are widely employed in design practice and research but are mainly limited to deep (nonbreaking) water conditions. Such formulas correspond to Equation (3.10) of Table 3.1. The van der Meer dataset was entirely limited to flat bathymetry and relatively deep waters. Therefore, these formulations are not applicable in shallow waters and heavy wave-breaking conditions. A correction was proposed by van der Meer, to extend the formulae to depth-limited water conditions with limited wave breaking if the ratio between the significant wave height at the toe of the structure and the deep-water one is lower than 0.7.

Smith et al. (2002) conducted several laboratory small-scale tests to gain insight into shallow water conditions. The work by Smith et al. (2002) was later extended by similar experiments of van Gent et al. (2003), who introduced new stability data acquired in shallow water conditions, aiming to re-calibrate the van der Meer formulae. Similar equations for plunging and surging waves were derived, which are Equation (3.14).

In van Gent (2004), the alternative stability formula expressed by Equation (3.15) of Table 3.1 was reported, not depending on the spectral wave period ($T_{m-1,0}$) or the notional permeability

factor (P), but simply including both the armor stone (D_{n50}) and core nominal ($D_{n50core}$) sizes, respectively.

Melby and Hughes (2004) and later Melby and Kobayashi (2011), developed a stability formula based on the maximum wave momentum flux and concluded that incorporating water depth leads to a better description of stability for both plunging waves, which are reported in Table 3.I as Equation (3.16). The parameter N_m is the stability number that depends on water depth and the nonlinear maximum wave momentum flux M_{fmax} computed at the toe of the structure.

In Eldrup and Andersen (2019), the hydraulic stability of a conventional rubble mound breakwater in shallow waters was investigated, with a focus on the effects of nonlinear and very low steepness waves characterized by a high and narrow crest and a wide wave trough. The authors revisited the van der Meer stability design formulae and proposed the new formulation reported in Table 3.I as Equation (3.17), based on the newly acquired data and the dataset provided by van Gent et al. (2003).

More recently, alternative approaches utilizing artificial intelligence computing techniques, such as artificial neural networks (ANN) (Lee et al., 2016), genetic programming (Koç et al., 2016; Lee and Suh, 2020), and machine learning models (Wei et al., 2019), have gained attention. For instance, in Etemad-Shahidi et al. (2020), a multi-variable regression model was employed on an experimental dataset consisting of 791 points from the literature. The aim was to develop a compact and concise formula valid from deep to shallow water conditions for both plunging and surging waves, which is Equation (3.18) of Table 3.I. These formulas consider the effect of the foreshore slope m .

3.2.1.2 Artificial block-armored breakwaters

In the context of breakwaters protected by concrete armor units, hydraulic stability refers to the ability to withstand wave impact without excessive movement or failure, while structural stability pertains to maintaining the geometric integrity of each unit. Designers must ensure that concrete armor units can withstand significant fractures and breakages caused by wave loadings and movement due to imperfect hydraulic stability. This is a significant aspect to be considered when concrete armor units are used compared to rock units, due to the different tensile strengths of the materials.

Presently, in prevalent single armor layer systems, design decisions for concrete armor units typically rely on empirical generalized design formulas. Subsequently, hydraulic performance is verified through small- or large-scale model tests tailored to the specific site geometry and concrete armor unit types under consideration. The final dimension requirements (i.e., tonnage) of the armor units are determined based on the hydraulic stability study, available size categories, and a conservative approach to setting confidence limits for design values.

Design formulas for concrete armor units typically derive from the same governing variables as those for rock stability but differ in their specific design formulas and coefficients. Damage assessment for concrete armor units primarily relies on the number of units displaced from cover layers due to wave action. Damage, quantified as the relative damage N_{od} , correlates with the actual number of units displaced relative to a nominal diameter D_n along the longitudinal axis of the structure, according to Equation (3.3). The percentage of damage to a structure can be calculated by relating N_{od} to the number of units in the cross-section with a length of $1D_n$.

General design formulas for concrete armor units incorporate parameters such as N_{od} , the number of waves N , and the offshore wave steepness $s_{0,m}$. However, most concrete armor units design formulas do not provide stability numbers in manuals; instead, the Hudson equation described again in Equation (3.8) of Table 3.I is preferred, with K_D values estimated through small-scale model tests (see Table 3.II). Thus, for preliminary sizing, the simple approach is to use Hudson's equation with specific K_D values derived from previous or generic model tests. Alternatively, empirical formulas may be used for selected armor unit types. Physical model tests are recommended for all complex concrete armor units due to stability variations under multiple influences. Such tests are more complex than those for conventional rock armor layers and require expertise in physical modeling.

Various stability formulas have been developed for types of armor units. Subsequent sections discuss and analyze design formulas for popular concrete armor unit types such as Cubic blocks, Tetrapods, Dolosse, Antifer Cubes, Accropodes, Core-locs, Xblocs, Cubipods, and Hollow units. As interlocking plays a crucial role in their stability, and steeper slopes are preferred for cost-effectiveness, slope angles generally should not exceed 1V:2H. Engineering manuals like the Coastal Engineering Manual (USACE, 2002) and The Rock Manual (CIRIA et al., 2007), as well as specific unit manuals, should be consulted for the use of these units.

Table 3.II Comparison of hydraulic stability for commonly applied armor units in breaking wave conditions. (K_D =stability coefficient, N_s = stability number).

Armor unit	Layers	K_D		N_s		References
		Trunk	Head	Trunk	Head	
Cube	1	6	5	2	2.2	van der Meer (1988b), CERC (1984), Cubipod manual (2016)
Cube	2	6.5	4.5	2	2.2	van Gent et al. (1999), Cubipod manual (2016)
Tetrapod	2	7	4.5	2.2	1.95	van der Meer (1988b), CERC (1984)
Antifer Cube	2	7	5	2	2.2	van der Meer (1988b, 1999)
Dolos	2	16	-	2.7	-	Burcharth and Liu (1993), Holtzhausen (1996)
Accropode	1	12	9.5	2.5	2.3	Sogreah (2000)
Core-loc	1	16	13	2.8	2.6	Melby and Turk (1997)
Xbloc	1	16	13	2.8	2.6	DMC (2003)
Cubipod	2	28	7	-	-	Cubipod manual (2016)
Cubipod	1	12	5	-	-	Cubipod manual (2016)

Cubes and Parallelepipeds

Initially, breakwaters with Cubes units were constructed in two layers with steep slopes, approximately 1V:1.5H, as determined by van der Meer (1988, 1999). The stability coefficient K_D for these blocks increases with the acceptable damage level N_{od} and marginally decreases with increasing wave steepness, as described by the van der Meer formula reported in Equation (3.19).

Subsequently, van Gent et al. (1999, 2002, 2003) proposed that modified single-layer Cubes might offer advantages over double layer Cubes in terms of interlocking and overall porosity,

rendering the latter outdated. The method of cube placement significantly affects hydraulic performance and structural response; randomly placed cubes generally enhance hydraulic performance by reducing wave overtopping and reflection, while more uniform placement may increase the risk of cubes being lifted by excess pore pressures. Single layer cubes, tested on a 1V:1.5H slope, exhibit larger stability but are susceptible to heavy wave attack on the crest. Design experiences with single layer cubes are limited, but they are considered more stable than conventional structures. However, excessive damage to a single layer of cubes can compromise the underlying rock layer. Safety factors for single layer cubes suggest comparable stability to other armor units.

In summary, single-layer cube design values align closely with those for double-layer cubes, implying a stability number of approximately $N_s=2.2$ for preliminary design. Various parallelepiped units, including cubes with central holes to reduce concrete consumption and mitigate internal stresses during hydration, have also been utilized over time.

Tetrapods

The hydraulic stability of Tetrapod-protected breakwaters and block sizing can be determined using equations developed by van der Meer (1988b, 1999) and De Jong (1996) for double layer systems on 1V:1.5H slopes. In particular, Equation (3.21) and Equation (3.23) of Table 3.I depict stability against surging and plunging waves, respectively. These equations pertain to an almost non-overtopped structure (less than 15% overtopping). Stability increases if the crest height decreases and varies with packing density.

Antifer Cube

The design formulas for sizing and estimating the size and hydraulic stability of Antifer Cubes align with those identified by van der Meer (1988b, 1999) for Cubes.

Accropode

Simple formulas describe Accropode stability, with recommended safety coefficients ensuring design robustness. Recommended slopes range from 4V:3H to 3V:2H, offering versatile solutions for coastal protection. For natural rock appearance, the Ecopode, closely related to the Accropode, was developed. Specifically, hydraulic stability can be described by two simple formulas (van der Meer, 1988b, 1999) in nonbreaking waves, which corresponds to Equation (3.25) of Table 3.I. The storm duration and wave period showed no influence on the stability of Accropode, and the “no damage” and “failure” criteria were very close.

This implies that up to a high wave height, Accropodes are completely stable. However, after the initiation of damage at this high wave height, the structure will progressively fail. Therefore, it is recommended to use a safety coefficient for design of about 1.5 on N_s values.

Sogreah (2000) recommends K_D values of 12/15 for breaking/nonbreaking waves, respectively, through engineering practice often employs lower values. $K_D = 15$ for the trunk and 12 for the head. Despite its merits, the Accropode was further refined into Accropode II in 1999, featuring improved hydraulic and structural stability with easier placement, facilitated by special surface roughening.

Dolos

Dolos represented a significant advancement in interlocking capability, enhancing the hydraulic stability of armor layers, especially when randomly placed in double layers with a specified

packing density (Palmer, 1998). The geometric shape of Dolos can vary based on block size, with the waist ratio influencing slenderness. Typically, the waist ratio is around $r=0.32$, but higher ratios are recommended for larger units ($r =0.34$ for 20-ton units and $r =0.36$ for 30-ton units). For larger units exceeding 20 tons, the waist ratio can be estimated using the following formula, where M is the weight of the block in tons:

$$r = 0.34 \left(\frac{M}{20} \right)^{\frac{1}{6}} \quad (3.30)$$

Several design formulas have been proposed for Dolos stability on non-overtopped breakwaters, considering parameters such as waist ratio and packing density. The stability number decreases linearly with increasing waist ratio and recommended slopes range from 1V:2H to 1V:3H. Burcharth and Liu (1993) presented Equation (3.27) of Table 3.I as the stability formula for Dolos on a 1V:1.5H non-overtopping slope with $0.32 < r < 0.42$ and $0.61 < \varphi < 1$. Holtzhausen (1996) presented another equation for Dolos units valid for packing density coefficients in the range of $0.83 < \varphi < 1.15$, which is presented as Equation (3.28) in Table 3.I. Equations implies that as the packing density is decreased, the number of displaced units (damage) is decreased, suggesting that armor layers with lower packing densities are more stable. This characteristic can be explained physically by the fact that high packing densities do not allow for optimum interlocking.

In summary, while Dolos offers hydraulic stability through interlocking, its structural fragility and brittle failure have rendered it outdated. Alternative solutions such as Core-loc have been developed to address these shortcomings. Regular monitoring and replacement of damaged units are recommended for existing Dolos-based structures. When designing Dolos armor layers with the Hudson equation, K_D is 15 for the trunk and 8 for the head.

Core-Loc

Similar to Accropode but with superior hydraulic stability, Core-loc boasts a recommended K_D value of 16, slightly higher than Accropode. Comparative tests show Core-Loc exhibits less movement post-settlement than Accropode. For a 4V:3H slope, the stability number of the Core-Loc design is $N_s = 2.78$, offering a 27% weight saving compared to Accropode (van der Meer 1999). Core-loc offers advantages in repair flexibility and streamlined placement, albeit potentially less structural stability due to its slenderness. Recommended slopes for Core-locs are 4V:3H to 1V:1.5H, with K_D values of 13 for the head and 16 for the trunk in double layer, randomly placed configurations.

Xbloc

With K_D values of 13 for the head and 16 for the trunk, Xbloc employs the Hudson formula for design, with single layer, randomly placed configurations. Unlike other single layer units, Xbloc placement follows a predefined grid, allowing random orientation of individual blocks. Recommended slopes range from 4V:3H to 1V:1.5H. Further details are available in the documentation of DMC (2003).

Cubipod

Hydraulic stability studies, conducted during the CUBIPOD research project⁹, involved renowned researchers and laboratories. 2D physical tests on scaled models, focusing on non-overtopping structures with 3V:2H slopes under nonbreaking conditions, yielded promising results. Cubipod units demonstrated higher stability coefficients (K_D) compared to Cubes for both trunk and roundhead sections. This increased stability allows for significant volume reduction in armor layers, presenting undeniable advantages over Cubes. The hydraulic stability of the Cubipod with K_D values of 5 for the roundhead and 12 for the trunk (including a safety margin), is assessed using the Hudson formula for single layer random placement applications. Further insights are given in the Cubipod Manual (2016) and related publications.

Hollow blocks

Different design schemes are necessary for these units due to their unique characteristics. Few stability design formulas exist, with sizing typically relying on-site experience and physical model tests. For example, Cob and Shed units have an onset of movement at $N_s = 4.8$ for two-layer random placement (Allsop and Herbert, 1991; Allsop and Jones, 1996).

Seabees are sized using a method derived by Brown (1988), ensuring substantial independence of unit mass and wave height as described by Equation (3.29) of Table 3.I, where n_v is the armor layer porosity and C_B is the stability coefficient (equivalent to K_D). The value of C_B varies with the position on the slope relative to the waterline. For design purposes, a value of C_B is determined for the storm armor zone and then armor unit sizes on the rest of the breakwater may be reduced progressively (to about 60% of the storm armor zone value) if desired. A typical value of $C_B = 5$ is generally considered.

The Haro, tested for single and double layers with pattern placement using a slope of 1V:1.5H and 1V:2H, exhibit stability against the Hudson formula, with recommended C_B values of 12 (N_s equal to 2.2 and 3.7 for no damage and severe damage conditions, respectively) for double layer placement on trunks (Van Damme et al. 1993, De Rouck et al. 1996).

The Samoa block, a variation of the Hollow block concept, features a cylindrical, non-hollow shape with lower porosity (Turk and Melby, 2002). Positioned uniformly, they require a high degree of interlocking due to reduced friction, making them suitable for dry revetments and slopes with complex geometry.

3.2.2 Excessive mean wave overtopping discharge

Concerning the wave overtopping phenomenon, it is usually described by the mean overtopping discharge (q). Table 3.III summarizes the most relevant state-of-art equations for the evaluation of the mean wave overtopping discharge, which are empirical formulas calibrated on experimental and/or field data. In particular, most of the reported formulas were calibrated using the database collected in the framework of the EU-project CLASH⁷, which includes data from basic research as well as site specific confidential tests, small scale tests from 2D and 3D models as well as prototype data, and simple geometries as well as very complex situations (Steendam et al., 2005). The indications EurOtop Manual (2018), which represents the current state of the art on wave overtopping of coastal structure, were also derived from the analysis of the CLASH database, extended with other experimental and field data, for a total of more than

⁹ <https://www.cubipod.com/en/>

13,000 tests on wave overtopping. It is worth to mention that in parallel with the EurOtop Manual (2018), an Artificial Neural Network (i.e. the EurOtop ANN¹⁰) is available for the prediction of mean overtopping discharge for all kind of structure geometries, given by a number of hydraulic and geometrical parameters as input.

Figure 3.3 shows the geometrical characteristics of the structure which influence the overtopping phenomenon of rubble-mound breakwaters, namely the structure crest height with respect to MWL (R_c), the armor crest freeboard without crown wall (A_c), the crest width (G_c), and the structure slope angle (α). It should be noted that the formulas presented in Table 3.III do not consider the effect of the toe berm, which in the case of coastal dikes is usually included through an empirical coefficient calculated as a function of the structure geometry (EurOtop Manual, 2018). Besides the above-mentioned geometrical characteristics, the wave motion descriptors are also included in the design formulas, namely the significant wave height at the toe of the structure (H_s), which is present in all the considered formulations, and the peak wave period (T_p) or the spectral wave period ($T_{m-1,0}$).

Moreover, empirical coefficients to take into account the surface roughness of the armor layer and the direction of wave attack are employed, namely γ_f and γ_β . Table 3.IV reports the values of γ_f suggested by the EurOtop Manual (2018). Recently, the experimental study proposed by Pepi et al. (2022) provided values of γ_f for upgraded rubble-mound breakwaters with additional armor layers, whose behavior differs from conventional structures. Concerning γ_β , which is equal to one for orthogonal wave attack, different formulations have been defined for its calculation (Etemad-Shahidi et al., 2022). A recent study presented by van Gent (2023), which was based on 3D physical model tests on dikes, rubble mound breakwaters and vertical caisson breakwaters, proposed a new expression for the oblique wave factor. In Table 3.III, the mathematical expressions to calculate γ_β employed by the authors of each mean wave overtopping formulas are indicated.

Finally, only in Equation (3.42) of Table 3.III, the mean of the 2% of the maximum values of wave run-up is included, which is expressed as follows (EurOtop Manual, 2018):

$$\frac{R_{2\%}}{H_s} = 1.65 \cdot \gamma_b \cdot \gamma_f \cdot \gamma_\beta \cdot \xi_{m-1,0} \quad (3.31)$$

with a maximum of

$$\frac{R_{2\%}}{H_s} = 1.00 \cdot \gamma_{fsurg} \cdot \gamma_\beta \cdot \left(4 - \frac{1.5}{\sqrt{\gamma_b \cdot \xi_{m-1,0}}} \right) \quad (3.32)$$

where from $\xi_{m-1,0}$ (i.e. the Iribarren number calculated as a function of the spectral wave period) equal to 1.8 the roughness factor γ_{fsurg} increases linearly up to 1 for $\xi_{m-1,0}=10$:

$$\gamma_{fsurg} = \gamma_f + (\xi_{m-1,0} - 1.8) \cdot (1 - \gamma_f) / 8.2 \quad (3.33)$$

¹⁰ <http://overtopping.ing.unibo.it/overtopping>

with a maximum $R_{u2\%}/H_s=3.0$ for structures with an impermeable core and 2.0 for a permeable core. The term γ_b , which takes into account the effects of the toe berm on wave run-up, is evaluated as follows (EurOtop Manual, 2018):

$$\gamma_b = 1 - r_b(1 - r_{ab}) \quad \text{for } 0.6 \leq \gamma_b \leq 1.0 \quad (3.34)$$

where

$$r_b = \frac{B}{L_{berm}} \quad (3.35)$$

$$r_{ab} = \begin{cases} 0.5 - 0.5 \cos\left(\pi \frac{d_b}{R_{2\%}}\right) & \text{for a berm above still water line} \\ 0.5 - 0.5 \cos\left(\pi \frac{d_b}{2H_s}\right) & \text{for a berm below still water line} \\ 1 & \text{for berms lying outside the area of influence} \end{cases} \quad (3.36)$$

where the geometrical parameters B , L_{berm} , and d_b are indicated in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5 Definition of horizontal berm B and characteristic berm length L_{Berm} (EurOtop Manual, 2018).

Table 3.III Summary of existing formulas for the estimation of mean wave overtopping discharge of rubble-mound breakwaters. The symbols are defined in the section List of symbols and acronyms (continues).

Reference	Armor units	Formula
Smolka et al. (2009)	Cube, Cubipod	$\frac{q}{\sqrt{gH_s^3}} = 0.2 \cdot \exp\left(0.53\xi_p - 3.27\frac{A_c}{R_c} - 2.16\frac{R_c}{H_s} \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma_f}\right) \quad \text{for } 2.7 < \xi_p < 7, \quad \cot\alpha = 1.5, \quad 1.30 < \frac{R_c}{H_s} < 2.80$ $\gamma_f = \begin{cases} 0.50 & \text{for Cubes} - 2 \text{ layers } (0.70 < A_c/R_c < 1.00) \\ 0.46 & \text{for Cubipods} - 1 \text{ layer } (0.40 < A_c/R_c < 0.65) \\ 0.44 & \text{for Cubipods} - 2 \text{ layers } (0.58 < A_c/R_c < 0.80) \end{cases}$ <p>where</p>
Jafari and Etemad-Shahidi (2012) and Etemad-Shahidi and Jafari (2014)	Various – CLASH database	$\frac{q}{\sqrt{gH_s^3}} = \begin{cases} \exp\left(-0.6396\frac{R_c}{\gamma_f\gamma_\beta H_s} \frac{\sqrt{s_p}}{\tan\alpha} - 0.7085 \tan\alpha - 11.4897\right) & \text{if } \frac{R_c}{H_s} > 2.08 \text{ and } \frac{G_c}{H_s} > 1.51 \\ \exp\left(-6.18\frac{R_c}{\gamma_f\gamma_\beta H_s} \frac{\sqrt{s_p}}{\tan\alpha} - 3.21\right) & \text{if } \frac{R_c}{\gamma_f\gamma_\beta H_s} \frac{\sqrt{s_p}}{\tan\alpha} \leq 0.86 \\ \exp\left(-3.1\frac{R_c}{\gamma_f\gamma_\beta H_s} \frac{\sqrt{s_p}}{\tan\alpha} - 6.05 \tan\alpha - 2.63\right) & \text{if } \frac{R_c}{\gamma_f\gamma_\beta H_s} \frac{\sqrt{s_p}}{\tan\alpha} > 0.86 \end{cases}$ <p>for $1.31 < \xi_p < 9.27$, $0.50 < \frac{R_c}{H_s} < 2.59$, $0.00 < \frac{G_c}{H_s} < 3.88$</p> $\gamma_\beta = \begin{cases} 1 - 0.0063 \beta & \text{for } 0^\circ \leq \beta \leq 80^\circ \\ 1 - 0.063 \cdot 80 & \text{for } \beta \geq 80^\circ \end{cases}$

Table 3.III Summary of existing formulas for the estimation of mean wave overtopping discharge of rubble-mound breakwaters. The symbols are defined in the section List of symbols and acronyms (follows).

Reference	Armor units	Formula
Molines and Medina (2016)	Various – CLASH database (conventional breakwaters)	$\frac{q}{\sqrt{gH_s^3}} = \exp\left(\lambda_2\lambda_3\lambda_4\lambda_5\lambda_6\left[a_1 + b_1 \cdot \frac{R_c}{H_s} \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma_f\gamma_\beta}\right]\right)$ <p>for $1.65 < \xi_{m-1,0} < 7.21$, $0.52 < \frac{R_c}{H_s} < 3.75$, $0.00 < \frac{G_c}{H_s} < 3.50$, $0.09 < \frac{R_c}{h} < 1.34$, $0.38 < \frac{A_c}{H_s} < 1.38$, $0.00 < \frac{B}{H_s} < 15.9$, $1.45 < \frac{h_t}{H_s} < 17.50$</p> <p>where</p> $\lambda_2 = a_2 + b_2 \cdot (\xi_{m-1,0}\sqrt{R_c/H_s}) \quad \lambda_3 = a_3 + b_3 \cdot \exp(c_3 R_c/H_s) \quad \lambda_4 = \max[c_4; a_4 + b_4 \cdot G_c/H_s]$ $\lambda_5 = a_5 + b_5 \cdot A_c/R_c \quad \lambda_6 = \begin{cases} \max[c_6; a_6 + b_6 \cdot R_c/h] \\ a_6 \text{ if } B_t = 0 \end{cases}$ $\gamma_\beta = \begin{cases} 1 - 0.0077 \beta \\ 1 - 0.0058 \beta \end{cases}$ <p>(3.39)</p>
EurOtop (2018)	Various – extended CLASH database	$\frac{q}{\sqrt{gH_s^3}} = a_E \cdot \exp\left[-\left(\frac{R_c}{H_s}\right)^{1.3} \gamma_f \gamma_\beta\right]$ <p>for $2 < \cot \alpha < 4/3$, $0.00 < \frac{R_c}{H_s} < 3.50$, $\xi_p \geq 2$</p> <p>where</p> $a_E = 0.09 \ (\sigma = 0.0135) \quad \text{and} \quad b_E = 1.5 \ (\sigma = 0.15)$ $\gamma_\beta = \begin{cases} 1 - 0.0063 \beta \text{ for } 0^\circ \leq \beta \leq 80^\circ \\ 1 - 0.063 \cdot 80 \text{ for } \beta \geq 80^\circ \end{cases}$ <p>(3.40)</p>

Table 3.III Summary of existing formulas for the estimation of mean wave overtopping discharge of rubble-mound breakwaters. The symbols are defined in the section List of symbols and acronyms (follows).

Reference	Armor units	Formula
Vieira et al. (2021)	Cube (single layer)	$\frac{q}{\sqrt{gH_s^3}} = 0.20 \cdot \exp\left(-6.45 \frac{R_c}{H_s \gamma_f^3} \sqrt{2\pi/gT_{m-1.0}^2 G_c}\right)$ <p>for $\cot \alpha = 1.5$, $1.4 < \frac{R_c}{H_s} < 3.7$, $2.8 \leq \xi_{m-1.0} \leq 4.4$, $s_p = 0.02$ and 0.05, $3.1 \leq \frac{h}{H_s} \leq 6.6$</p> <p>where</p> <p>$\gamma_f = 0.52$</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(3.41)</p>
Etemad-Shahidi et al. (2022)	Various – data from Thompson and Shuttler (1975), van der Meer (1988a, c), van Gent et al. (2004), Vidal et al. (2006)	$\frac{q}{\sqrt{gH_s^3}} = a_{ES} \cdot \exp\left[b_{ES} \left(\frac{R_{2\%} - R_c}{H_s}\right) - c_{ES} \frac{G_c}{H_s}\right]$ <p>for $0.25 < \tan \alpha < 0.80$, $0.43 < \frac{R_c}{H_s} < 2.70$, $1.27 < \xi_{m-1.0} \geq 11.74$</p> <p>where</p> <p>$a_{ES} = 1.22 \cdot 10^{-4}$ ($\sigma = 1.30 \cdot 10^{-5}$), $b_{ES} = 3.50$ ($\sigma = 0.13$), $c_{ES} = 0.64$ ($\sigma = 0.07$)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(3.42)</p>

Table 3.IV Roughness factor for different types of armor layer (EurOtop Manual, 2018).

Type of armor layer	γ_f
Smooth impermeable surface	1.00
Rocks (1 layer, impermeable core)	0.60
Rocks (1 layer, permeable core)	0.45
Rocks (2 layers, impermeable core)	0.55
Rocks (2 layers, permeable core)	0.40
Cubes (1 layer, flat positioning)	0.49
Cubes (2 layers, random positioning)	0.47
Antifers	0.50
HARO's	0.47
Tetrapods	0.38
Dolosse	0.43
Accropode I	0.46
Xbloc; CORE-LOC; Accropode II	0.44
Cubipods (1 layer)	0.49
CUBipods (2 layers)	0.47

3.3 Design formulas for vertical breakwaters

Vertical breakwaters, also known as vertical wall or vertical facing (see Figure 3.6), consist of a concrete or reinforced concrete rectangular-section structure, resting on the seabed, in the rare case in which the geotechnical characteristics of the ground allow this, or usually on a more or less thick embankment of loose material. The "stem" normally emerges from the sea level to a height of about one meter. The structure is generally completed with the realization of a concrete superstructure, from which a vertical wall may be raised, of a height adequate to protect the quay behind, positioned in many cases just behind this vertical wall.

Vertical breakwaters, unlike rubble-mound, which operate to cause wave breaking, are designed to reflect the wave motion that strikes them. Indeed, such structures are recommended and normally employed in the presence of deep seabed (generally above a depth of 10-15 m), which makes the construction of rubble-mound breakwaters not economically advantageous; with adequate depths, it is often possible to exclude wave breaking in front of the wall, thus ensuring the wall's fully reflecting behavior in all sea states, resulting in the formation of a standing waves known as a *clapotis*.

Figure 3.6 Sketch of a vertical breakwater.

However, intermediate conditions may occur when the foundation deck on which the caisson rests reach substantial thicknesses, such as to reduce the depth of the seabed in front of the vertical wall of the structure. Under such conditions, the structure therefore assumes different characteristics, and in relation to these, it is possible to classify the vertical breakwaters according to the following three different types (see Figure 3.7):

- a) Upright type - vertical concrete block or caisson breakwater (also cellular) placed directly on the seabed or on a thin foundation layer;
- b) Vertical Composite Breakwater - vertical caisson-type breakwater placed on a thick foundation layer. It is defined as low-mound when the height of the embankment is contained within 30% of the depth of the sea, or high-mound when the composite breakwater based on a reef that reaches a height above the low tide level;
- c) Horizontal Composite Breakwater – a caisson breakwater placed on a thin foundation layer, that is protected on the seaward side by a reef leaning against the vertical face of the structure.

Figure 3.7 Characteristic types of vertical-wall breakwaters.

Breakwaters belonging to the Upright and Vertical Composite Breakwater categories characterized by a shallow breakwater (low-mound) do not cause the wave motion on the breakwater that occurs for high-mound breakwaters, with the generation of an impulsive pressure stress on the structure, induced by the breaking wave motion. In the case where the embankment is placed at an intermediate depth between the low-mound and high-mound levels, the wave motion may occasionally generate an impulsive pressure regime, induced by the breaking wave.

The type c) horizontal composite breakwater is normally used when there is a need to reduce the wave reflection phenomenon (e.g. to contain the propagation of residual waves within the port area, characterized by high wave amplitude, with the consequent reduction in the conditions of safe operation of the infrastructure). At the same time, the protective reef leaning against the caisson, while inducing wave breaking, dissipates the energy content of the waves, significantly reducing the loads induced by them on the vertical wall.

Figure 3.8 shows different types of composite breakwaters, characterized by different construction types of the elevating structures.

Figure 3.8 Construction types of composite breakwaters: (a) monolith concrete block; (b) block masonry; (c) cellular concrete block; (d) upright caisson; (e) sloping top caisson; (f) perforated wall caisson.

Originally, the vertical breakwaters consisted of a single monolithic concrete block (Figure 3.8a) placed on a foundation reef. The vertical wall may alternatively be realized by superimposing cyclopean concrete blocks (Figure 3.8b), possibly solidified by clamping techniques or other jointing methods. A single cellular concrete block (Figure 3.8c) may be used to form the vertical wall; placed in situ, it is then filled with loose stone material and sealed with the crowning concrete superstructure. The construction technique that has now established itself, thanks to the numerous advantages connected to it (high ease of construction, handling and laying, and economic and environmental advantages of various kinds) is constituted by the monolithic cellular reinforced concrete caisson (Figure 3.8d), prefabricated in a specialized yard, towed by tugboats, laid by sinking on the embankment, filling it with seawater, and then filled with sand from dragging and/or concrete. The cellular caisson breakwaters were subsequently improved by using sloping superstructures or perforated walls to reduce wave reflection (Figure 3.8e-f).

Even in the case of vertical breakwaters, as is the case for rubble-mound breakwater, the design of each individual part of the structure (embankment liner, cellular caisson, tailrace wall, etc.) is a complex task, due to the stochastic nature of the external loads and the response of the structure itself to these forces. Even more complicated, the design of upgrades on existing structures appears to be, given the high degree of uncertainty that characterizes the knowledge framework on the conditions affecting the structure during its operational life. For this reason, the existing dimensioning formulas, even for this type of breakwater, refer exclusively to the construction of new works and not to interventions on existing structures.

Despite the content of Section 3.2, concerning the design of breakwaters, based essentially in the determination of the weight of the rocks that makes up the reinforcement of the breakwater's external covering, correlating the size of the rock with the height of the design wave, through the use of empirical formulas that assess the stability of the individual element subjected to the action of wave motion, in the case of vertical breakwater, the design of the structure is carried out in two distinct phases. The first phase consists in determining the loads acting on the structure by the waves; this phase is conducted by using the empirical formulas found in the literature for determining the pressure distribution acting on the vertical wall by stationary wave motion, even breaking or not; this pressure distribution depends on the characteristics of the wave motion attacking the structure; once the pressure distribution is known, the stress pattern acting on the structure is determined. The forces acting on the structure of the vertical breakwater strictly depend on the kinematic characteristics of the wave motion in front of the structure, the topographic and geotechnical characteristics of the seabed,

and the dynamic characteristics of the structure itself. Figure 3.9 shows the diagram of the forces generated by the wave motion that is normally used in the dimensioning of vertical breakwaters.

The second phase consists in determining the weight in water of the caisson capable of resisting the previously determined loads. Indeed, the stability of vertical structures under wave attack depends essentially from their intrinsic weight which depends essentially on the width of its section, being the height imposed by the bathymetric conditions of the site.

Figure 3.9 Diagram of the forces generated by wave motion.

The probabilistic approach to the design of vertical breakwater also requires the use of empirical formulae describing the force distribution on the structure, which can be rewritten in the form of reliability functions (failure functions), referring to fixed acceptance limits for each failure mechanism.

In the case of vertical breakwaters, the failure mechanisms may be different and of various nature and cause. It is possible to classify them according to different criteria. For example, in relation to their origin it is possible to distinguish:

- failure due to design defect, related to the use of calculation schemes that are not appropriate to the objective situation;
- failure due to poor knowledge of environmental parameters characteristic of the design (e.g. incorrect evaluation of geotechnical parameters, or lack or poor quality of wave motion data);
- failure due to inadequate choice of construction system;
- failure due to poor quality of construction materials;
- failure due to deterioration of the structure resulting from poor maintenance.

Failure mechanisms can also be classified according to two distinct macro-categories: global (overall) or localized failure (see Figure 3.10).

The first category includes the following cases:

- 1) stability of the wall to shoreward sliding: the resultant of the horizontal forces acting on the seaward side exceeds the friction force acting between the base of the caisson and the foundation layer;
- 2) overturning and consequent overloading of the foundation material: the rotation of the caisson occurs when the moment induced by the action of the wave motion exceeds the stabilizing moment due to the structure's own weight; this failure mechanism occurs

when there is no rupture of the foundation soil, due to the high mechanical characteristics of the seabed or the base reef.

- 3) settling or sinking: the subsidence of the structure occurs when consolidation of the foundation soil occurs;
- 4) foundation soil slip: the base slab of the caisson transfers loads to the foundation soil that exceed its breaking strength, thus creating a slip surface. The strength of the soil is influenced by the increase in interstitial pressure in the soil matrix, due to pressure changes in the soil related to cyclic wave motion. The failure of the foundation soil along the slip surface causes rotation and failure of the caisson.
- 5) rift slip rupture: the caisson base slab transfers loads to the foundation reef that exceed its breaking strength, thus creating a rupture surface that can also affect the foundation soil;

The second category of local breakages includes the following cases:

- 1) Sea-side cliff erosion: induced by wave motion can cause sea-side rotation of the caisson and sea-side caisson failure; the most critical wave motion stress occurs in wave hollow conditions in front of the caisson wall;
- 2) Excavation of the seabed: induced by wave motion can cause sea-side rotation of the caisson and failure of the sea-side caisson; the most critical wave motion stress occurs in the condition of a wave line in front of the caisson wall;
- 3) Ejection of base reef material: the wave-induced oscillatory movement of the caisson causes an alternating flow of water within the reef voids and into the subsoil;
- 4) Breakage and displacement of the cape boulders in the reef in front of the horizontal composite breakwaters: this results in an increase in wave motion stresses on the front wall of the caisson, causing it to slip. Damage to the breakwater can lead to increased overflow on the structure;
- 5) Breakage of the caisson wall: caused by excessive wave loads (often related to their impulsive nature) on the reinforced concrete structure or by ship impacts;
- 6) Displacement and ejection of structural cyclopean boulders from their seat, with consequent failure of the vertical breakwater.
- 7) Breakage of the breakwater wall or localized parts of the overburden massif, caused by the overtopping of waves onto the structure.

Figure 3.10 Failure mechanisms of vertical breakwaters.

As described above, the failure mechanisms affecting vertical breakwater can often occur jointly through reciprocal interactions that are often very complex. For example, the failure of the foundation soil by erosion at the base of the cliff or vertical structure may trigger a second failure mechanism by rotation (or overturning) and horizontal sliding.

From the examination of damage events of vertical breakwaters, the most frequent failure mechanisms that have occurred are related to the exceeding of the geotechnical resistance parameters of the foundation soil or embankment layer and to horizontal displacement by sliding of the vertical structure. The latter mechanism is generally more critical than that for overturning, especially for breakwaters characterized by relatively low crowning massifs.

In this paper, therefore, a description will be made of the most common formulas for evaluating wave-induced stresses. These formulae are then used for the sizing of the work, which can be carried out according to the most recent probabilistic approach, a summary description of which will be made with regard to those concerning the following failure mechanisms:

- 1) horizontal displacement;
- 2) excessive wave overtopping.

3.3.1 Calculation formulas for wave loads on breakwaters with a flat front wall.

Classification of wave loads

Parameters influencing wave action forces

The main parameters influencing the force of the wave acting on a vertical wall are the period of the wave, the height of the wave, the direction of the wave, the level of the tide, the depth and slope of the seabed, the depth of the water in which the front berm of the foundation reef lies, its width and the slope of its escarpment, the height of the top of the vertical wall and the depth of the water at the base of the vertical wall. The effect of the wall alignment must also be considered. The force of the wave on a vertical wall with a concave alignment may be greater than that on a vertical, straight wall. Furthermore, if the front of the vertical wall is covered with concrete blocks that dissipate the waves, the characteristics of these blocks and the height and width of the crown will influence the wave force.

Types of wave forces

The wave force acting on a vertical wall can be classified according to the type of wave, thus having:

- a) non-breaking wave force;
- b) breaking wave force;
- c) post-breaking wave force.

In the first scenario (non-breaking wave), a standing wave may occur. Assuming a total reflection index and that the wall is frictionless, the amplitude of the wave will increase by a factor of 2. In the second case, the breaking waves can cause an enormous force on the structure. However, this force is limited to a very short period of time on the order of 0.1 seconds. The load is therefore often classified as an impact.

The third scenario is when waves that have already broken, impact the structure and is characterized by great turbulence on the water surface.

Oumeraci et al. (1999) distinguishes breaking waves into two other categories: weakly breaking waves and impacting waves. Figure 3.11 shows the force overtime graph for the four different types of impact waves.

Figure 3.11 Different types of wave loads (Oumeraci et al., 1999).

According to Oumeraci et al. (1999), the impact of already broken waves and the impact of weakly breaking waves do not occur for vertical breakwaters without berms.

The force of a standing wave is produced by waves whose height is small compared to the depth of the water, and the change in wave pressure over time is gradual. When the depth of the structure is greater than about 1.5 times the height of the wave, standing waves can occur (CERC, 1984).

As the height of the wave increases, the strength of the wave also increases. Breaking waves can therefore exert much greater forces due to the dynamic effects of turbulent water and trapped air pockets.

In general, the largest wave force is generated by waves breaking just before reaching the vertical wall. Consequently, with the exception of very shallow water conditions, the force exerted by waves breaking just in front of a vertical wall is larger than the wave force exerted by higher waves that have already broken offshore. It should be noted that especially when breaking waves act on a vertical wall placed on a steep seabed, or on a vertical wall placed on a very high, even slightly sloping beach, a very strong impulsive breaking wave force may occur.

Therefore, wave loads can also be classified according to two distinct types:

1. Pulsating" wave loads which are assumed to be "quasi-static", allowing the application of quasi-static stability formulae and analyses;
2. breaking wave impact loads for which both the magnitude and the variation in time are necessary to perform a dynamic analysis of the structure's response, which must be treated with particular caution.

Wave irregularity and wave force

Sea waves are irregular in height and period. Depending on the depth of the water in which the structures are to be installed and the topography of the seabed, wave forces, such as non-breaking, breaking or already breaking waves, act on the structure. When calculating wave forces, it is important to include the waves that cause the most severe effect on the structure. Sufficient consideration must be given to the irregularity of the wave motion and the characteristics of the wave force depending on the type of structure.

In general, it can be assumed that the greater the wave height, the greater the wave force becomes. It is therefore acceptable to focus on the wave force of the highest wave among a train of random waves attacking the structure. However, with regard to the stability of concrete blocks or reinforcement stones on the slope, and the force of waves acting on floating structures and cylindrical structures with low rigidity, it is preferable to consider the effect of repeated random wave action.

3.3.2 Overview of wave load calculation formulae

Numerous formulae are available in the literature for different types of waves impacting the vertical wall structure. These formulae generally include the magnitude of the maximum pressures and their distributions and forces. In some cases, the uplift pressures are also given. All the formulae are completely empirical or semi-empirical, since the process of wave impact on the structure is not yet fully explained. Table 3.V below lists the most important ones in chronological order; details of the most successful formulae are given below.

Table 3.V Summary of existing formulas for stability of vertical breakwaters (Oumeraci et al., 1999).

Author	Year	Pres-sures	Forces	Uplift	Comments
Quasi-Static Waves					
Sainflou	1928	yes	yes, but difficult	no	vertical wall, no berm
Miche-Rundgren	1944 1958	yes	yes	no	design curves from SPM, 1984
Goda	1985	yes	yes	yes	most-widely used design method
Impact Waves					
Hiroi	1919	yes	yes	no	vertical wall
Bagnold	1939	-	-	-	conceptual model only
Minikin	1963	yes	yes	no	sometimes incorrect dimensions!
Ito	1971	yes	yes	yes	
Blackmore & Hewson	1984	yes	yes	no	
Partenscky	1988	yes	not given	no	air content of wave needed
Kirkgöz	1990 1995	yes	yes	no	vertical wall only
Takahashi	1994	yes	yes	yes	extension of Goda model
Allsop et al.	1996	no	yes	yes	
Walkden et al.	1996	no	yes	no	relation of forces and rise time
Oumeraci & Kortenhaus	1997	yes	yes	yes	time-dependent approach!
McConnell	1998	no	yes	no	amendment of O&K, 1997
Hull & Müller	1998	yes	yes	no	amendment of O&K, 1997
Vicinanza	1998	yes	yes	no	amendment of O&K, 1997
Broken Waves					
SPM	1984	yes	yes	no	vertical walls only
Camfield	1991	yes	yes	no	amendment of SPM, 1984
Jensen	1984	yes	yes	yes	Crown walls
Bradbury & Allsop	1988	yes	yes	yes	Crown walls
Pedersen	1997	yes	yes	yes	Crown walls
Martín et al.	1997	yes	yes	yes	Crown walls

3.3.3 Calculation formulae for stationary or pulsating (non-bulging) wave loads on vertical walls

The stationary or (pulsating) forces can be traced back to those of a hydrostatic scheme. Stationary and therefore non-breaking wave conditions occur where the depth of the structure is greater than approximately 1.5 times the maximum expected wave height. These forces are also referred to as quasi-static, because they change relatively slowly and vary over the same period as the waves. The quasi-static wave loads transmitted by the waves to the wall can be referred to two distinct phases:

1. Wave motion in the crest phase. The vertical wall causes the wave surface to rise along the wall and the structure is subjected to an increase in hydrostatic pressure.
2. Wave motion in the trough phase. The wave level decreases (wave trough) leaving a negative force on the vertical wall. There are few methods for predicting wave loads in the trough phase.

Linear theory of small amplitude waves

The calculation of pulsating forces can be derived from the linear theory of small amplitude waves and its pressure distribution (see Figure 3.12).

Figure 3.12 Pressure distribution in the crest phase of a standing wave in front of a vertical wall.

According to this theory, assuming the wall is totally reflective, the value of the maximum pressure is given by the following formulae:

$$p_{max} = \rho_w g H_i \frac{\cosh(k(h+z))}{\cosh(kz)} \quad \text{per } -h < z < 0 \quad (3.43)$$

$$p_{max} = \rho_w g H_i \left(1 - \frac{z}{H_i}\right) \quad \text{per } 0 < z < H_i \quad (3.44)$$

where H_i is the height of the incident wave, h is the depth, ρ_w is the density of the water, g is the acceleration of gravity and k is the wave number ($2\pi/L$, where L is the wavelength). The unit force applied on the structure is given by the integration of the previous relationship over the entire depth of the water:

$$F = \int_{-h}^0 \rho_w g H_i \frac{\cosh(k(h+z))}{\cosh(kz)} dz + \int_0^H \rho_w g H_i \left(1 - \frac{z}{H_i}\right) dz = \rho_w g H_i \left(\frac{\sinh(kh)}{k \cosh(kh)} + \frac{H_i}{2} \right) \quad (3.45)$$

Sainflou method

Sainflou's approach is based on Stokes' second-order wave theory and is therefore applicable to waves that are somewhat steeper than in the linear theory. It assumes that there is complete reflection and that the waves are of the non-breaking type. The waves follow trochoidal standing wave theory.

This method simplified the wave pressure theory, and gives the wave pressure distributions in crest and trough phases (Figure 3.13).

Figure 3.13 Crest and cable pressure distribution according to Saintflou's diagram.

It follows that the pressure at the crest of the wave is determined by the following equations:

$$P_1 = (P_2 + \omega_o h) \left(\frac{H+h_o}{H+h+h_o} \right) \quad (3.46)$$

$$P_2 = \rho_w g H_i \frac{\omega_o h}{\cosh\left(\frac{2\pi h}{L}\right)} \quad (3.47)$$

and in the trough wave condition:

$$P_1' = \omega_o (H - h_o) \left(\frac{H + h_o}{H + h + h_o} \right) \quad (3.48)$$

$$P_2' = P_2 = \rho_w g H_i \frac{\omega_o h}{\cosh\left(\frac{2\pi h}{L}\right)} \quad (3.49)$$

$$h_o = \left(\frac{\pi H^2}{L} \right) \coth\left(\frac{2\pi h}{L}\right) \quad (3.50)$$

In Equations (3.46) to (3.50), H is the wave height at water depth h , and h_o is the height of the centre of the clapotis orbit (mean water level at the wall) above the still water level (SWL). ω_o represents the specific gravity of seawater ($\rho_w g$).

The advantage of the Sainflou method is that it approximates the distribution of the resultant pressure with a straight line, making it easy to determine the resultant force. Experimental observations by Rundgren (1958) indicated that Sainflou's method overestimates the unbroken wave force for steep waves. Miche's (1944) higher-order theory, modified by Rundgren (1958) to consider the wave reflection coefficient of the structure, seems to fit better with experimentally measured forces on vertical walls for steep waves, while Sainflou's theory gives better results for long, low-steepness waves.

Several versions of the Sainflou formula appear in the literature. The original Sainflou formula dates back to 1928. Other versions appear in the Shore Protection Manual (CERC, 1984), Coastal Engineering Manual (USACE, 2002) and Van den Bos and Verhagen (2017), Leidraad Kunstwerken (2017).

A comparison between the parameters of the original Sainflou formula and the one proposed in the Leidraad Kunstwerken and the Coastal Engineering Manual (USACE, 2002) is presented in the following table.

Table 3.VI comparison between the parameters of the original Sainflou formula and the one proposed in the Leidraad Kunstwerken (TAW, 2003) and the Coastal Engineering Manual (USACE, 2002).

Symbol	Sainflou (1928)	Leidraad Kunstwerken (2003)	CEM (2002)
h_0	$kH_{inc}^2 \coth(\frac{1}{2}kd)$	$\frac{1}{2}kH_{inc}^2 \coth(kd)$	$\frac{1}{2}kH_{inc}^2 \coth(kd)$
h_p	$h_0 + 2H_{inc}$	$h_0 + H_{inc}$	$h_0 + 2H_{inc}$
p_0	$\rho g \frac{2H_{local}}{\cosh(\frac{1}{2}kd)}$	$\rho g \frac{H_{inc}}{\cosh kd}$	$\rho g \frac{2H_{inc}}{\cosh kd}$
p_1	$(p_0 + \rho g d) \frac{h_0 + 2H_{inc}}{d + h_0 + 2H_{inc}}$	$\rho g (h_0 + H_{inc})$	$(p_0 + \rho g d) \frac{h_0 + 2H_{inc}}{d + h_0 + 2H_{inc}}$

Miche-Rundgren method (Rundgren, 1958)

Miche uses the second-order theory of the motion of a standing wave, under the assumption that mass transport is zero, to determine the distribution of pressures on a vertical wall at a finite depth. At the bottom, pressure P_2 is the same as in the Sainflou scheme. The expression representing the trend of pressures below sea level differs from that proposed in the Sainflou method. For technical purposes, however, it is stated that it is adequate to consider the linear pressure distribution, assuming that the pressure value at the maximum/minimum surface elevation is zero. With this assumption, the pressure distribution becomes equal to Sainflou.

Miche also identifies a different relationship for calculating h_0 , given by the following formula:

$$h_0 = \left(\frac{\pi H^2}{4L} \right) \left(1 + \frac{3}{4 \sinh^2(2\pi d/L)} - \frac{1}{4 \cosh^2(2\pi d/L)} \right) \coth \left(\frac{2\pi d}{L} \right) \quad (3.51)$$

The previous relation reduces to Saintflou's in the case where the wave height is equal to the stationary wave height ($2H_i$, where H_i is the height of the incident wave approaching the structure).

Goda method (1973)

In 1966, Ito et al. developed a formula suitable for representing the pressure distribution on a vertical wall for any incident wave condition (breaker or non-breaker). Similarly, Goda (1974), on the basis of his earlier studies on the fourth-order nonlinear theory of wave of finite amplitude, proposed his own formula concerning the pressure exerted on a vertical wall, valid for non-breaking incident waves or under exclusively depth-related breaking conditions. Its application to the case where the breaking occurs under severe wave motion conditions with the concomitant formation of white-capping is excluded; indeed, in the case where the vertical wall is located on a steep seabed, or built on a very high foundation reef, i.e. in the case that geometric conditions favor high wave breaking pressure, the formula leads to an underestimation of the force exerted to the structure by the wave. The expression was later modified by Tanimoto et al. (1976) to take into account the effect of the angle of incidence of oblique wave fronts with respect to the alignment of the vertical wall. Further adjustments were made by Takahashi et al. (1994) to better represent the effects on the pressure distribution brought about by the berm of the embankment reef, a superstructure with an inclined face, wave breaking and the characteristics of the incident wave. In particular, Takahashi et al. (1994) modified the formula, introducing a coefficient that takes into account the contribution of impulsive pressures.

The original proposed formula (Goda,1973) has many advantageous features over its predecessors:

1. it is suitable for use for all wave conditions (i.e. both standing and breaking waves),
2. the design wave considered is the maximum wave height.
3. it is based on non-linear wave theory and can represent characteristic wave pressure by considering two components: that determined by breaking waves and the slowly varying (quasi-static) wave pressure. Therefore, it can be applied relatively easily to different types of vertical breakwaters.
4. the Goda formula also allows for the evaluation of the pressure distribution at the interface between the bottom of the caisson and the embankment layer; in this expression, the buoyancy force on the structure in still water and the uplift pressure determined by the wave action are defined separately.

Since Goda's formulae determine the force applied to the wall by a single wave, the wave parameters of the most severe wave force of a group of waves must be used in performance verifications of breakwaters, in general. The highest wave will be taken into account. The occurrence of the highest wave in a random wave group is a probabilistic event and therefore it is not possible to explicitly determine the wave parameters. However, based on empirical results Goda suggests using 1.8 times the significant wave height as the height of the highest wave, where no wave transformation is observed due to breaking. It has also become standard to use the wavelength corresponding to the significant wave period as the wavelength of the highest wave.

The formula therefore proposes a trapezoidal distribution of the pressures on the vertical wall and considers the wave H_{max} offshore, in the case of a non-breaking wave, given by the maximum height reached among 250 incident waves of a sea state, i.e. corresponding to a probability of exceedance equal to 0.4%. In the case of a breaking wave, Goda's relation considers as wave height the highest H_{max} among the random breaking waves, which is proposed at a distance of $5H_s$ from the vertical wall. The under-pressure distribution, on the other hand, has a triangular shape. Figure 3.14 below shows the diagram of the pressure distribution according to Goda (1974).

Figure 3.14 Pressure distribution according to Goda's scheme (1974).

The wave pressure is zero at the height expressed as η^* in Equation (3.52), the maximum value P_1 is expressed by Equation (3.53) at the still water level, the value P_3 at the base of the vertical wall and pressure p_2 in Equation (3.54) for the pressure at the depth of the seabed.

$$\eta^* = 0.75(1 + \cos \beta_{VB}) \lambda_1 H_{Des} \quad (3.52)$$

$$P_1 = 0.50(1 + \cos \beta_{VB})(\lambda_1 \alpha_1 + \lambda_2 \alpha^* \cos^2 \beta_{VB}) \omega_o H_D \quad (3.53)$$

$$P_2 = \frac{P_1}{\cosh\left(\frac{2\pi h}{L_{Des}}\right)} \quad (3.54)$$

$$P_3 = \alpha_3 p_1 \quad (3.55)$$

$$P = \alpha_4 p_1 \quad (3.56)$$

$$P_u = 0.5(1 + \cos \beta_{VB}) \lambda_3 \alpha_1 \alpha_3 \omega_o H_D \quad (3.57)$$

in which:

$$\alpha^* = \alpha_2 \quad (3.58)$$

$$\alpha_1 = 0.6 + 0.5 \left(\frac{\frac{4\pi h}{L_{Des}}}{\sinh\left(\frac{4\pi h}{L_{Des}}\right)} \right)^2 \quad (3.59)$$

$$\alpha_2 = \min \left\{ \frac{h_5 H_s - d}{3 h_5 H_s} \left(\frac{H_{Des}}{d} \right)^2, \left(\frac{2d}{H_{Des}} \right) \right\} \quad (3.60)$$

$$\alpha_3 = 1 - \left(\frac{h'}{h} \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\cosh\left(\frac{2\pi h}{L_{Des}}\right)} \right) \quad (3.61)$$

$$\alpha_4 = \left(1 - \frac{h_c}{\eta^*} \right) \text{ per } \eta^* > h_c \quad (3.62)$$

$$\alpha_4 = 0 \text{ per } \eta^* \leq h_c \quad (3.63)$$

where:

η^* = height above the quiet sea level where the wave pressure intensity is 0 [m]

β_{VB} = angle between the most dangerous direction within an interval of $\pm 15^\circ$ from the main wave direction and the line perpendicular to the frontal line of the vertical wall [°]

H_{Des} = design wave height (Goda considers $H_D = 1.8 H_{1/3} = 1.8 H_s$ in the case of a non-break wave, or the maximum wave height considering the transformation due to random wave breaking) [m]

L_{Des} = Design wave length (according to Goda the highest design wave length is that corresponding to the period of the significant wave $T_{1/3} = T_s$) [m]

P_1 = wave pressure at undisturbed sea level [kN/m²]

P_2 = wave pressure at the seabed level [kN/m²]

P_3 = wave pressure at the base of the vertical wall [kN/m²]

P_4 = wave pressure at the highest point of the loaded breakwater [kN/m²]

P_u = underpressure acting on the foundation base of the vertical structure [kN/m²]

$\omega_o = \rho_w g$ = specific weight of seawater [kN/m³]

α^* = pressure coefficient relative to wave impact [-]

α_1 = pressure coefficient dependent on the length (and period) of the design wave [-]

α_2 = pressure coefficient dependent on the steepness of the design wave [-]

α_3 = pressure coefficient dependent on pressure decrease with depth [-]

$\lambda_{1,2,3}$ = pressure correction factors (dependent on geometry, type of structure) [-]

h_{5H_S} = depth measured off the structure, at a distance of $5H_S$ from the wall [m]

h_c = height measured between mean sea level and the top of the caisson wall [m]

h = depth measured in front of the cliff slope [m]

h' = height of the vertical wall breakwater [m]

d = depth measured directly in front of the wall [m]

The three correction coefficients $\lambda_{1,2,3}$ allow Goda's formula to be used for vertical breakwaters characterized by different geometrical and typological configurations. For a vertical wall, the correction coefficients are obviously equal to 1.0. The wave pressure acting on other types of breakwaters, such as those protected with a clinker covering of boulders that dissipate the waves, or caissons with an anti-reflective vertical wall that dampens the wave actions, can also be expressed using Goda's generalised formulae corrected by appropriate correction coefficients.

The parameter α_1 given by Equation (3.59) expresses the effect on the pressure distribution which is determined by the wave period parameter; a value of 1.1 is assumed for shallow water waves and 0.6 for deep water waves. The wave period influences the maximum height to be used in the calculation; for a constant wave height in deep water, the greater the period, the greater the maximum height of the wave in a shallow sea; a greater amplitude implies an amplifying effect on the pressure distribution, taken into account by the parameter α_1 , which becomes larger.

The parameter α_2 evaluates the effect of the change in wave force determined by the height of the foundation reef and the slope of the bottom. As can be seen from Equation (3.60), when the height of the embankment slope is gradually increased from zero (i.e. $d = h$) with constant H_D , α_2 also increases from zero to a maximum value. After reaching its limit value, α_2 decreases until it reaches zero again for $d = 0$. The maximum value of α_2 is 1.1; combining this with the limiting value of α_1 equal to 1.1, the pressure intensity of wave P_1 , taken at still water level, is $2.2\rho_w g H_D$.

With regard to the effect of the bottom slope, since the variable h_{5H_S} in the equation used to determine α_2 represents the depth of the water at a distance from the vertical wall equal to 5 times the design significant wave height, a steep bottom slope can exert the same increasing effect on the pressure distribution, as the presence of a high foundation cliff. In the area of wave breaking, the steeper the slope of the bottom, the greater the wave height, since the wave height used in the calculation is the maximum height of the incipient breaking wave, related precisely to the depth h_{5H_S} , which, due to the steepness of the bottom, will be greater due to

its distance from the vertical wall of 5 times $H_{1/3}$. The slope of the seabed therefore has a strong influence on the force of the waves.

However, in some cases, for vertical-walled breakwaters located on a high reef foundation or steep seabed, the breaking wave may act with a large impulsive force, and under such conditions Goda's formulae may underestimate the wave force. When applying Goda's formulae, it is therefore preferable to pay attention to the risk of occurrence of impulsive wave force due to breaking waves. In particular, in some cases of breakers on rather high swells, it is necessary to consider the application of Goda's formula modified by Takahashi et al. (1994), which will be discussed below. It introduces not only the parameter α_2 into Equation (3.59), but also the impulsive wave force coefficient α_I , to be used instead of α_2 when α_I is the greater of the two.

A critical issue with Goda's formula concerns its applicability to extremely shallow waters, e.g. near the shoreline. For cases such as those in which waves exert their action on a vertical wall near the shoreline, it is advisable to use other calculation equations in conjunction with the Goda formula.

3.3.4 Calculation formulae for impulsive (breaking) wave loads on vertical walls

Breaker waves exert dynamic loads on the vertical wall in the form of pressures of short duration but much greater intensity than wave loads under stationary or quasi-static conditions. The first research on this specific topic was conducted in 1939 by Bagnold, who developed a conceptual model that became a reference for subsequent research. Bagnold proved that impulsive impact pressures occur when a breaker wave hits the vertical wall and only in the case where the falling breaker traps a cushion of air against the wall, but he did not propose any formula for determining the impulsive load itself. The formulas available in the literature are described below.

Hiroi method (1919)

Hiroi (1919) developed a formula representing the pressure distribution of a breaking wave in relatively shallow water, derived through empirical observations in the field, and used for a long time in Japan before the development of Goda's formula (1973). This formula assumes that the pressure distribution acts uniformly on the vertical wall.

The wave pressure is obtained from the following equation:

$$p = \rho_w g H_D \quad (3.64)$$

The highest point reached by the wave above the undisturbed sea level is defined by the following expression:

$$\eta^* = 1.25 H_{Des} \quad (3.65)$$

where:

H_{Des} is the design wave height, which is generally considered to be equal to the significant height $H_{1/3}$, since the difference between wave heights H_{max} and $H_{1/3}$ is negligible in shallow water.

The use of Hiroi's formula is recommended for applications in relatively shallow water ($h_s < 2H_{1/3}$), while for deep water with $h_s > 2H_{1/3}$ (see Figure 3.15), the use of Sainflou's formula is recommended (Allsop et al., 1996).

Figure 3.15 Pressure distribution according to Hiroi's diagram (1919).

Minikin method (1963)

The formulation proposed by Minikin (1963), concerns the distribution of pressures on the vertical wall generated by a breaking wave. This relationship also considers the contribution of impulsive loads, and suggests that the distribution has a parabolic trend.

The inherent limitation in using this formula is that it does not adequately describe how the geometric characteristics of the foundation cliff influence the distribution of impulsive pressures on the structure.

The dynamic pressure P_D takes on a maximum value at the undisturbed SWL and, in a parabolic pattern, decreases to zero at $0.5H_b$ above and below the SWL. It is shown in Figure 3.16 below and described mathematically by Equation (3.66):

$$P_D = 101\rho g \frac{H_b h_s}{L_D D} (D + h_s) \quad (3.66)$$

where:

H_b = height of the wave at the breaking [m];

$D = h_s + \tan\theta \cdot L_{h_s}$ = depth measured at a distance of one wavelength from the wall [m];

h_s = height of the wave at the base of the wall [m];

L_D = wavelength at depth D [m];

L_{h_s} = wavelength at depth h_s [m];

The total force resulting from the area representing the dynamic pressure distribution is given by:

$$R_D = \frac{P_D H_b}{3} \quad (3.67)$$

To determine the total force, it is necessary to add the hydrostatic contribution R_s , to the dynamic force R_D , acting on the vertical wall. More recent studies (Allsop et al., 1996) have shown that the above formulas are qualitatively flawed since R_D in Equation (3.67) decreases with increasing incident wavelength L_D , as well as being dimensionally inconsistent.

Figure 3.16 Pressure distribution according to Minikin's scheme (1963).

Figure 3.17 Pressure distribution according to Minikin's scheme (1963).

Ito method (1972)

In 1972, Ito updated Hiroi's formula, which was originally introduced for simple vertical walls, to take into account changes in pressure distributions induced by the presence of foundation reefs, thus extending the use to the case of composite breakwaters as well.

Ito's formula, like Hiroi's, considers the distribution of horizontal pressures acting on the vertical wall to be uniform and rectangular. Unlike the previous one, it also considers a triangular distribution of the under-pressures acting at the caisson-foundation wall interface; also, unlike the previous one, Ito's formula determines the pressure by considering the maximum wave height H_{max} , as the design wave height, instead of the significant wave height $H_{1/3}$. The reference value of H_{max} , is given by $2H_s$, on deep water and equal to H_b , if the wave motion is limited to breaking by depth. Therefore, Ito considers the distribution of pressures to take into account the ratio H/h_s between wave height and depth h_s measured at the base of the vertical wall, and therefore suggests that the determination of pressures should be based on this ratio. Ito's method has been approximated by Bruining (1994) with the formulation of two equations, the scope of which is precisely discriminated by this ratio, given below.

$$p = 0.7\rho_w g H_{max} \quad \text{for } H > h_s \tag{3.68}$$

$$p = \rho_w g H_{max} (0.15 + 0.55H)/h_s \quad \text{for } H < h_s \tag{3.69}$$

Blackmore and Hewson method (1984)

Blackmore & Hewson (1984) suggest a formula based on field measurements at a full scale. The formula considers observations, i.e. it considers the effect of trapped air, which leads to a reduction in the impact pressure of field tests compared to laboratory tests. The authors demonstrated that this discrepancy in results was due to the larger impact-damping effect of the larger amount of air trapped by the breaking waves in the real-world situation, than in the previous laboratory experiments; in the real-world case, the air cushion enclosed between the wave and the vertical wall is larger than in the experiments, and this larger amount of trapped air reduces the pressure forces exerted on the structure by the breaking waves.

Blackmore and Hewson (1984) proposed the following formula referring to the distribution of average pressures acting on the structure subjected to breaking waves:

$$p_1 = \lambda \rho C_b^2 T \quad (3.70)$$

where:

p_1 = is the peak pressure at the depth to the SWL equal to $0.5H_b$;

H_b = the wave height at the breaking;

T = wave period;

C_b = wave celerity in shallow water = $\sqrt{gh_s}$;

h_s = depth measured at the base of the structure;

λ = aeration factor, taking into account the percentage of the air trapped by the breaking waves; the factor has dimension $[s^{-1}]$ and takes on values between 0.1 and $0.3 s^{-1}$ under real conditions.

Figure 3.18 Pressure distribution according to the scheme of Blackmore & Hewson (1984).

In the proposed formula, the height of the breaking wave is taken into account in an indirect way, using the celerity of the wave in shallow water; the latter can be determined by considering the height of the breaking wave H_b and the breaking depth d_B , using the following relationship:

$$C_b = \sqrt{g(d_B + H_b)} \quad (3.71)$$

Partenscky method (1988)

The method, developed on the basis of previous studies by Oumeraci, proposes the following formula for calculating the maximum dynamic pressure for waves impacting the structure by transmitting short duration pulses in the range of 0.01-0.03 s:

$$p = K_L \rho_w g H_b \quad (3.72)$$

where H_b is the height of the breaking wave and K_L is a coefficient that takes into account the percentage of air trapped in the breaking wave, through the parameter a_0 , according to the following expression:

$$K_L = [5.4(1/a_0) - 1] \quad (3.73)$$

Goda method extended by Takahashi (1994)

Goda's original formula has a restricted field of application to the case of quasi-stationary wave motion, which corresponds to a very slowly varying pressure component over time and can therefore be assumed to be quasi-static, and to the case of breaking waves on a deep seabed, also known as slightly breaking waves. To include in the original formulation the impulsive (dynamic) forces caused by breaking waves directly on the structure, Takahashi proposed a new formulation of Goda's equations, modifying the coefficient α^* in the equation (3.58), which is replaced by:

$$\alpha^* = \max\{\alpha_2, \alpha_I\} \quad (3.74)$$

i.e. to be taken as the maximum value between the coefficient α_2 calculated by means of Equation (3.60) and a new coefficient α_I that derives from other coefficients, considering the geometry of the foundation reef and the height assumed by the wave above it.

The coefficient α_I can be determined using the diagram in Figure 3.19 below, proposed by Takahashi (1994), or alternatively by using the following expressions:

$$\alpha_I = \alpha_{I0} \cdot \alpha_{I1} \quad (3.75)$$

Figure 3.19 Calculation Diagram of impulsive pressure coefficient Takahashi (1994).

The coefficient α_{10} represents the effect of the height assumed by the wave above the cliff, while the coefficient α_{11} takes into account its geometric shape. They are respectively given by:

$$\alpha_{10} = \begin{cases} \frac{H}{d} & \text{when } H \leq 2d \\ 2.0 & \text{when } H > 2d \end{cases} \quad (3.76)$$

$$\alpha_{11} = \begin{cases} \frac{\cosh \delta_2}{\cosh \delta_1} & \text{when } \delta_2 \leq 0 \\ \frac{1}{\cosh \delta_1 \cdot (\cosh \delta_2)^{1/2}} & \text{when } \delta_2 > 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.77)$$

where the coefficients δ_1 and δ_2 are given by the following expressions:

$$\delta_1 = \begin{cases} 20 \cdot \delta_{11} & \text{when } \delta_{11} \leq 0 \\ 15 \cdot \delta_{11} & \text{when } \delta_{11} > 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.78)$$

$$\delta_{11} = 0.93 \left(\frac{B_m}{L} - 0.12 \right) + 0.36 \left(\frac{h_s - d}{h_s} - 0.6 \right) \quad (3.79)$$

$$\delta_2 = \begin{cases} 4.9 \cdot \delta_{22} & \text{when } \delta_{22} \leq 0 \\ 3.0 \cdot \delta_{22} & \text{when } \delta_{22} > 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.80)$$

$$\delta_{22} = -0.36 \left(\frac{B_m}{L} - 0.12 \right) + 0.93 \left(\frac{h_s - d}{h_s} - 0.6 \right) \quad (3.81)$$

where:

B_m = width of the berm of the foundation reef;

L = wavelength;

h_s = depth of water measured at the base of the cliff;

d = depth measured at the base of the structure.

The coefficient α_1 reaches a maximum value of 2 for $B_m/L = 0.12$, $d/h_s = 0.4$, and $H/d > 2$. For $d/h_s > 0.7$, the coefficient takes on values close to zero and is obviously lower than α_2 . Finally, the impulsive forces decrease significantly for oblique wave attack directions.

Goda's original formulation was developed for up-right breakwaters with simple vertical walls. To account for changes in the wave-induced pressure regime on structures with characteristics other than plain-walled vertical up-right breakwaters, Takahashi introduced the coefficients λ_1 , λ_2 and λ_3 . The Equation (3.53) therefore takes on a unit value for these coefficients in Goda's original formulation.

The λ_1 coefficient determines the increase or decrease in the pressure component of standing waves, the λ_2 coefficient introduces corrections in the component of dynamic or impulsive pressures generated by breaking waves, and finally the λ_3 coefficient determines changes in the regime of under pressures.

An example of the application of the coefficients λ_1 , λ_2 and λ_3 in the extended Goda formula elaborated by Takahashi concerns the type of perforated caissons with vertical rectangular

openings (vertical slit caisson), i.e. equipped with a frontal chamber that acts as an anti-reflection of wave motion through the dissipation of its energy content, generating vortices and turbulence inside it; a typical section of these perforated caissons is shown in Figure 3.20, but there are now worldwide different declinations of this type of structure based on the way the holes in the vertical front wall are made.

Figure 3.20 Cross-section of a typical Takahashi (1994) perforated caisson.

For this type of caisson, the force peak may occur in distinct phases during the evolution of the wave dynamics in front of the vertical wall and within the dissipation chamber. It is possible to identify three different critical moments during the passage of the wave crest and an equal number during the trough phase, as depicted in Figure 3.21 below. The pressure distribution must be distinctly calculated for each of these six conditions, to assess which of the six investigated conditions is the most severe.

Figure 3.21 Phases of wave evolution and related pressure calculation for a Takahashi (1994) perforated caisson.

Crest-I: This is the moment when the wave forces, which occur in crest conditions in front of the partly perforated and partly impermeable outer wall, reach their positive peak.

Crest-II a: This is the phase in which the load on the inner wall of the dissipation chamber develops as an impulsive force and reaches its peak value. This phase does not occur if the characteristics of the acting wave motion are such that forces of an impulsive nature do not develop.

Crest-II b: This is the phase in which the impulsive loads on the inner wall of the dissipation chamber reaches its lowest value.

Trough-I: This is the phase in which the stress on the outer wall of the caisson reaches its negative peak value.

Trough-II: This is the phase in which the sea level in front of the caisson is the lowest reached by the wave motion during the trough.

Trough-III: This is the time instant when the sea level inside the dissipation chamber is the lowest reached during the wave's cable phase.

The pressure distribution must be separately calculated for each of these six conditions to assess which of the six conditions is the most severe.

For the design of the perforated caisson, the pressure distribution in the three wave crest phases is conducted using Goda's formulae extended and modified by Takahashi, in which the λ_1 , λ_2 and λ_3 coefficients are replaced with those represented in the following table, which refers to the notation given in the diagram in Figure 3.22, relating to the pressure distribution in the Crest IIa phase; in that figure the suffixes to the λ coefficients refer to : S= slit wall; L= impermeable front wall; R= wave chamber rear wall; M= wave chamber bottom slab; and U= uplift force.

Table 3.VII Values of the pressure correction factors for the Goda's method extended by Takahashi (1994).

		Crest-I	Crest-IIa	Crest-IIb
Slit Wall	λ_{s1}	0.85	0.7	0.3
	λ_{s2}	0.4 ($\alpha^* \leq 0.75$) 0.3/ α^* ($\alpha^* > 0.75$)	0	0
Impermeable Front Wall	λ_{L1}	1	0.75	0.65
	λ_{L2}	0.4 ($\alpha^* \leq 0.5$) 0.2/ α^* ($\alpha^* > 0.5$)	0	0
Wave Chamber Rear Wall	λ_{R1}	0	20/3L' ($H/L' \leq 0.15$) 1.0 ($H/L' > 0.15$)	1.4 ($H_p/h \leq 0.1$) 1.6-2H _p /h (0.1 < H _p /h < 0.3) 1.0 (H _p /h \geq 0.3)
	λ_{R2}	0	0.56 ($\alpha^* \leq 25/28$) 0.5/ α^* ($\alpha^* > 25/28$)	0
Wave Chamber Bottom Slab	λ_{M1}	0	20/3L' ($H/L' \leq 0.15$) 1.0 ($H/L' > 0.15$)	1.4 ($H_p/h \leq 0.1$) 1.6-2H _p /h (0.1 < H _p /h < 0.3) 1.0 (H _p /h \geq 0.3)
	λ_{M2}	0	0	0
Uplift Force	λ_{U1}	1	0.75	0.65
	λ_{U2}	0	0	0

Figure 3.22 Wave pressure distribution at crest-IIb for a perforated wall caisson.

For this type of caisson, the coefficient α_I , through which it is possible to evaluate the impulsive component of the pressure, is replaced with the coefficient α'_I ; for its evaluation, the following substitutions are made for the physical and geometric parameters used in the calculation of α_I :

- d is replaced by d' (depth of the dissipation chamber);
- L is replaced by L' (wavelength corresponding to the depth d');
- B_m = width of the berm of the foundation cliff is replaced by $B'_m = \max \{l - (d - d'), 0\}$, where l is the width of the dissipation chamber.

Takahashi method

The method is based on a simplified model of the pressure distribution of impulsive waves, which considers the angle of attack of the wave, but also the characteristic curvature δ , assumed by the wave at the moment of breaking, which is variable, according to the way the breaking wave impacts the structure. Based on the value of the curvature δ , Takahashi distinguishes three types of impulsive breaking waves, as represented in Figure 3.23, and suggests a formulation to calculate the maximum intensity of the pressure in the form of $p/\omega_o H$, for the curvature of the breaking wave equal to $\delta > \beta > 0$, and a relationship to determine the duration τ of the pressure pulse. The two relations are given below:

$$\frac{p}{\omega_o H} = \frac{0.4\pi K_m^2}{K_a} \cdot \frac{h + 0.75H}{h_{toe} + R_c} \quad (3.82)$$

$$\tau = \pi \left(\frac{\pi \omega_o K_m^2 K_l^2 K_a H^2}{4\gamma_{heat} g P_o} \right) \quad (3.83)$$

where:

K_m is a correction factor related to the mass (in practical applications, assumed to be 0.83);

K_l is an impulse coefficient related to the height of the wave (it is given by the ratio between the height of the wave front l (see Figure 3.23) and the height of the wave H ; in theory it can assume values between 0 and 1, but in practice a variation range between 0.49-0.90 is considered);

K_a is a coefficient related to the size of the air cushion (related to angles β and δ and its minimum value ranges between 0.01 and 0.1);

h is the water depth;

h_{toe} is the water depth measured at the foot of the vertical wall;

γ_{heat} is the heat capacity ratio (specific heat ratio);

P_o is the atmospheric pressure.

It is evident from the above formula that the impulse pressure increases as the height of the wave front increases and the trapped air cushion decreases.

Figure 3.23 Three basic type of impulsive pressure (Takahashi et.al. 1994).

Klammer, Korthenaus and Oumeraci method (1996)

As part of the European research project PROVERBS 'Probabilistic Design Tools for Vertical Breakwaters', several experiments were conducted on a large-scale model at the Large Wave Flume (GWK) laboratories in Hannover, Germany, to compare the results of horizontal impulsive forces on a vertical wall observed under random wave conditions with those calculated using the method of Klammer, Korthenaus and Oumeraci.

Figure 3.24 Stress time distribution diagram (Klammer et al., 1996).

Using a model based on impulse and solitary wave theory, the following predictive formula for horizontal forces under peak conditions was proposed by the aforementioned authors:

$$\frac{F_{h,max}}{\rho \cdot g \cdot H_b^2} = 8.94 \cdot \frac{k_{wm}}{k_{r,Fh}} \cdot \left(\frac{t_R}{\sqrt{d_b/g}} \right)^{-1} \quad (3.84)$$

where:

k_{wm} = parameter of water mass m involved in the impact;

Experimentally, the observed values, dependent on the wave breaking mode, are as follows: for a fully developed plunging type wave with a large amount of air trapped in the breaker $k_{wm} = 11\%$, for a plunging type wave with little air trapped $k_{wm} = 16\%$, for a flip-trough type breaker wave $k_{wm} = 28\%$ (see Figure 3.21). The authors of the formula propose the following values:

- well developed plunging breaker: $k_{wm} = 0.10$;
- plunging breaker: $k_{wm} = 0.15$;
- 'flip-through': $k_{wm} = 0.20$;

$k_{r,Fh}$ = parameter referring to the time development of the impact forces on the vertical wall. The authors of the formula propose the following values:

- well developed plunging breaker: $k_{r,Fh} = 0.80$;
- plunging breaker: $k_{r,Fh} = 0.80$;
- 'flip-through': $k_{r,Fh} = 1.00$;

t_R = time taken to reach the maximum peak value of the horizontal force, assuming linear load growth (see Figure 3.25).

Figure 3.25 Impact modes of plunging breaking waves on a vertical wall (Klammer et al., 1996).

Using a cautious and conservative approach, given the lack of an unambiguous parameter allowing the identification of which type of breaking wave acts on the wall, we may consider $k_{wm} = 0.20$ and $k_{r,Fh} = 0.8$ in the previous equation, which is simplified in the form:

$$\frac{F_{h,max}}{\rho \cdot g \cdot H_b^2} = 2.24 \cdot \left(\frac{t_r}{\sqrt{d_b/g}} \right)^{-1} \quad (3.85)$$

For the wave height referred to in the previous report, it is determined by the expression provided by Oumeraci et al. (1993), in which the reflective effect of the vertical structure and its influence on wave breaking is considered.

$$H_b = L_b \cdot \left[0.1025 + 0.0217 \cdot \left(\frac{1 - k_r}{1 + k_r} \right) \right] \cdot \tanh \left(2\pi \frac{d_b}{L_b} \right) \quad (3.86)$$

where:

d_b = water depth at which the wave breaks;

L_b = wavelength of the breaking wave;

k_r = reflection coefficient of the structure.

For calculating the height of the breaking wave H_b , the actual depth in front of the structure must be considered. The presence of a foundation cliff may indeed affect the breaking depth d_b . However, in case the berm of the foundation cliff has a limited width B_b (i.e. $B_b/L < 0.15$), this effect is limited, and the depth d measured directly in front of the structure can be considered. At the same time, considering $d_b = h_s$, leads to an overestimation of the height H_b , since this assumption neglects, in the phenomenon of landsliding, the influence of the geometric

characteristics of the cliff (width B_b of the berm and slope 1:m with $m=\cot\alpha$ of the external face) as well as the length of the incident wave L .

It is therefore necessary to refer to an effective calculation depth d_{eff} , which considers the above parameters and is given by:

$$d_{eff} = d + B_{rel} \cdot m_{rel} \cdot (h_s - d) \quad (3.87)$$

where B_{rel} and m_{rel} are respectively the part of the berm and the portion of the escarpment that have an influence on the breaking depth and are given by:

$$B_{rel} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{per } \frac{B_b}{L} > 1 \\ 1 - 0.5 \cdot \frac{B_b}{L} & \text{per } \frac{B_b}{L} \leq 1 \end{cases} \quad (3.88)$$

$$m_{rel} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{per } m < 1 \\ m - 0.5 & \text{per } m \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (3.89)$$

Allsop and Vicinanza method (1996)

As part of the European research project PROVERBS 'Probabilistic Design Tools for Vertical Breakwaters', numerous tests on small-scale models subjected to random waves were conducted at HR Wallingford's laboratories. From the results of these simulations, a new formula for the prediction of impulsive pressure distributions on vertical breakwaters was deduced. This is valid in a narrow range of application, i.e. for waves impacting the walls in the range $0.35 < H_{si}/d < 0.6$.

The method is recommended in Oumeraci et al. (2001) only for preliminary design and by the British Standards (BS6349-1 and BS6349-2, 2000), and is expressed by the following relationship:

$$F_h = 15\rho_w \cdot g \cdot h^2 (H_{1/3}/h)^{3.134} \quad (3.90)$$

where:

h = is the depth of water measured at the foundation berm;

$H_{1/3}$ = significant wave height.

PROVERBS method (2001)

PROVERBS (an acronym for PRObabilistic design tools for VERTical BreakwaterS) is the name of a research project included in the 4th Framework Program of the European Union, which aims to provide tools for the design of vertical breakwaters based on the principle of reliability to limit states of structures according to probabilistic criteria.

As part of this research project, Oumeraci et al. (2001) developed guidelines for determining the loads exerted by wave motion on structures, both in stationary conditions and in breaking situations.

The method proposed in PROVERBS, for evaluating the forces acting on the sea-side structure, the land-side structure and the forces acting on the foundation sole directed upwards, consists of 12 steps; through these steps, indications are given on the pressure distribution along the wall, but also on the time necessary to reach the maximum value of the impact forces.

Figure 3.26 shows the pressure distribution and the nomenclature of geometric features used in the PROVERBS method. The main formulations obtained for the design using the probabilistic method described by Oumeraci et al., 2001 in PROVERBS are described below.

Figure 3.26 Pressure distribution diagram according to PROVERBS.

Calculation of the wave height at breaking in front of vertical wall structures

To consider the influence of the reflection by vertical wall structures on wave breaking, a new criterion was suggested by Calabrese (1997), which is based on the results of numerous hydraulic model tests with random waves and previous theoretical models developed by Oumeraci et al. (1993). The wave height at breaking is given by the following expression:

$$H_b = L_{pi} \cdot \left[0.1025 + 0.0217 \left(\frac{1 - k_r}{1 + k_r} \right) \right] \cdot \left[\tanh \left(\frac{2\pi k_b h_s}{L_{pi}} \right) \right] \quad (3.91)$$

where:

k_r is the reflection coefficient; and the following reference values are assumed:

$k_r = 0.95$ for simple vertical walls and small mounds, high crest;

$k_r = 0.8 + 0.1 \cdot R_c/H_{si}$ for low crest walls ($0.5 < R_c/H_{si} < 1.0$);

$k_r = 0.5$ to 0.7 for composite walls, large mounds, and heavy breaking;

L_{pi} is the wavelength at depth h_s (at the base of the cliff) and relative to the peak period T_p , determined iteratively with linear wave theory, by the following expression:

$$L_{pi} = \left(\frac{gT_p^2}{2\pi} \right) \left[\tanh \left(\frac{2\pi h_s}{L_{pi}} \right) \right] \quad (3.92)$$

k_b is an empirical correction factor estimated through the following relationship:

$$k_b = 0.0076 \left(\frac{B_{eq}}{d} \right)^2 - 0.1402 \left(\frac{B_{eq}}{d} \right) + 1 \quad (3.93)$$

where B_{eq} is the equivalent width of the cliff berm, defined by the following expression:

$$B_{eq} = B_b + \frac{h_b}{2 \tan \alpha_{cliff}} \quad (3.94)$$

Where $\tan \alpha_{cliff}$ is the slope of the sea-side foundation cliff, and B_b is the width of its berm, while h_b is the height of the foundation cliff and d is the depth of water measured at the base of the caisson.

Calculation of wave impact probability

Considering that the impulsive forces are much higher than the loads induced by quasi-stationary waves, weakly breaking waves and broken waves, it is necessary to know, before applying a formula for calculating the forces acting on a structure, what type of wave regime is characteristic of the vertical breakwater to design.

It is therefore necessary to determine the number of the waves approaching the structure which break directly on it, causing impulsive forces, and how many waves will not, transmitting only non-impulsive forces (well treated by Goda). To this end, considering that wave heights larger than the breaking wave H_b (obtained with the equation above), will approach the structure already broken or break on it with an impact, it can be stated that the probability of exceedance of the breaking wave height H_b , is given by:

$$P_b(\%) = \exp \left[-2 \left(\frac{H_b}{H_{si}} \right)^2 \right] \times 100 \quad (3.95)$$

where H_{si} is the significant wave height at depth h_s , measured at the base of the foundation cliff.

The maximum wave height separating impulsive waves by already broken waves is determined by the following relationship:

$$H_{bs} = 0.1242 L_{pi} \left[\tanh \left(\frac{2\pi h_s}{L_{pi}} \right) \right] \quad (3.96)$$

Therefore, the percentage of waves breaking directly on the structure is given by the following relationship:

$$P_i(\%) = \left\{ \exp \left[-2 \left(\frac{H_{bc}}{H_{si}} \right)^2 \right] - \exp \left[-2 \left(\frac{H_{bs}}{H_{si}} \right)^2 \right] \right\} \times 100 \quad (3.97)$$

Through the results obtained using the above relationship, the following cases can be distinguished:

$P_i(\%) < 2\%$ Weak breaking, transmitted loads are non-breaking;

$2\% < P_i(\%) < 10\%$ Breaking waves resulting in impacts;

$P_i(\%) > 10\%$ Very intense breaking resulting in impact loads.

For very low impact rates (less than 1%), the problem is reduced to the quasi-static problem and the Goda method can be used to calculate pressures and forces. In all others circumstances, the method described below must be used.

Calculation of maximum horizontal forces for impulsive loads

To determine the maximum horizontal force for a fixed probability of exceedance (and thus a fixed return time), it is necessary to know the probability distribution that best fits the observations on impact forces obtained experimentally. The studies carried out suggest that the GEV (Generalised Distribution of Extreme Values) is the best distribution to fit the impulsive force. The GEV distribution can be expressed as:

$$F_{h,max}^* = \frac{\alpha_{GEV}}{\gamma_{GEV}} \{1 - [-\ln P(F_{h,max}^*)] \gamma_{GEV}\} + \beta_{GEV} \quad (3.98)$$

where, $P(F_{h,max}^*)$ is the probability of non-exceedance of the impulsive forces (generally set at 90%), while α_{GEV} , β_{GEV} and γ_{GEV} are the statistical parameters of the GEV distribution, determined from the results of the tests carried out with the scaled physical models; when the slope of the bottom was assumed to be 1/20 in the model, the values assumed by the aforementioned parameters are 3.745, 7.604 and -0.295, respectively.

The maximum horizontal force is given by the following expression:

$$F_{h,max} = F_{h,max}^* \cdot \rho_w g H_b^2 \quad (3.99)$$

Where H_b is the height of the breaking wave calculated using the above expression (3.99), and ρ_w is the density of water.

Determining the simplified time course of impulsive forces

In the case of impulsive forces, the loads acting on the structure, are time-varying. It would therefore be necessary to know the complete history of the impact force, to consider the time-varying forces and pressures induced by the breaking wave. The typical time history of the horizontal load on the structure is, for practical reasons, simplified by replacing it with a triangular diagram (see Figure 3.27), which is identified by two main parameters: the rise time t_r and the total duration of the impulsive action t_d .

Figure 3.27 Simplified diagram of the time course of the impulsive force (Oumeraci et al., 2001).

The area of the typical impulse diagram during a period equal to its total duration $t_{d,Fh}$ is given by the summation of impulses I_{rFh} and I_{dFh} . The actual force history is replaced by an equivalent triangle, having the same horizontal force peak F_h , the same I_{rFh} and I_{dFh} pulses, with different rise times t_r and total impact duration t_d .

I_{rFh} is the momentum of the water mass involved in the impact, while I_{dFh} is the momentum of the total mass involved in the wave breaking.

To determine the accretion time of the impact force, the theoretical approach of Korthenaus and Oumearci described earlier, based on the solitary wave hypothesis, is used in Proverbs.

The experimentally measured rise time is determined using the following expression:

$$t_{r,Fh} = 8.94 k_w \frac{\sqrt{d_{eff}/g}}{F_{h,max}^*} \quad (3.100)$$

where d_{eff} has the same meaning and the same wording as in (3.87) above, where B_{rel} assumes the same expression (3.86), while m_{rel} in PROVERBS assumes the following expression:

$$m_{rel} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for vertical wall without berms} \\ 1 & \text{per } m < 1 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{m}} & \text{per } m \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (3.101)$$

k_w is the ratio between the mass of water which hits the wall M_{imp} , and the total mass of the breaking wave. It depends by the type of breaking and can be estimated by:

$$k_w = \frac{M_{imp}}{M_{wave}} = \frac{I_{r,Fh}}{I_{d,Fh}} = 0.16 \div 0.25 \quad (3.102)$$

In the case of deterministic approach t_r is therefore given by the following relation:

$$t_r = (0.5 \text{ to } 1.0)t_{r,Fh} \quad (3.103)$$

In the probabilistic approach, the value $(8.94 k_w)$, in the previous relation (3.100) is substituted by a single coefficient k' , and the rise time is given by the following expression:

$$t_r = k' \frac{\sqrt{d_{eff}/g}}{F_{h,max}^*} \quad (3.104)$$

The factor k' can thus be well described by a log-normal distribution with a mean value of 0.086 and a standard deviation of 0.084.

The total duration t_d depends on the type of breaking. In a deterministic approach, the upper limit calculated on random-wave test results (shown in Figure 3.28) is explained by the following relation:

$$t_d = t_r \cdot [2.0 + 8 \cdot \exp(-18t_r T_p)] \quad (3.105)$$

Figure 3.28 Triangular impact duration t_d vs. relative triangular rise time t_r for random waves (Oumeraci et al., 2001).

As we can see from Figure 3.28, the total duration is rarely less than 2.0, i.e. the decay time of the impact is usually longer than the rise time.

In a probabilistic approach, the total pulse duration is given by the following expression:

$$t_d = \frac{-c}{\ln(t_r)} \quad (3.106)$$

where c is an empirical parameter with a Gaussian probability distribution with a mean value of 2.17 and standard deviation of 1.08.

Determining the simplified pressure distribution of impulsive forces

Based on the analysis of approximately 1000 impact pressure distributions measured during the large-scale model tests, the simplified distribution of pressures at the instant of maximum impact force $F_{h,max}$ was derived (see Figure 3.28 above). Four parameters are required to describe this distribution.

Elevation of the pressure distribution

It can be determined by this first attempt formula:

$$\eta^* = 0.8H_b \quad (3.107)$$

The bottom pressure p_3 can be derived as a function of the maximum pressure at the still water level as follows:

$$P_3 = 0.45P_1 \quad (3.108)$$

Maximum pressure P_1

Given that $F_h(t)$ represents the sum of the instantaneous pressure distribution acting on the structure (assumed to be an infinitely high wall), the maximum pressure P_1 at sea level SWL and the pressure at the crest of the structure are determined from the equivalent triangular force versus time diagram $F_h(t)$, for the two distinct cases of overtopping or non-overtopping on the structure.

- Without overtopping $h_c > \eta^*$
In this case we have:

$$F_h(t) = \frac{1}{2}P_1(t)\eta^* + (d + d_c)P_3 \cdot (P_1(t) - P_3) \quad (3.109)$$

Whence, by substituting Equation (3.107) and Equation (3.108) into Equation (3.109):

$$P_1(t) = \frac{F_h(t)}{0.4 \cdot H_b + 0.7 \cdot (d + d_c)} \quad (3.110)$$

With regard to the pressure at the crest of the structure p_4 , we have:

$$P_4=0 \quad (3.111)$$

- With Overtopping $h_c < \eta^*$
The force reduction due to overtopping is considered by cutting the pressure distribution at the level of the structure crest. In this case we have:

$$F_{h,max,ov} = F_{h,max} - \frac{1}{2}(\eta^* - h_c)P_4 \quad (3.112)$$

whence

$$P_1(t) = \frac{F_h(t)}{0.7 \cdot (d + d_c) + \frac{h_c}{2} \left(1 + \frac{\eta^* - h_c}{\eta^*}\right)} \quad (3.113)$$

With regard to the pressure at the crest of structure P_4 , we have:

$$P_4 = \frac{\eta^* - h_c}{\eta^*} P_1 \quad (3.114)$$

Determining the horizontal force arm

The arm of the horizontal force can be determined using the pressure distribution through the following expression:

$$l_{Fh}(t) = \frac{P_1\eta_{ov}^2 + 3P_1d'\eta_{ov} + 3P_4d'\eta_{ov} + 2P_4\eta_{ov}^2 + 2P_1d'^2 + P_3d'^2}{6F_h(t)} \quad (3.115)$$

where:

$$\eta_{ov} = \min\{\eta^*; h_c\} \quad (3.116)$$

$$d' = d + d_c \quad (3.117)$$

Determination of the uplift force

For the calculation of the uplift force acting below the foundation of the vertical structure, the same relations defined for the horizontal impulsive force (3.98) can be used, but with statistical parameters of the GEV probability distribution equal to: $\alpha_{GEV} = 2.17$; $\beta_{GEV} = 4.384$; $\gamma_{GEV} = -0.11$ (derived from large-scale model tests with a bed slope of 1:50).

The calculation of the rising time of the uplift forces can be performed using the same formula (3.104) in which the factor k' takes the value of 0.16 (standard deviation of 0.17);

For the total duration t_d , the same expression is used as for the impact forces (3.106), but assuming an average of 1.88 and a standard distribution of 0.99.

Determination of under pressure distribution

The pressure on the outer land-side edge of the foundation is given by the following expression:

$$p_{ru} = \rho g H_b \cdot \left(\frac{H_b}{h_s} - 0.1 \right) \quad (3.118)$$

Having noted the value of the land-side pressure, it is possible to determine the pressure on the outer sea-side edge of the foundation using the following relationship:

$$p_u = \frac{2F_{u,max}}{B_c} - p_{ru} \quad (3.119)$$

where:

B_c = the width of the structure;

$F_{u,max}$ = the maximum value of the lifting force;

p_{ru} = pressure on the ground-side outer edge of the foundation.

The lifting force arm can be determined for each moment from the considered instantaneous pressure distribution using the following expression:

$$l_{Fu}(t) = \frac{B_c^2 \cdot (p_{ru} + 2p_u)}{6 F_{u,max}} \quad (3.120)$$

Cuomo et al. method (2010)

Based on the results of experimental work carried out on a large-scale model at the CIEM/LIM laboratory in Barcelona, as part of the VOWS (Violent Overtopping by Waves at Seawall) research project, Cuomo et al. (2010) proposed a predictive formula for wave forces acting on vertical breakwaters, valid under both standing and impulsive wave conditions.

The total horizontal force impacting the structure (referring to an overtopping level of 1/250) can be determined using the following relationship:

$$F_{h,imp,1/250} = k_r^{1.65} \rho g \cdot H_s \cdot L_{hs} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{|h_b - d|}{d} \right) \quad (3.121)$$

where:

k_r = reflection coefficient

H_s = significant (spectral) wave height;

L_{hs} = wavelength at the base of the structure relative to the mean period of the wave T_m ;

d = depth of water in front of the structure.

The term $\left(1 - \frac{|h_b - d|}{d} \right)$, where h_b represents the breaking depth, is indicative of the degree of severity of the breaking in front of the structure. The depth h_b is evaluated using an expression derived from Miche's breaking criterion, where $H_b = H_s$; this relationship is given below:

$$h_b = \frac{1}{k} \operatorname{arctanh} \left(\frac{H_s}{0.14 \cdot L_{hs}} \right) \quad (3.122)$$

where $k = 2\pi/L_{hs}$.

Based on the experimental observations made during the physical model tests, Cuomo et al. proposed a new predictive formula valid in the case of quasi-static wave motion, which is given below:

$$F_{h,qs,1/250} = 4.8\rho g H_{m0}^2 \quad (3.123)$$

The above prediction formula is valid $0.2 \text{ m} < H_s < 0.7 \text{ m}$, $0.5 \text{ m} < h_s < 1.3 \text{ m}$ and $2 \text{ s} < T_m < 3.7 \text{ s}$.

All the methods discussed up to now consider plain vertical walls. In the case of perforated vertical walls, the reflection and turbulence will be lower. Despite their increased complexity and cost of construction as compared to plain caissons, perforated caissons are becoming more and more popular not only for antireflective quay walls inside sheltered harbors, but also for external caisson breakwaters, to partly overcome the typical drawbacks of vertical structures: large reflections, forces, overtopping and toe scour. Perforated vertical breakwaters are intended to absorb part of the wave energy through various mechanisms, such as turbulence, resonance and viscous. The larger the water level difference at the two porous wall sides, the larger the energy dissipation is, which is therefore strongly dependent on the wave length L (Oumeraci et al., 2001).

3.4 Design formulas for seawalls

Seawalls are shore-parallel structures designed to prevent coastal risks, such as further shoreline erosion and flooding, and to protect infrastructures or roads from wave action (Allsop et al., 2005; Kraus and McDougal, 1996).

Wave overtopping is one of the main failure mechanisms of seawalls; indeed, it may cause hinterland flooding and jeopardize assets and human safety. Hence, overtopping-related variables (e.g. mean overtopping discharge, q , and the maximum individual wave overtopping volume, V_{max}) are used in the design process to determine the main structural variables, such as the crest freeboard, R_c , for vertical seawalls. The proper assessment of R_c – the crest height from the still water level – has to ensure that the average flow rate and the maximum individual overtopping volume do not exceed the safety limits indicated in the guidelines (e.g. EurOtop, 2018; The Rock Manual, 2007).

For design purposes, the engineering community can resort to different empirical models. These can be split into traditional regression formulae and machine learning techniques, e.g., the Artificial Neural Network of Zanuttigh et al. (2016) or the boosting decision tree XGBoost of Den Bieman et al. (2021), which exploit the availability of large databases (i.e. CLASH⁷).

The design formulae for vertical seawalls in the surf zone are listed and discussed in the following.

Goda (2009)

Goda (2009) provides a unique predictive formula valid for both vertical and sloping seawalls built at any depth from deep water to the shoreline:

$$\frac{q}{\sqrt{g \cdot H_{s,TOE}^3}} = \exp \left[- \left(a_G + b_G \cdot \frac{R_c}{H_{s,TOE}} \right) \right] \quad (3.124)$$

where q is the mean wave overtopping discharge, g is the gravity acceleration, $H_{s,TOE}$ is the significant wave height at the toe of the structure, R_c is the structure freeboard, and a_G and b_G are empirical coefficients. The Goda's model relates the mean overtopping discharge only to the significant wave height (either H_s or $H_{1/3}$) at the toe of the structure; the influence of the wave period is neglected.

The coefficients a_G and b_G in Equation (3.124) have been determined based on selected CLASH datasets, which count 715 and 1254 data for vertical and sloping seawalls, respectively. These depend on the relative toe depth, $h_{TOE}/H_{s,TOE}$, on the foreshore slope, $\tan m$, and on the surface slope for inclined seawalls.

It is worth noting that, as the performance of the model decreases for lower flow rates, the author recommended the use for preliminary design only.

IFORM – Mase et al. (2013) and Yuhi et al. (2021)

The predictive formula of Mase et al. (2013) allows to estimate the mean overtopping discharge of seawalls located on land or in very shallow water. The flow rate depends on the maximum run-up (R_{MAX}), the crest freeboard (R_c) and the deepwater significant wave height (H_{s0}):

$$\frac{q}{\sqrt{g \cdot H_{s0}^3}} = c_M \cdot a_M \cdot \left(\frac{R_{MAX}}{H_{s0}} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R_c}{H_{s0}} \right)^{b_M} \quad \begin{array}{l} 0 < R_c \\ \leq R_{MAX} \end{array} \quad (3.125)$$

where the maximum run-up, namely the run-up height not exceeded in $p\%$ of cases in runs of 100 waves, and a_M , b_M , and c_M are empirical coefficients. Hence, the authors adopt a run-up statistics as hydraulic variable; indeed, the IFORM is based on the approach of Hedges and Reis (1998), which considers two physical restraints: wave overtopping does not occur when the maximum run-up is lower than the crest of the seawall, and the flow rate remains finite when the crest freeboard is zero.

Assuming a Rayleigh distribution, R_{MAX} is related to $R_{2\%}$ and can be determined by means of the following equation:

$$R_{MAX} = R_{99\%} = 1.52 \cdot R_{2\%} = 1.54 \cdot H_{s0} \cdot \left[2.99 - 2.73 \cdot \exp \left(-0.57 \cdot \frac{\tan \alpha}{\sqrt{s_0}} \right) \right] \quad (3.126)$$

where s_0 is the deep-water wave steepness and $\tan \alpha$ is the imaginary slope proposed by the authors. In particular, the latter takes into account a cross-sectional area of seawall and foreshore between the wave breaking point, h_b , and the run-up level, $R_{2\%}$. Thus, an iterative approach is necessary. Furthermore, the model requires the water depth at breaking point, that is anything but easy to estimate for irregular wave trains.

It is worth noting that Mase et al. also provided a predictive model that refers to a most probable maximum run-up, namely the value not exceeded in 37% of the (cases assuming a Rayleigh distribution).

The coefficient a and b depend on relative crest freeboard; in particular, Yuhi et al. (2021) have provided a set of piecewise formulas based on a new regression analysis by using 132 laboratory data of Altomare et al. (2016) and 270 data of CLASH database. Furthermore, to extend the applicability of the empirical formula to vertical or steep walls, Tamada et al. (2015) have introduced the coefficient c that depends on the structure's slope and is equal to 0.5 in case of vertical seawalls.

EurOtop Manual (2018)

The EurOtop Manual (2018) provides different predictive formulae depending on several factors, as proved by the decision chart that launches the Manual's chapter regarding vertical walls.

As concerns seawalls in shallow water, the Manual distinguishes between breaking and non-breaking waves; such a discrimination is based on impulsiveness parameter, h^* . When waves are relatively small relative to the local water depth, "non-impulsive" or "pulsating" ($h^* > 0.23$) loads occur, while impulsive condition ($h^* \leq 0.23$) describes waves that break along the foreshore or against the wall.

The equation of the impulsiveness parameter reads:

$$h^* = \frac{h_{TOE}^2}{H_{s,TOE} \cdot L_{m-1,0,TOE}} \quad (3.127)$$

where $L_{m-10,TOE}$ is the deep-water wavelength related to the harmonic spectral period $T_{m-1,0,TOE}$. For non-breaking waves, $h^* > 0.23$, the EurOtop Manual (2018) suggests:

$$\frac{q}{\sqrt{g \cdot H_{s,TOE}^3}} = 0.05 \cdot \exp\left(-2.78 \cdot \frac{R_c}{H_{s,TOE}}\right) \quad (3.128)$$

The two coefficients in Equation (3.128) refer to the mean value approach of the EurOtop Manual (2018); in the design (semi-probabilistic) approach, the coefficients become 0.062 and 2.61, respectively.

On the other hand, two equations are used to describe the overtopping of breaking waves depending on the relative crest freeboard value. For low-crested structure, an exponential formula is provided; otherwise, the overtopping model follows a power law:

$$\frac{q}{\sqrt{g \cdot H_{s,TOE}^3}} = 0.011 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{L_{m-10,TOE}}{h_{TOE}}} \cdot \exp\left(-2.2 \cdot \frac{R_c}{H_{s,TOE}}\right) \quad R_c/H_{s,TOE} < 1.35 \quad (3.129)$$

$$\frac{q}{\sqrt{g \cdot H_{s,TOE}^3}} = 0.0014 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{L_{m-10,TOE}}{h_{TOE}}} \cdot \left(\frac{R_c}{H_{s,TOE}}\right)^{-3} \quad R_c/H_{s,TOE} \geq 1.35 \quad (3.130)$$

The coefficients in Equation (3.141) and Equation (3.142) are those relative to the mean value approach; in the design approach, the coefficients are 0.0155 in Equation (3.141) and 0.002 in Equation (3.142).

Unlike the predictive model for pulsating waves, the EurOtop Manual (2018) formula relates the mean overtopping discharge in impulsive conditions to both the significant wave height and the harmonic spectral period.

In the design process of sea defenses, the maximum individual overtopping volume, V_{MAX} , is handled as a key variable as well. Indeed, in many cases, individual overtopping volumes can be significantly larger than the mean volume; hence, this variable must be addressed to guarantee structural and functional safety. However, unlike q , assessing V_{MAX} is quite challenging since it is related to individual wave overtopping events and requires a wave-by-wave analysis.

Individual overtopping events are described by the exceedance probability distribution, which is commonly related to the mean overtopping discharge, the storm duration and the probability of overtopping, P_{OW} (i.e. the number of overtopping waves to the number of incident wave ratio). As first stated by Van der Meer and Janssen (1994) and Franco et al. (1994), the wave-by-wave overtopping volumes follow a two-parameter Weibull distribution; then, the maximum individual overtopping volume can be derived as:

$$V_{MAX} = a_{WB} \cdot [\ln(N_{OW})] \frac{1}{b_{WB}} \quad (3.131)$$

where N_{OW} is the actual number of overtopping waves, a_{WB} and b_{WB} are the Weibull's distribution scale and shape parameters, respectively. In particular, by assuming the equality of the theoretical and the measured mean overtopping volumes, the scale parameter formulation is:

$$a_{WB} = \frac{1}{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{b_{WB}}\right)} \cdot \frac{q \cdot T_m}{P_{OW}} \quad (3.132)$$

where Γ is the mathematical gamma function and T_m is the mean wave period. On the other hand, different formulation for the shape parameter have been proposed by the literature in the last two decades. However, a few studies have dealt with the overtopping volume distribution for vertical walls in shallow water (Salaudin et al., 2022; Besley et al., 1999).

Lashley et al. (2021)

The authors revisited the graphical approach of Goda et al. (1975) and modelled the flow rate as a function the relative water depth, the relative crest freeboard, the foreshore slope and the deep-water wave steepness. In particular, the presence of the seabed slope and the relative water depth ensures to adopt the deep-water conditions instead of the incident one; indeed, consistent with Hofland et al. (2017), Lashley et al. have demonstrated that the foreshore effects on wave conditions at the toe of the structure can be accounted for by means of $\tan(m)$ and h_{TOE}/H_{S0} .

By gathering three different datasets that include laboratory experiments of vertical walls with shallow foreshores and emerged toe as well, the new proposed formula reads:

$$\frac{q}{\sqrt{g \cdot H_{S0}^3}} = a \cdot \exp\left(-b \cdot \frac{R_c}{H_{S0}} + c \cdot \frac{h_{TOE}}{H_{S0}}\right) \quad (3.133)$$

where the coefficients a , b and c rely on the deep-water wave steepness and the foreshore slope and vary depending on the relative foreshore depth. Equation (3.133) is only valid for $h_{TOE}/H_{s0} < 1$.

The functional form of the coefficients is in line with existing models that use the breaker parameter (i.e. the seabed slope to the square of wave steepness ratio), while the values of their exponents have been obtained using a trial-and-error approach to minimize the scatter. By means of these coefficients, the authors express the correlation between the overtopping discharge and the wavelength (the longer the waves, the larger the flow rates); moreover, steeper foreshores lead to the overtopping discharge increases.

The overtopping model has been derived assuming a straight uniform foreshore slope, so the authors did not recommend its direct feasibility on highly irregular bathymetry. A complex foreshore can indeed significantly affect the wave transformation, increasing the uncertainties related to a deep-water-wave-based overtopping model.

Tuozzo et al. (2024)

Tuozzo et al. (2024) performed an extensive numerical experimental campaign via the non-hydrostatic model SWASH (Zijlema et al., 2011) to gather a varied and wide dataset on wave overtopping on vertical seawalls in shallow water, i.e. for $h_{TOE}/H_{s0} < 4$ according to the classification of Hofland et al. (2017). Such analysis allowed the authors to develop a unique predictive formula for breaking and non-breaking waves. Its validity has been verified with almost 200 laboratory data derived from different experimental campaigns on vertical walls in shallow waters. The new predictive formula reads:

$$\frac{q}{g \cdot h_{TOE} \cdot T_P \cdot m^{P_{sw}}} = \min \left[0.0107 \cdot \left(\frac{R_c}{\zeta_{\frac{1}{4}}} \cdot \gamma_{br} \right)^{-1.49} ; 0.068 \cdot \left(\frac{R_c}{\zeta_{\frac{1}{4}}} \cdot \gamma_{br} \right)^{-3.04} \right] \quad (3.134)$$

which adopts the new hydraulic variable recently introduced by Buccino et al. (2023), $\zeta_{\frac{1}{4}}$, namely the highest one-fourth of water elevation distribution at the structure's location. Hence, the mean flow rate depends on this water level statistic, the peak wave period T_P (instead of the spectral period commonly adopted in literature), the water depth at the toe of the wall, h_{TOE} , and the foreshore slope m . Concerning the latter, the authors proposed an equivalent slope formulation in order to apply Equation (3.147) even with complex uneven foreshore. The formula has been derived for a relative crest freeboard range included between 1 and 6. Finally, the additional parameters γ_{br} and P_{sw} , account for the transition from pulsating to impulsive wave loadings, allowing Equation (3.147) to be used for breaking and non-breaking wave conditions. Thus, they depend on the degree of stability of the waves, and their formulation read:

$$\gamma_{br} = \max \left[1; \frac{h_{TOE}}{H_{s0}} \cdot \tanh \left(10 \cdot \pi \cdot \frac{h_{TOE}}{L_{p,DEEP}} \right) \right] \quad (3.135)$$

$$P_{sw} = \frac{0.5}{\left[1 + 50 \cdot \exp \left(-10 \cdot \frac{H_{s0}}{h_{TOE}} \right) \right]} \quad (3.136)$$

Overall, the reliability of these predictive tools depends partially on the database used to calibrate them. Indeed, beyond the range of applicability, the data used to derive an empirical equation – or to develop a machine learning approach – affects, to some extent, its validity.

With the exception of Tuozzo et al. (2024), the existing predictive models discussed above have used data on vertical walls contained in the CLASH database. However, despite the remarkable size, a large part of this database is characterized by low reliability. Among the shallow water data, indeed, only 152 are labelled as “reliable”, i.e. with a Reliability Factor (RF) equal to 1 and 2. During the data collection within the CLASH project, indeed, high RF was assigned to data when all required experiment information was available in the corresponding reports, and measurements and analysis were performed reliably. Conversely, no acceptable measurements and uncertainty tests led to low RF values (i.e., 3 or 4). Moreover, just 9 out of 152 reliable data are in very shallow foreshore, with the lower value ($h_{TOE}/H_{s0} = 0.82$) near the shallow foreshore condition. Thus, the reliable data used to derive the empirical formulae seem to contain a paucity of information on the overtopping process of vertical walls in the surf zone. Such assertion is confirmed by their harmonic spectral period at the toe of the structure to the deep-water peak period ratio, which is included between 0.8 and 1.1, namely the typical value for a single-peaked wave spectrum in deep water. The latter observation makes the relationship between harmonic spectral period and flow rate suspicious, as in the surf zone the spectral period should be significantly larger than the peak period (as observed by Hofland et al., 2017) due to the presence of surf beats.

Therefore, the uncertainties related to some of the existing formulae (such as the lack of a large reliable dataset or the hydraulic variable frequently adopted), along with the paucity of information on statistical distribution of the individual volume for vertical seawall in the surf zone, highlight the necessity to deepen the knowledge about these coastal defense structures.

Figure 3.29 Sketch of a seawall.

Table 3.VIII Summary of existing formulas for the design of seawalls.

Reference	Formulas
Goda (2009)	Equation (3.124)
Mase et al. (2013)	Equations (3.125) and (3.126)
EurOtop (2018)	Equations (3.128), (3.129), (3.130), (3.131)
Lashley et al. (2021)	Equation (3.133)
Tuozzo et al. (2024)	Equation (3.134)

3.5 Design formulas for artificial beach nourishment

Beach nourishment is a soft coastal engineering approach, designed for the unique conditions of the location under consideration. Artificial beach nourishment involves adding sand or sediment to a beach to restore eroded shoreline, widening the beach, or protecting coastal structures from erosion. Beach-compatible sand is transferred from a sand source (borrow area) to the beach receiving the sand (beach fill site) by hydraulic dredging or mechanical transfer, such as trucking (Davis et al., 2018). At the beach fill site, bulldozers redistribute the deposited sand into a restored dune or berm.

Design formulas used for artificial beach nourishment are empirical equations employed by coastal engineers to determine the quantity and characteristics of sediment required for a successful nourishment project. These formulas consider various factors including wave energy, sediment transport, coastal morphology, and project objectives. This involves using design formulas for initial design, followed by physical and numerical investigations to confirm and refine design conditions on different spatial and temporal scales. Insights into the wave climate, longshore and cross-shore solid transport, and the specific characteristics of the project location are essential when designing an artificial beach nourishment project. This section focuses solely on the most widely used design formulas considered for the pre-design of the nourishment process.

There are two primary approaches used for long-term analysis: the diffusion equation (Hanson and Kraus, 1989; Hanson et al., 2002) and the equilibrium hypothesis (Capobianco et al. 2002; Kraus 2001). The equilibrium hypothesis suggests that continuous dynamic forces will lead to a stable beach shape known as the "*equilibrium beach*". Despite its limitations, this simplified approach is the predominant method worldwide for designing artificial beach nourishments. Designing a beach nourishment involves determining the required volume of nourished material and the frequency of replenishment interventions. The nourishment volume density (or unit volume) is the sand volume per unit length of the nourished beach (m^3/m). Specifically, the design profile represents the shape the fill material is expected to achieve after being subjected to waves over the first few months to a year after placement. In this context, the equilibrium beach profiles (EBPs) play a crucial role in understanding beach morphology and project design. Various models and formulations, including spiral logarithms (Yasso, 1965; Vichetpan, 1969; Silvester, 1970) and parabolic models (Hsu and Evans, 1989), have been proposed for representing EBPs in different beach environments, including tidal (Inman et al., 1993; González, 1995; Bernabeu, 1999; Medina et al., 2000; Gomez-Pina, 2001) and non-tidal beaches (Bruun, 1954; Dean, 1977; Bodge, 1992; González and Medina, 1999; Larson et al., 1999; Romaozyk et al., 2005; Requejo et al., 2005). The concept of an "*equilibrium profile*" serves as a fundamental method for analyzing beach responses to long-term wave conditions. This equilibrium profile shape is primarily governed by sediment size characteristics, as highlighted by Dean (1991). Dean's parabolic EBP hypothesis suggests that wave energy saturates at equilibrium under breaking waves, where shoreward propagating wave energy exceeding a threshold value is assumed to be dissipated by wave breaking.

Research by Bruun (1954) and Dean (1977) has demonstrated that many ocean beach profiles exhibit a concave shape, with depth varying as the two-thirds power of the distance offshore along submerged portions. The well-known equation representing this profile shape is:

$$h(x) = A_{BR} x^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad (3.137)$$

where

h = water depth at distance x from the shoreline (m)

x = distance from the shore (m)

A_{EBP} = scale parameter mainly dependent on sediment characteristics ($m^{1/3}$)

Linear shallow water wave theory establishes a relationship between the scale parameter A_{BR} , and the median grain size d_{50} . Moore (1982) correlated parameter A_{EBP} with d_{50} , indicating that larger sediment size leads to greater A_{BR} values and steeper beach slopes. Dean (1987) further refined this relationship, expressing A_{BR} as a function of fall velocity w . On a log-log plot, the relationship appears almost linear and can be represented as follows:

$$A_{EBP} = 0.067w^{0.44} \quad (3.138)$$

Subsequently, Bernabeu (1999) derived a more complex and comprehensive equilibrium profile that considers wave reflection from the beach, resulting in a bi-parabolic profile. This profile considers reflection effects in both tidal or non-tidal beaches and divided the profile in three zones as follows:

$$x = \left(\frac{h}{A_R}\right)^{3/2} + \frac{B_R}{A_R^{3/2}} h^3 \quad \text{for the surf zone profile } (0 < x < x_r) \quad (3.139)$$

$$X = x - x_0 = \left(\frac{h}{C_R}\right)^{3/2} + \frac{D_R}{C_R^{3/2}} h^3 \quad \text{for the shoaling profile } (x_r < x < x_0) \quad (3.140)$$

$$x_0 = x_r - \left(\frac{h_r}{C_R}\right)^{3/2} - \frac{D_R}{C_R^{3/2}} h_r^3 \quad \text{shoaling profile origin } (x = x_0) \quad (3.141)$$

where:

x_r = intercepting profile point (m)

h_r = water depth at the intercepting profile point (m)

x_0 = origin of the shoaling profile (m)

$A_R, B_R, C_R,$ and D_R = shape parameters that depend on wave and sediment characteristics, among which Ω

$\Omega = H_b/\omega T$ = Dimensionless fall velocity, where H_b is the wave height at breaking, ω is the angular frequency of waves, and T is the wave period.

These equations were fitted to over 50 profiles from 13 Spanish beaches, yielding relationships between shape parameters and wave or sediment characteristics. The dimensionless fall velocity (Ω) was identified as a key variable, leading to expressions for $A_R, B_R, C_R,$ and D_R within a specific range of Ω .

Various studies have explored variations in EBP for beaches affected by wave-structure interaction phenomena. Modifications to the wave momentum flux equation have been incorporated in the equations to account for these effects. For example, Requejo et al. (2005) proposed new expressions for wave energy flux in refraction-diffraction areas, while Muñoz-Pérez et al. (1999) introduced a methodology for reef-protected beaches. González et al. (2010) developed a methodology combining equilibrium shapes for nourishment projects along

Atlantic and Mediterranean coasts, considering both high- and low-tides, based on earlier work by González and Medina (2001). They concluded that while the resulting beach profile form is similar to that proposed by Dean, the shape parameter can be greater than the A_{EBP} values used in Dean (1977) and should be re-calibrated and validated for the specific project conditions.

Nevertheless, despite advancements and updates in beach nourishment design methodologies over the past two decades, the power profile by Dean (1977) continues to be preferred and widely adopted choice for designing artificial beach fills worldwide. This profile provides a straightforward and effective means of estimating beach profiles under wave action, making it a popular option among coastal engineers and designers. This formulation requires the well-known depth of closure (DoC), which delineates the seaward limit where sediment deposition ceases to significantly contribute to beach maintenance. Several formulations have been proposed by researchers to estimate the DoC (d_c), providing valuable insights for nourishment projects (e.g. Hallermeier, 1981; Birkemeier, 1985; Nicholls et al., 1996; Requejo et al., 2005). Among these formulations, the most widely used ones are Equation (3.142) proposed by Hellermeier (1981) and Equation (3.143) proposed by Birkemeier (1985), which are based on relationships involving the mean annual significant wave height (H_s) and wave period (T_s):

$$\text{Hellermeier (1978):} \quad d_c = 2.28H_s - 68.5(H_s^2 g T_s^2) \quad (3.142)$$

$$\text{Birkemeier (1985):} \quad d_c = 1.75H_s - 57.9(H_s^2 g T_s^2) \quad (3.143)$$

Additionally, the CUR (1990) provides a simplified expression to relate the DoC to the mean annual significant wave height ($H_{s,12}$), which occurs 12 hours per year on average: $d_c = 1.6H_{s,12}$.

Once the depth of closure and the size of the sand are determined, it becomes necessary to assess whether the Dean profile would yield an intersecting or nonintersecting nourished profile. Dean (1998) categorized three types of nourished profile based on the volumes added and whether the nourishment is coarser or finer than the native beach sand (Figure 3.30):

- a. intersecting profile: the nourished profile intersects the native profile landward of the depth of closure.
- b. nonintersecting profile: the nourished profile does not intersect the native profile before the closure depth.
- c. nonintersecting submerged profile: the nourished beach does not intersect the native profile, and no subaerial beach exists after equilibrium.

Figure 3.30 Sketch of an artificial beach nourishment (from Capobianco et al. 2022).

The type of profile depends on factors such as the size of the added sand relative to the native sand. An intersecting profile typically requires the added sand to be coarser than the native sand, while nonintersecting or submerged profiles arise if the sediment is of the same diameter or finer than the native sand. Determining fill volumes to achieve the design profile involves the assumption that fill material resembles native beach sediments. Design profiles based on the "equilibrium profile" concept guide fill requirements, considering initial foreshore slopes typically ranging from 1:10 to 1:15 above high-water datum, grain size distribution, and coastal processes. Material redistribution within the project's confines, typically up to the DoC, is anticipated by the profile translation method, ensuring efficient beach maintenance and restoration. Dean (1991) introduced analytical techniques for predicting beach profile responses to nourishment projects, facilitating planning and design. These methods geometrically determine the volume of fill needed to achieve a desired width of subaerial beach per unit shoreline length once profiles reach equilibrium. Material deposition on the beach redistributes over time, tending in the medium to long term to naturally assume their stable equilibrium configurations under wave actions (Verhagen, 1992).

In intersecting (Equation (3.144)) and non-intersecting profile (Equation (3.145)) conditions, relationships exist between shoreline advancement (Δy) and replenishment volume (V). Intersecting and nonintersecting profiles are determined by inequalities involving the A_N scale parameter values for native and fill sediments, and the depth of closure (d_c). A requirement for intersecting nourished profiles is for the fill material to be coarser than the native beach sediments. Nonintersecting and submerged nourished profiles require that the fill material be equal to or finer than the native material.

$$Y \left(\frac{A_N}{d_c} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} + \left(\frac{A_N}{A_F} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} < 1 \text{ (intersecting profiles)} \quad (3.144)$$

$$Y \left(\frac{A_N}{d_c} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} + \left(\frac{A_N}{A_F} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} > 1 \text{ (nonintersecting profiles)} \quad (3.145)$$

where A_N is the value of the scale parameter for the native sediments and A_F is the value of the scale parameter for the fill material, and Y the desired distance of seaward translation.

Additionally, equations are provided for determining the volume of fill needed to achieve desired beach dimensions, considering differences in sediment grain size between native and fill materials. For circumstances where the fill material is similar to the native beach sediments (i.e. $A_F = A_N$), the volume (V) of fill required could be determined using the equation presented in the CERC (1984):

$$V = (B_h + d_c)Y \quad (3.146)$$

where B_{CERC} is the desired berm height (m) and Y the desired distance of seaward translation (m).

For situations where the fill material is finer than the native sediments (i.e. $A_F < A_N$), a critical volume of fill is required for any subaerial beach to form after equilibrium. The volume for a nonintersecting profile is determined by the following equation:

$$V = \frac{3}{5} d_c^{\frac{5}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{A_N} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{A_N}{A_F} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{A_N}{A_F} - 1 \right) \quad (3.147)$$

If the amount of fill placed is less than that determined using the nonintersecting profile equation, the nourished profile will be submerged. The volume (V) required for satisfying conditions for a submerged profile is given by the following equation:

$$V = YB_{CERC} + \frac{3}{5} d_c^{\frac{5}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{Y}{H^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \left(\frac{1}{A_F} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \right)^{\frac{5}{3}} A_N - \left(\frac{1}{A_N} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \right] \quad (3.148)$$

Similarly, if the fill material is coarser than the native material (i.e. $A_F > A_N$), a small quantity of fill material will be required to widen the beach. The volume (V) of fill required to achieve design dimensions satisfying the conditions of an intersecting nourished profile is given by the following equation:

$$V = YB_{CERC} + \frac{A_N Y^{\frac{5}{3}}}{\left[1 - \left(\frac{A_N}{A_F} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \right]} \quad (3.149)$$

Furthermore, the design of the replenishment intervention also requires some “safety” factors considered in the equations to design with a based confidence level. In the CEM (USACE, 2002) several methodologies for calculating the fill factor (R_A), which indicates the required surplus volume, and the renourishment factor (R_f), indicating renourishment frequency are given and discussed. These calculations consider differences in grain size between native and fill sands.

An all-encompassing design method for artificial beach nourishment, including all relevant parameters, is not currently available. Most widely used pre-design formulas date back to 1980s-1990s and do not consider the high uncertainties related to the effects of climate change. Various design tools are accessible for different aspects of beach nourishment design, including models for the prediction the morphological behavior of the fill (such as one-line, two-line and field model), as well as methods for determining grain size characteristics and profile shape. On the other hand, the empirical equation proposed by Dean is based on the hypothesis that beaches maintain equilibrium profile when sea level does not rise. Indeed, when this aspect occurs, the beach profile spreads towards offshore, and shoreline tends to retreat landward without additional sand input to the beach under rising sea level. In order to maintain the beach equilibrium profile facing future sea level rise, the entire beach profile would have to increase vertically with the same amount of sea level rise (Astrid, 2010; Cooper et al., 2013). Based on this, Yoshida et al. (2014) developed a new formula to consider the necessary additional sand volumes due to SLR effects. This formula is:

$$V_p = S_N Y_0 + \int_0^{W^*} \left(A_{EBP} y^{\frac{2}{3}} + S_n \right) dy - \int_0^{W^*} \left(A_{EBP} y^{\frac{2}{3}} \right) dy \quad (3.150)$$

where V_p is the profile change volume (m^3/m), Y_0 is the dry beach width, S_N is the height of beach nourishment, i.e. the amount of vertical increase of equilibrium profile to maintain the beach width to be protected, Y^* , and W^* is the cross-shore distance to closure the depth d_{c^*} .

The amount of vertical increase of equilibrium profile S_N can be equated as follows:

$$S_N = SLR - \left(\frac{d_{c^*} + B_h}{W^*} \right) (Y_0 - Y^*) \quad (3.151)$$

SLR is the sea level rise, d_{c^*} is the closure depth and B_h is the berm height. The amount of sea level rise after beach nourishment causes a permissible retreat ($Y_0 - Y^*$) after the profile increases the amount of S_N . V_p is the additional profile volume for preventing future beach width from being narrower than Y^* , while this nourishment allows shoreline to be retreated when the future beach width becomes wider than the beach width of step 2 after sea level rises. The closure depth d_{c^*} is given by the equation from Hallermeier (1981). The berm height B_h is given by the equation mentioned by Takeda and Sunamura (1983):

$$B_h = 0.125 H_b^{\frac{5}{8}} (g T_s^2)^{\frac{3}{8}} \quad (3.152)$$

where H_b is the breaker wave height given by the equation of Sunamura (1983) and T_s is the significant wave period. The data used in this framework are sea level rise, waves, grain size and foreshore slope. This framework only takes into consideration the impact of sea level rise on the coast without considering existing erosion. Determining beach width required for disaster prevention must therefore be integrated with evaluation of risks associated to other forms of coastal erosion in order to improve this framework.

In this section, an extensive overview of the most popular design formulas for artificial design of beach nourishment has been carried out. However, it must be clear that it is crucial for designers to be cognizant of specific regulations and guidelines applicable to the project country or region.

Different locations may have unique environmental considerations, regulatory requirements, and project objectives that can influence the selection of appropriate design formulas and methodologies. Consulting existing regulations and guidelines is mandatory to ensure that the chosen design approach aligns with local environmental policies, ecological concerns, and coastal management strategies. By adhering to these regulations and guidelines, designers can develop sustainable and environmentally responsible beach nourishment projects tailored to the specific needs and conditions of each location.

4. Adaptation solutions of existing coastal and harbor defense structures

4.1 Overview

Aging of coastal and harbor defense solutions is a worldwide problem, which nowadays goes along with the need of upgrading for protection against the effects of climate change on coastal areas (Hughes, 2014; Toimil et al., 2020). In this context, the present chapter provides a summary of adaptation solutions of existing rubble-mound breakwaters, vertical breakwaters, seawalls and beach nourishments, which have been already realized or are under design.

4.2 Adaptation of existing rubble-mound breakwaters

Most historical coastal and harbor breakwaters worldwide have suffered severe damage from extreme sea storms during their lifetime and require upgrading, particularly considering the impacts of climate change (Hughes, 2014). Considering rubble-mound structures, special attention must be paid to harbor breakwaters, because the impossibility to fulfill the design requirements would have significant economic and social impacts, above all if national interest and strategic ports are considered. The aging of harbor defense structures is a global issue, necessitating urgent maintenance and upgrades, especially due to projected intensification of external loading from climate change effects (Isobe 2013; Burcharth et al. 2014; Toimil et al. 2020). In particular, Italy boasts a huge number of historical harbor breakwaters, which have been modified during their lifetime to repair damages caused by wave load or to increase the hydraulic performances to allow the growth of the port.

Despite the practical relevance of the matter concerning the upgrade of aging coastal and harbor breakwaters, few research has been carried out, which mainly consists in design exercises using only desk study tools (Burcharth et al., 2014) and in the definition of experience-based or theoretical methods for the selection of the most suitable upgrading options on the basis of the characteristics of the existing breakwater (Croeneveld et al., 1985; Foti et al., 2020). Some investigations on implemented upgrading projects are available, that however only describe design procedures, neither defining specific formulas for the design of upgrading options nor testing the adequacy of the traditional equations for newly built structures (Ligteringen et al 1993; Reis et al., 2011; Santos-Ferreira et al., 2015; Main et al., 2016; Jensen et al 2018). Research projects such as THESEUS¹¹ and CCSEAWAVS¹² have focused on studying vulnerability, resilience, and environmentally friendly upgrading solutions for coastal structures in the face of climate changes. However, the design of upgrading solutions for existing rubble-mound breakwaters poses challenges due to uncertainties regarding their current state, external hydrodynamic loading conditions, and the empirical nature of formulas describing wave-structure interaction. Furthermore, the lack of standardized methodologies and knowledge about adaptation of existing breakwaters complicates the entire process.

Reliability-based approaches would significantly contribute to handling the problem posed by balancing the compromises and investments made on the side of the defense system, due to

¹¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/244104>

¹² <http://thalis-ccseawavs.web.auth.gr/en/>

increased safety levels, with the accompanying benefits (limiting losses) in the protected areas. Reliability-based approaches, such as the one proposed by Koftis et al. (2015) and Galiatsatou et al. (2018), offer a framework for upgrading coastal and harbor rubble-mound breakwaters against climate change, considering both safety levels and economic optimization.

Great part of the historical coastal and harbor defense structures is in shallow waters and consists of non-conventional breakwaters, which have been repeatedly modified over the years and usually converted into rubble-mound structures (Lara et al., 2019). Therefore, traditional empirical design formulas defined for new structures may be not able to properly characterize the hydraulic behavior of both damaged and restored breakwaters, whose actual composition in terms of material and layers geometry is often unknown, because of the lack of documents and reports regarding the modifications implemented during their lifetime. As regards the available numerical models, they have not been sufficiently calibrated to simulate all the common restoration concepts, particularly concerning the stability of the armor layer (Burcharth et al., 2014; Lara et al., 2019). As a consequence, physical modeling represents the most reliable approach not only to describe the response of existing or upgraded rubble-mound structures and their possible failure modes, but also to calibrate existing or new numerical models. The integration and combination of physical and numerical models to analyze complex hydraulic problems is known in the literature as composite modeling (Guanche et al. 2015). Such an approach allows to overcome the lack of specific formulations for upgraded structures and the intrinsic limits of physical modeling (e.g., scale effects, too invasive measurement instruments, difficulties in the repeatability of the tests), in terms of both stability of the armor layer and wave overtopping.

Starting from the available state of art, a summary of the main phases for the selection of the best upgrading options for a certain existing harbor breakwater is here presented. The choice of the most suitable upgrading solutions for existing rubble-mound breakwaters must be addressed considering several factors (Croeneveld et al., 1985; Burcharth et al., 2014; Foti et al., 2020). First, a field survey is required to assess the magnitude of the damage and identify its possible causes, in order to avoid the failure of the restored breakwater for the same reasons. Then, the required structure performances and acceptable risk of failure must be fixed, on the basis of the structure function (e.g. coastal or harbor defense) and economic relevance. Furthermore, the geometric characteristics of the breakwater and the local topography must be considered, together with specific environmental restrictions which could influence the design. Finally, the available materials, equipment and financial resources play a fundamental role for the evaluation of the economic and technical feasibility of different upgrading options.

On the basis of the above-mentioned factors, four main repair methods are usually contemplated for the upgrade of damaged rubble-mound breakwaters (Croeneveld et al., 1985): i) addition of units of the same type of the existing ones, eventually reinforced or slightly greater to increase their weight; ii) replacement of the entire armor layer, removing all the original units; iii) reconstruction of the rubble-mound structure, replacing not only the original armor layer, but also the underlayers; iv) provision of a low-crested or submerged toe berm or detached breakwater to reduce the wave impact on the existing structure. In addition, a shallow foreshore in front of the structure can be constructed or added (nourishment). If the adaptation of existing rubble-mound breakwaters to the effects of climate change is considered, the above-mentioned upgrading strategies can be applied with some tricks to face the increased external forcing. For

instance, the overtopping rates can be reduced by heightening the existing wave wall or by the construction of a new one. Furthermore, besides the addition of a submerged toe berm or detached breakwater, if the construction of an extra or totally new armor layer is considered, the rise of the structure crest level to reduce the overtopping discharges or the reduction of the seaside slope to limit wave runup and increase the armor layer stability can be designed, as showed in Figure 4.1 (Burcharth et al., 2014; Foti et al., 2020).

Figure 4.1 Examples of concepts for upgrading rubble-mound breakwaters: a) extra armor layer to increase height and stability of the existing structure; b) extra flatter armor layer to limit the impact of the wave motion and increase the structure stability; c) additional submerged breakwater to limit the impact of the wave motion on the existing structure. Source: Foti et al. (2020).

The selection of the blocks for the armor layer restoration is a difficult issue, because there is a lack of in-depth investigations on the interaction between the existing units and the additional ones. In this regard, Carver (1989) provided an inventory of existing US Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) projects that have used dissimilar armor blocks for repair and rehabilitation of rubble-mound coastal breakwaters. The results of the survey showed that in 1989 only the 24% of the considered districts had experienced the use armor units different from the existing ones for the armor layer restoration, thus highlighting the necessity to perform further systematic experimental studies for the evaluation of the interfacing and stability response of different armor blocks. Currently, the only guidance for the choice of shape and size of the additional armor units comes from traditional formulations for new constructions, prototype experience, engineering judgment, inferences from model tests of similar structures, or site-specific model tests. The use of additional armor units heavier than the existing ones could be considered if the present structure appears undersized with respect to the design wave action, in the absence of technical or practical limitations (Croeneveld et al., 1985). Instead, to the best of the author's knowledge, the use of additional armor units smaller (i.e. lighter) than the existing ones, which could be contemplated to fill the voids of the damaged breakwater with limited movements of the present blocks, has not been investigated yet. Certainly, in this case the structural response of the whole armor layer to the design wave load must be evaluated by means of physical model tests. The same applies to the use of units with different interlocking level than the existing ones,

for which special attention on the regularization of the laying surface and on the zones of transition should be paid.

The problem lies in the absence of a standard procedure capable of aiding the designer in selecting the best options specifically for the projects in a probabilistic manner. Methods like adaptation pathways, as described by van Gent and Teng (2023), provide a systematic approach to selecting adaptation measures for rubble-mound breakwaters, considering uncertain future sea-level rise. The methodology is focused on adaptation measures to fulfil design criteria for wave overtopping discharges. Once the attention is focused on the problem, adaptation to the breakwaters can be achieved in several ways, and there would be a hierarchical scheme to find the best solution.

Recently, Stagnitti et al. (2022a, b, 2024) proposed a new methodology for the upgrading of harbor rubble-mound breakwaters in the context of climate change. The case study was the Catania Harbor breakwater. The methodology requires the actual state of degradation of rubble-mound breakwater, the statical definition of hydrodynamic conditions, and the evaluation of the probability of failure of upgraded structures. The assessment of existing breakwater degradation can now be facilitated by diachronic analysis of georeferenced field data using GIS technology, along with advancements in UAV technology for 3D modeling. Additionally, new approaches to defining hydrodynamic conditions, considering the stochastic nature of variables and climate change effects, are emerging. Once upgrading solutions are designed, evaluating their probability of failure is crucial. Rubble-mound breakwaters can fail due to various factors, including armor layer and toe berm stability, overtopping volumes, wave wall resistance, or soil solidity. Comparing the probability of failure for different upgrading solutions can help select the most appropriate options.

In the '70s and '80s several restoration projects for damaged rubble-mound breakwaters using armor units both equal and different from the existing ones were documented in the USA (Carver, 1989). Among the most recent rubble-mound breakwaters upgrades, the rehabilitation of Sines west breakwater in Portugal deserves to be mentioned (Reis et al., 2011). Between 1978 and 1979, when the construction of the breakwater was nearly complete, extreme sea storms caused failure of almost the entire 42 t Dolosse armor layer and superstructure. Subsequent to the failure, which was most probably a consequence of a combination of different factors (i.e. shortcomings in the selection of design waves, deficiency in project management, differences between the constructed breakwater and the design specifications, low structural strength of Dolosse, physical removal by wave action of the toe stones, incompleteness of the construction), studies were undertaken by several hydraulic laboratories. The scope of such investigations was to analyze the stability and, in some cases, the overtopping of different solutions for the rehabilitation of the Sines west breakwater using Antifer cubes, also considering the reactivation of berths 1, 2 and 3. The final restoration, which implies the reactivation of berth 1, was designed on the basis of the experience gained with the previous rehabilitation works, also using the same materials, and it was tested in laboratory for the analysis of stability and overtopping for each of the proposed solutions.

The north breakwater of Nazaré Harbor, which is another Portuguese rubble-mound breakwater originally made of Tetrapod units, was severely damaged during the winter of 2013-2014 and its head and first section were completely destroyed (Santos-Ferreira et al., 2015). Since the main

damage observed in the northern breakwater was probably caused by the increased significant wave height, the rehabilitation solution was designed considering a higher design wave height and Antifer blocks were chosen for their greater robustness and weight with reference to the Tetrapods.

The Coffs Harbor Northern Breakwater in Australia was subjected to excessive rates of overtopping discharge, which represent a risk to human life, vessels and infrastructure and hence the upgrading project was developed (Main et al., 2016). The feasibility study was elaborated by the Australian Department of Industry (Lands) and GHD (one of the world's leading professional services companies operating in the global market sectors of water, energy and resources, environment, property and buildings, and transportation). Given the unique set of constraints and opportunities presented by the Northern Breakwater and surrounds, balanced technical, social, environmental and economic outcomes were achieved not only by means of innovative technical design solutions, but also by means of innovative and transparent approaches to engaging the community, local industry, gaining environmental approvals and support from other stakeholders. The preferred option was a composite armored berm upgrade, which consists of a layer of three-legged concrete armor units called Hanbar, to be constructed on top of a newly built rock berm extending from the seaward side of the existing structure at mean sea level. Furthermore, the widening and the rising of the crest of the breakwater along the eastern portion of the structure was planned. Having undertaken a comprehensive options development and evaluation exercise, Lands was able to proceed directly to physical modeling, with confidence that the preferred option represented the solution that offered the best value for money. UNSW's Water Research Laboratory (WRL) undertook the 3D physical modeling, which provided a more accurate simulation of wave processes in the nearshore area and verified the results from the Neural Network tool for assessment of overtopping. The findings of the physical modeling exercise were used to develop the detailed design and included a number of refinements during testing. Finally, a revised breakwater upgrade design was developed to minimize the environmental impacts of the upgrade works.

The cube-armored outer breakwater of the Port of Catania in Western Sicily (Italy) appears severely damaged due to its obsolescence, and it is no more able to ensure wave overtopping discharges compatible with port operations. In order to improve the degraded hydraulic performances of the outer breakwater of the Port of Catania, the Port Authority of the Eastern Sicily Sea started the procedure for the strengthening of the current armor layer. The design of the upgrading solution of the outer breakwater was strongly supported by the scientific contribution of the Department of Civil Engineering and Architecture (DICAr) of the University of Catania, which performed both physical and numerical tests for the assessment of the response of different upgrading options to wave actions. During the detailed design phase, the response of six upgrading configurations to wave action was experimentally investigated, with reference to two representative cross-sections (Stagnitti et al., 2020, 2023b). The choice to consider different cross-sections was due not only to the need for testing the profanes of portions of the breakwater exposed to different wave magnitude, but also to account for the lack of geometric homogeneity along the existing structure, which influences the response of the latter as well as the design of possible upgrading solutions. The rising of the wave wall and the addition of extra armor units equal to or smaller than the existing ones according to different placement patterns were selected as possible upgrades of the breakwater. The analysis of the

experimental results revealed that the only upgrading solution that generated both reduction of wave overtopping and minimization of the cumulative damage of the outer armor layer despite of the geometry of considered cross-section was the one that consisted in the addition of 62 tons cubes equal to the existing units over the properly reshaped armor layer following the 2:1 design slope up to the crest level at +8.80 m above MSL, with a quarry stone toe berm to support the extra armor layer and the wave wall at +9.50 m above MSL. This is because the preliminary reshaping of the existing armor layer ensures a similar laying surface for the additional armor blocks at each considered cross-section. The effectiveness of the upgrading configuration was verified by running numerical simulations for the comparison with the existing structure (Castiglione et al., 2023; Stagnitti et al., 2023a), as well as by performing probabilistic calculation for the assessment of the structure reliability under present and future climate scenarios (Stagnitti et al., 2022a, b, 2024). Therefore, the best-performing upgrading solution identified through the analysis of the experimental campaign was proposed as the basis for the detailed design of the upgrading solution of the Catania outer breakwater. The executive design of the upgrade of the outer breakwater is currently ongoing, supported by new experimental and numerical investigations.

In conclusion, this section emphasizes the importance of adapting existing rubble-mound breakwaters to mitigate the impacts of climate change and ensure the long-term resilience of coastal breakwaters. However, it is evident that, to the authors' knowledge, a rigorous standardized and fully validated methodology to aid the designer in the process is not present worldwide. New efforts should be provided to improve the methods and integrate them into existing regulations and guidelines, presenting a systematic framework for identifying, evaluating, and implementing adaptation measures tailored to the specific challenges faced by these structures.

4.3 Adaptation of existing vertical breakwaters

Sea level rise and increasing intensity of extreme events related to climate change pose new challenges for vertical breakwaters. Since these structures are of fundamental importance for the protection of coastlines and port infrastructure, adaptation of existing vertical breakwaters is essential to ensure their functionality and safety over time. This chapter analyzes the main issues affecting vertical breakwaters and proposes adaptation strategies based on current knowledge and innovative technologies. Vertical breakwaters, while providing effective protection from the impact of high waves, suffer from specific failure modes due to concentrated wave impact (Takahashi, 2002). The difficulty in repairing such structures places more attention on the design phase, although there are several adaptive solutions to improve the dissipation efficiency of wave energy impinging on the existing structures. The interventions that could be carried out include the consolidation of the foundation embankment using cement or nanosilica injections (Leone, 2021), the addition of a crowning wall for protection against overtopping (Allsop et al., 2005), the installation of dissipative barriers or rocks cast reinforcement in front of the structure that can dissipate wave energy before it reaches the main structure (Lazzaro et al., 2024), and the use of connecting spanners between the various longitudinal elements of the vertical breakwater, suitable for distributing the wave impact load (De Girolamo, 1997).

Unlike rubble-mound breakwaters, vertical breakwaters are particularly vulnerable to structural failure due to the intense and localized pressures exerted by breaking waves. The interaction

between storm waves and a vertical surface result in impact forces that are considerably higher than those observed in sloped structures. This makes vertical breakwaters more prone to cracking, displacement, and even partial collapse if subjected to extreme conditions without adequate protection. Moreover, sea level rise exacerbates the overtopping problem, increasing the frequency and intensity of events in which waves exceed the crest of the structure. This leads to erosion of the rear side, flooding of protected areas, and long-term structural degradation.

To respond to these challenges, three main categories of adaptation strategies can be identified: foundation stabilization, structural enhancement, and wave energy dissipation measures. Foundation stabilization aims to counteract potential settlement or failure due to erosion and scouring. Techniques such as jet grouting, as well as cement or nanosilica injections into the subsoil, can significantly increase the bearing capacity and resistance of the foundation materials (Leone, 2021). Structural enhancement interventions are focused on improving the vertical breakwater's resistance to overtopping and impact forces. Among the most effective solutions are the installation of a new crown wall or the raising of the existing one to reduce overtopping discharges, and the implementation of longitudinal reinforcements such as connecting spanners to improve structural integrity and distribute impact loads more evenly across the breakwater's surface.

In addition to structural and foundational modifications, a highly promising approach involves the addition of energy-dissipating features on the seaward side of the structure. These include armor layers or rock revetments that can absorb and dissipate a significant portion of the incoming wave energy before it reaches the vertical wall. Alternatively, specially designed wave barriers, such as perforated plates or submerged obstacles, may be installed in front of the breakwater to break incoming waves and reduce dynamic pressure on the main structure (Lazzaro et al., 2024).

In conclusion, the adaptation of vertical breakwaters represents a critical component of coastal defense strategies in the context of climate change. Despite the progress made in recent years, further efforts are needed to provide engineers and decision-makers with reliable tools, validated methodologies, and practical guidelines for assessing, designing, and implementing adaptation interventions. As sea levels continue to rise and storm patterns evolve, ensuring the resilience of vertical breakwaters will be essential to protecting coastal communities, harbor operations, and critical infrastructure worldwide.

4.4 Adaptation of existing for seawalls

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the Global Mean Sea Level is destined to significantly rise in the future. Based on the projections on future greenhouse gas concentration (RCP), the UN's Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has predicted an increase in Global Mean Sea Level ranging between 0.29 m and 1.10 m by the end of the century (Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate, SROCC 2019). At the same time, several studies (e.g. Reguero et al., 2019) have issued that the future increase in the Sea Surface Temperature (SST) may lead the energy of waves to grow by 32% to 122% by 2100 compared to 1985-2000. Nevertheless, the worsening of the wave extremes will likely save the Mediterranean Basin, as suggested by Lira Loarca et al. (2021).

Irrespectively, a severe increase in the number and magnitude of overtopping events is expected, which will undermine the stability and serviceability of most existing measures for coastal protection.

As far as seawalls are concerned, a possible pathway to counteract the overtopping excess is the use of rubble mound dampers, either as toe structures or detached low-crested/submerged breakwaters (LCB), which dissipate part of the incoming wave energy before reaching the wall. Depending on the desired overtopping reduction, the cross-sectional width of the dampers can be remarkable.

Unfortunately, however, there is an almost total lack of design standards for those integrated seawall systems, which drives engineers toward irrational and anti-economical solutions. Recent research works (Tuozzo et al., 2022; Di Leo et al., 2024) have shown that the procedure proposed in the EurOtop Manual (2018) to calculate the mean overtopping rate of a vertically composite upright section cannot be extended to protected seawalls due to the significant difference in the volume of the rubble mounds. Moreover, there are no design guidelines for LCB-protected walls, nor on the effects of the rubble mound structures on the distribution of the individual overtopping volumes.

At the current stage of research, integrated seawall systems represent an interesting gap to fill in the years to come.

4.5 Adaptation of existing artificial beach nourishment

Beaches play important roles in disaster prevention, recreational use, and nurturing unique ecosystems. Beach nourishment can maintain the position of the shoreline and the natural environment. However, applying artificial nourishment to the whole beach area is not a practical method due to high costs and the large quantity of sand required. There has been no framework for effective adaptation of beach nourishment to solve coastal erosion issues. Over time, the effectiveness of artificial beach nourishment may diminish due to natural processes such as wave action, storms, or changes in sediment transport patterns, particularly exacerbated by the effects of climate change. With the change in wave characteristics due to climate change presenting another concern, such as the growth of wave height due to extreme storms. The future shoreline would retreat due to sea level rise and the increase in wave heights during storms, which consequently, would cause harmful impacts on socioeconomics in coastal regions as 10% of the world's population live in low-lying coastal regions within 10 m above the present sea level (McGranahan et al. 2007). Sandy beaches play important roles in disaster prevention with existing unique ecosystems and recreational use, they can dissipate wave energy, preventing waves from overtopping coastal defenses therefore decreasing the force of incoming waves.

It is necessary to consider adapting beaches for recreational use to maintain ecosystems and prevent disasters. To make an adaptation against beach erosion, evaluation of the possible impacts due to sea level rise and climate change and associated beach erosion should be carried out. Examples of recent proposed adaptations based on the impact assessments include periodic beach nourishment, associated with breakwaters and dune afforestation, which could protect tourist resorts from erosion and inundation risks (Snoussi et al., 2008). Stabilization and accretion of the beach requires artificial beach nourishments (Marcinkowski et al., 2013). It is

ideal to maintain beaches without hard structures considering beach benefits for disaster prevention, environment conservation and recreational use. Applying beach nourishment to the whole beach area is not a practical method because of its high cost and large sand quantities (Cooper et al., 2012). In such context, it was observed that adaptation and upgrading methods are suggested to maintain and improve the effectiveness of existing artificial beach nourishment projects. Here are reported some common methods:

- monitoring and evaluation: regular monitoring the beach profile, sediment transport, and shoreline changes is essential for identifying areas experiencing erosion or requiring additional nourishment. This data helps inform decisions about the timing and extent of future nourishment activities. Among the other methods, video-monitoring systems have become widely used all around the world in coastal monitoring strategies, allowing both high temporal and spatial sampling frequency, with low logistics and costs efforts (Valentini et al., 2017a,b). Moreover, conducting detailed Beach profile surveys (BPS) using techniques like laser scanning or GPS-based surveys provides accurate data on the shape and volume of the beach. This information guides the design of nourishment projects and helps assess their effectiveness over time.
- incremental nourishment: rather than waiting for significant erosion to occur, implementing smaller-scale nourishment projects at regular intervals can help maintain the beach's profile and reduce the need for large-scale interventions later. This approach minimizes disruptions to beach users and reduces costs over the long term.
- advanced engineering techniques: using advanced combined “soft” engineering techniques, such as Beach Drainage Systems (BDS) (Aristodemo et al. 2011; Saponieri et al. (2018)) or the use of geotextile tubes or offshore sediment sources, can enhance the effectiveness and longevity of beach nourishment projects (Saponieri, 2018);
- dune restoration and stabilization: enhancing natural dune systems or creating artificial dunes can provide additional protection against erosion and storm damage. Planting green solutions such as native vegetation on dunes helps stabilize the sand and promotes dune growth, contributing to the overall resilience of the beach ecosystem. The most recent contribution in literature refer to the resilience of vegetated coastal dunes (Sigren et al., 2014; Ayat and Kobayashi, 2015; Martinez et al., 2016; Ajedegba et al., 2019), and to hybrid coastal protection structures (Wamsely et al., 2010; Spalding et al., 2014; Figlus et al., 2015) but also to eco-consolidation dunes with use of environmentally friendly techniques (D’alessandro et al., 2020; Leone et al., 2021);
- structural measures: to limit sediment losses during intervention lifetime, nourishment works are frequently combined with hard coastal defense structures, since they reduce sediment spreading and lengthen the time span between periodic re-nourishments for coastal restoration. These measures should be carefully designed to minimize adverse impacts on coastal processes and neighboring beaches. To reduce such impacts on environment, submerged breakwaters are widely used as shore protection system aimed at preventing shoreline retreat;
- sand bypass systems: restore natural sediment flow disrupted by coastal structures, helping to maintain a natural sediment balance and reducing the need for frequent nourishment;
- ecological engineering: integrate ecological principles into coastal management strategies to enhance the resilience of beach ecosystems. This may include creating or

restoring coastal wetlands, which serve as natural buffers against erosion and provide habitat for diverse plant and animal species. Incorporating ecological features into beach nourishment projects can improve their overall effectiveness and sustainability;

- community engagement and stakeholder collaboration: engaging local communities, stakeholders, and beach users in the planning and implementation of beach nourishment projects is crucial for ensuring their long-term success. Community input can help identify priorities, address concerns, and build support for adaptation and upgrading efforts. Stakeholder collaboration also facilitates the sharing of resources and expertise, leading to more effective and integrated coastal management solutions. Besides implementing adaptive management strategies allows flexibility in responding to changing environmental conditions and uncertainties associated with beach nourishment projects. Adjustment based on new information or monitoring efforts optimize project effectiveness;
- climate change adaptation strategies: incorporate strategies to address rising sea levels and increasing storm intensity into beach nourishment projects to address these challenges. This may involve incorporating sea level rise projections into project design, implementing shoreline setback policies to accommodate future erosion, and integrating nature-based solutions that enhance coastal resilience in the face of climate-related impacts;
- financial planning and funding mechanisms: securing adequate funding for ongoing monitoring, maintenance, and future nourishment activities is essential for the long-term success of artificial beach nourishment projects. Developing sustainable funding mechanisms, such as dedicated beach preservation funds, user fees, or public-private partnerships, ensures that resources are available to adapt and upgrade existing projects as needed.

For beach fill projects, three-dimensional movable bed models are needed to simulate onshore-offshore and alongshore motions, and vertical movements within the water column. Physical modeling faces challenges due to scale effects, but with consideration, it can provide useful design information. Moreover, recently, numerous numerical models have been developed to predict shoreline and beach evolution. These models can be applied to the formulation and design of beach fill projects. With proper application, these models can be used to efficiently evaluate the performance of alternative project designs and to evaluate the effects of design constraints on project performance. A major advantage of the numerical modeling approach is that once the model is set up and calibrated, design changes can be evaluated efficiently. Climate change effects on wave climate are very important in determining the stability and longevity of a beach fill. On maritime shores, the water levels are changed by periodic storm surges, which are known to result in major damage. Besides, the effect of climate change must be considered in upgrading artificial nourishments. Yoshida et al. (2014) proposed a framework for beach nourishment as an adaptation to beach erosion induced by SLR for all Japanese coastlines. Their framework was based on future beach width resulting from SLR and it aimed to specify vulnerable beach areas and estimate the sand volume and costs required to maintain beach width to satisfy different beach functions. Similarly, Somphong et al. (2020) developed a framework for beach nourishment as an adaptation method to future sandy beach loss owing to sea-level rise in Thailand to be used as guideline for coastal management planning to deal with SLR.

5. Conclusions

Coastal areas, which are extremely vulnerable environments hosting unique ecosystems and intense socio-economic activities, are threatened by the impacts of climate change. Therefore, new defense solutions and the maintenance of existing ones are strongly required to reduce coastal risk and mitigate effects of coastal erosion and flooding, as well as protect harbors from excessive wave loads and overtopping. Indeed, magnitude and frequency of extreme sea storms are gradually increasing, thus reducing the efficacy of coastal defense solutions, which prove to be inadequate or even face the risk of failure also during short duration, but highly energetic, events. As a consequence, the adaptation of existing coastal and harbor defense works is often required, in order to ensure the protection of coastal areas. The design of new solutions, the adaptation of existing ones as well as the maintenance activities should be performed following a probabilistic approach, able to deal with uncertainties related not only to the stochastic nature of external forcing in a changing climate but also to the complexity of wave-structure-sediment interaction, and the lack of knowledge about geometry and materials of existing structures.

In this context, the present document provides a critical review of existing state of art on the three following topics:

1. weakness and strength of existing guidelines and recommendations for the design of coastal and harbor defense solutions;
2. existing design formulas for the description of failure mechanisms of coastal and harbor defense solutions;
3. adaptation of existing coastal and harbor defense solutions to the effects of climate change.

In particular, four kinds of coastal and harbor defense solutions have been considered, namely rubble-mound breakwaters, vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments.

The presented critical review highlights that design methodologies for coastal and harbor defense solutions currently employed in Italy are based on deterministic approaches, which, contrary to probabilistic methods, are not able to deal with the uncertainty due to the complex interaction between waves and defense solution, to the unknown nature of the existing structures, as well as to the effects of climate change on met-ocean climate. Moreover, existing design formulas only consider newly built defense solutions, which are not always applicable to unconventional upgraded structures. Finally, the current knowledge on the upgrading of existing defense solutions is mainly based on reports and scientific papers describing real case studies or proposing methodologies for specific conditions, without providing an integrated approach to be followed for the assessment of the state of the existing structure to the choice of the best upgrading option and its construction, in the context of climate change.

Therefore, further research is needed to extend the application of existing probabilistic methodologies to both harbor and coastal defense solutions, and to include in the design phase a multivariate-based risk analysis with the implementation of analytical and numerical models suitable for predicting coastal dynamic effects induced by extreme events under climate change conditions. Moreover, new design tools should be defined to facilitate design, planning and

decision-making. In this framework, PROMETEO will introduce a new probabilistic framework which includes all the above-mentioned issues.

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